

Supplementary Materials: Restorative materials health outcomes

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Amalgam vs Composite resin

Table 1: Amalgam vs Composite - adverse events

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Adverse events: Adverse events reported during 5yr follow-up (N)	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 132 (49.4) vs 122 (45.7) p=.44
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Adverse event: Adverse health events (N)	Amalgam: 4 adverse events (1 death due to unintentional gunshot, 1 death due to hepatitis, brain aneurysm, kidney stones) vs Composite: 5 adverse events (2 diagnosed epilepsy, 1 hyperthyroidism, 1 asthma, 1 psychiatric hospitalization)
Study quality: Strong (green shade). N=Number, NECAT=New England Children's Amalgam Trial, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, yr=Year			

Table 2: Amalgam vs Composite - general physical health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs CR	General physical health: Weakness, fatigue, edema, during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 6 (2.3) vs 6 (2.3) p>.99
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs CR	General physical health: Migraine: Migraine occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 16 (6.0) vs 14 (5.2) p=.85
Roberts 2008 [Subset RCT Casa Pia- followed only amalgam arm (prospective cohort)] ³	Amalgam vs CR	General physical health: Urinary bacteria (N)	Numbers bacteria on the supplemented media similar in two groups over 9 visits. NS differences between groups in proportions of children with positive growth or numbers of bacteria that grew on unsupplemented/supplemented media. Adjustment for covariates: odds of having Hgr bacteria slightly lower in Amalgam vs Composite group (OR 0.96, 95% CI 0.69, 1.33), though not statistically significant (p=.82)
Study quality: Strong (green shade). CI=Confidence Interval, CR=Composite Resin, Hg=Mercury, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, NECAT=New England's Amalgam Trial, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, RBC=Resin Based Composite, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, yrs=Years			

Table 3: Amalgam vs Composite - immune function

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Maserejian 2014 (Dental sealants and composite restorations) [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁴	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: B-Cell activation, %CD69 + PW, %CD23	Changes in B-cell responsiveness greater throughout follow-up among children with bisGMA-based composite restorations, which opposed findings for amalgam treatment levels. Present no.bisGMA-based standard composite restorations associated with increased B-cell activation markers over follow-up (B-cell %CD69+PWM, $\beta=1.7$, 95% CI: 0.6,2.7; %CD23+PWM, $\beta=2.2$, 95% CI:0.5,4.0). In contrast, for amalgam, both B-cell markers indicated decreases in responsiveness since baseline (B-cell %CD69+PWM, $\beta=-2.1$, 95% CI:-3.8,-0.4; %CD23+PWM, $\beta=-3.8$, 95% CI:-6.2,-1.4)
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Distribution of lymphocytes, monocytes and neutrophils	No consistent or significant difference between and within treatment groups at 5-7 days, 6mnths, 12mnths, 60mnths post-treatment based on ANCOVA models. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Responsiveness T-cells (Activation markers CD69/CD25)	NS difference between groups. No differences consistently observed at 6,12 or 60mnths. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Proliferative responses T-cells	NS difference between groups [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: B-cell function (expression of CD69/CD23)	NS difference between groups [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Functional status monocytes (free radicals O2- = ethidium fluorescence)	Monocytes amalgam population: responsiveness within 5-7 days (7.8%); this trend did not persist beyond this time point. Monocytes from amalgam population reduced responsiveness within 5-7 days (8.4%); this trend did not persist beyond this time point. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Functional status neutrophils (free radicals H2O2=dihydrorhodmine fluorescence)	Neutrophil responses exhibited fluctuation within and between both treatment groups however none statistically significant
Perng 2023 [Retrospective cohort with control] ⁶	Amalgam vs Composite vs Amalgam+ Composite)	Immune function: Incidence rate of SLE per 100,00 person-months	NS different: Only amalgam: 0.92 (95%CI= 0.73-1.16); only resin: 1.04 (95% CI =0.90-1.19); amalgam + resin: 1.14 (95% CI=1.01-1.27)
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). CI=Confidence Interval, NECAT=New England Children's Amalgam Trial, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SLE=Systemic Lupus Erythematosus			

Table 4: Amalgam vs Composite - neurological

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: Central nervous system disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 2 (0.8) vs 3 (1.1) p>.99a
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: Neurological illness occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 4 (1.5) vs 1 (0.4) p=.37a
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: Nerve conduction velocity	High variability: inconsistent treatment effects over time. Statistically significant treatment difference at year 7 ((univariate) nominal .05 level of significance) Because of inconsistency of estimates+ large number of tests, finding not interpreted as evidence for treatment effect (finding favours results for the amalgam group, opposite that hypothesized)
Lauterbach 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: NHS overall summary	Across time, slight differences between two groups in % exhibiting any NHSs, but directions of differences not consistent over time, nor statistically significant in any year. Slight increase in % participants exhibiting NHSs in both groups during last 3 years
Lauterbach 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: Postural hand tremor (%)	% Participants exhibiting positional hand tremor started low (0-2 percent) in first four years of follow-up and increased over seven years of follow-up to between 4.4 percent and 4.9 percent. Increase uniform in both groups, group differences not consistently in one direction, no significant differences groups in any years
Lauterbach 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: NSS (%)	Year 2: 68.0% amalgam group vs 78.4% RBC showed one or more NSSs. Marginally significant (p=.02). Adjust for multiple comparisons - differences non-significant (p=.12). Direction of difference Yr 2 (10 percent higher in composite group) opposite expected direction if mercury from amalgam having harmful effect. Differences small/varying directions/not statistically significant for remaining years. Trend of decreasing percentages across time in both groups
Lauterbach 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Neurological: NSS severity	Years 3-7: no significant difference between groups. General trend in both groups for average NSS severity score to decrease progressively across time (typical for normal development)
Study quality: Strong (green shade). aPercentages calculated from all randomized participants in each group (n = 267) and sum to > 100% in each group because participants may be counted for > 1 condition. NHS=Neurological Hard Signs, NS=Non-Significant, NSS=Neurological Soft Sign, RBC=Resin Based Composite, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, yr=Year			

Table 5: Amalgam vs Composite - neuropsychological

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] [RCT-NECAT] ⁸	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Change scores over time- neuropsych tests	Of all the change scores evaluated, only two differed significantly between the amalgam and composite treatment groups: Number-letter-memory test and finger windows subtests of WRAML. Tested yearly over 5-years
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] [RCT-NECAT] ⁸	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Change scores over time: subsets of WRAML (Finger Windows and Number-Letter Memory)	4-year change score of amalgam group significantly more positive than change score of composite group , indicating greater improvement over time in amalgam group
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECTAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: GMI	Non-significant increases between baseline-Yr 5 in both treatment group (adjusting for baseline score+randomization stratum+additional covariates). Favoured amalgam group
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Memory summary	Differences in mean z scores were small and not statistically significant at any year.a Tests given: RAVLT Memory, RAVLT Total Learning, WRAML Visual Memory/Visual Learning
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] [RCT-NECAT] ⁸	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Summary of NS findings	NS differences in change scores between groups for following neuropsych tests: WISC-III: Verbal comprehension, perceptual organisation, freedom from distractibility, processing speed. Verbal subtests (Information Similarities, Vocabulary, Comprehension, Digit Span). Performance subtests (Picture Completion, coding, Picture Arrangement, Block Design, Object Assembly, Symbol Search, Mazes). WIAT: Composite Scores (Reading, Mathematics), Scale (Basic Reading, Reading Comprehension, Numerical Operations, Math Reasoning, Spelling, Listening Comprehension), WRAML: Index: Verbal+Visual Memory, Learning. Scale: Picture Memory, Design Memory, Story Memory, Verbal Learning, Sound Symbol, Sentence Memory, Visual Learning. WRAVMA: Drawing, Matching, Pegboard. Trail-Making Test: Part A: Time to complete, no.errors. Part B: Time to complete, no.errors. Finger tapping: Right/Left Hand. Verbal Cancellation, Verbal fluence (category fluency, letter fluency), Reaction Time, Stroop Colour-Word Interference Test (Colour, Word, Colour-Word), WCST (No. categories achieved, no trials to first category, total errors, total perseverative errors % conceptual level responses)
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: FSIQ summary	Non-significant increases between baseline-Yr 5 in both treatment group (adjusting for baseline score+randomization stratum+additional covariates). Favoured amalgam group. Repeated measures model using 3yr and 5year change in IQ - treatment group was not significant. However, year significant (an increase of 0.43 per year, p=.005). Interaction between treatment group/year not significant (p=.54) , indicating secular trend in IQ score independent of treatment group. Sensitivity analysis consistent with above: neither treatment group nor time was significant in the analysis controlling for time between baseline and 5yr follow-up with or without a treatment group x time interaction term. Analysis adjusted for potential inter-examiner differences revealed no statistically significant associations with treatment group, as well as no statistically significant inter-examiner differences.

			As-treated analysis: no significant effect treatment group (p=.24). Dose-response model, using surface-years of amalgam instead of treatment group as exposure index: no significant effect of amalgam exposure (p=.40); mean (SE) 5yr improvement in IQ score increased very slightly with greater exposure to amalgam (i.e., children with more amalgam fillings scored slightly higher, 0.016 [0.019] points increase/surface year amalgam exposure
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: WASI IQ score (FSIQ)	No statistically significant difference.a (At year 7)
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: CTONI IQ score (FSIQ)	Similar in 2 groups.a
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: VMCS	Non-significant increases between baseline-Yr 5 in both treatment group (adjusting for baseline score+randomization stratum+additional covariates). Favoured amalgam group
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Attention/concentration summary	Differences in mean z scores small and not statistically significant at any year. Tests given: Coding, Symbol Search, Digit Span, Digit Windows, Trails A, Trails B, Stroop Word/Colour/Colour Word
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Visuomotor summary	NS change scores at Year 7 follow-up. Tests given: WRAVMA Drawing/Matching/Pegs (dominant and non-dominant, SRT, Finger tapping (dominant and non-dominant)
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Overall summary	For final analysis yr 7, prescribed significance levels .011 for the Hotelling test, .024 for O'Brien test to detect worse outcomes in amalgam group, and .011 for O'Brien test to detect better outcomes in amalgam group. Final test statistic values: F=0.60 (p=.66) for Hotelling test and t =0.21 (1-sided p=.42) for O'Brien test. No evidence of group differences for primary outcome variables found in any 7 annual interim analyses , with 2-sided p values for Hotelling test ranging from .42 to .91, and 1-sided p values for O'Brien test ranging from .29 to .48
Study quality: Strong (green shade) aNo statistical significance reported. CTONI=Comprehensive Test of Nonverbal Intelligence, FSIQ=Full Scale Intelligence Quotient, GMI=General Memory Index, Hg=Mercury, N=Number, NECAT=New England Amalgam Trial, RAVLT=Rey Auditory Verbal/Visual Learning Test, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SE=Standard Error, SRT=Standard Reaction Time,, VMCS=Visuomotor Composite Scores, WASI=Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence, WRAML=Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning, WRAVMA=Wide Range Assessment of Visual Motor Ability, yr=Year			

Table 6: Amalgam vs Composite - oral health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Ahlgren 2014 [Case control] ⁹	Exposure: Amalgam or Composite restoration in individuals with OLL vs DP or PSFF	Oral health: Total N contact allergies	No contact allergy to composite substances found in two OLL patients with composite fillings but no amalgam adjacent to lichen lesions. In both groups, all patients with composite restorations also had amalgam restorations. Only two patients in OLL group had composite fillings adjacent to lichen lesions and with no amalgam present in that region. All other patients with composite fillings adjacent to lesions also had amalgam adjacent to or in contact with lesions
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ¹⁰	Amalgam vs Composite	Oral health: Probing pocket depths changes from baseline (T0) to T2 (Teeth with PPD ≥ 5 mm at T2 n (%))	Significant difference between groups: Higher proportion of PPD ≥5mm adjacent to amalgam vs composite restorations (45/255 [17.65%] vs 7/93 [7.53%], p=.02)
Ptak 2023 [Retrospective cohort] ¹¹	Exposure to Amalgam or Composite	Oral health: Pupal disease, OR	For patients who received large fillings, not statistically significant difference based on operative material (amalgam vs composite: odds ratio 5 1.32 [95% confidence interval, 0.94–1.85], p <.05) or no. surfaces involved (3 vs 4: odds ratio 5 0.78 [95% confidence interval, 0.54–1.12], p<.05)
Roberts 2008 [Secondary analysis of RCT-Casa Pia] ³	Health (amalgam vs composite)	Oral health: Oral bacteria, OR	No statistically significant differences in proportions of children with growth on ampicillin or mercury media. After adjustment for covariates, odds having Hgr bacteria not statistically different (p= .81) between two treatment groups (OR 1.04, 95% CI 0.74, 1.48) or between numbers of oral bacteria on any medium (p=.15)
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). CI=Confidence Interval, Hgr=Mercury resistant, N=Number, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OR=Odds Ratio, PPD=Probing Pocket Depths, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, T=Time			

Table 7: Amalgam vs Composite - renal

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/ exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Distribution renal marker stratified by yr/treatment group: γ -GT (U/g creatinine)	Differences between treatment groups small and non-statistically significant ($p > .3$ for ANCOVA models). No significant effects of no. fillings , nor U-Hg level in ANCOVA models ($p > .2$ for all) except for a decrease of γ -GT in years 3–5 with increasing number of composite fillings. Models including also an interaction between BPb and U-Hg showed no such interaction for γ -GT or NAG
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Distribution renal marker stratified by yr/treatment group: Albumin (mg/g creatinine)	Differences between treatment groups small and non-statistically significant ($p > .3$ for ANCOVA models) No significant effects of no. fillings , nor U-Hg level in ANCOVA models ($p > .2$ for all). Interaction term U-Hg*BPb was positive and statistically significant ($p = .04$ for year 3–5 and $p = 0.008$ for year 5). The model indicated a 34% increase of urinary albumin at U-Hg 1.5 μ g/g creatinine and BPb 4 μ g/dL (90th percentiles) compared with children with median U-Hg and BPb levels (0.52 μ g/g creatinine and μ g/dL) in year 5
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Distribution renal marker stratified by yr/treatment group: NAG (U/g creatinine)	Differences between treatment groups small and non-statistically significant ($p > .3$ for ANCOVA models) No significant effects of no. fillings , nor U-Hg level in ANCOVA models ($p > 0.2$ for all). Models including also an interaction between BPb and U-Hg showed no such interaction for γ -GT or NAG
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Distribution renal marker stratified by yr/treatment group: A1Md (mg/g creatinine)	29% of samples were above detection limit (29% vs 30% in amalgam and composite groups, respectively) making treatment group comparison meaningless
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: High values/yr - γ -GT (U/g creatinine)	No overall difference between treatment groups in logistic regression models. Moderately significant decrease in prevalence of high γ -GT with increasing numbers of both amalgam and composite fillings ($p = .02$ and $.03$, respectively)
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: High values/yr - NAG (U/g creatinine)	No overall difference between treatment groups in logistic regression models. Exposure–response analyses also showed no effects of number of fillings or U-Hg level on these markers
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: High values/yr - A1Md (mg/g creatinine)	No overall difference between treatment groups in logistic regression models. Exposure–response analyses also showed no effects of number of fillings or U-Hg level on these markers
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT]	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: High values/yr - Albumin (mg/g creatinine)	Significant difference: Prevalence urinary albumin > 30 mg/g creatinine (called MA)-in year 3 or year 5 higher in amalgam than composite group [repeated measures logistic regression: odds ratio (OR) = 1.8; 95% CI (CI), 1.1–2.9; $p = .03$]. The tendency was similar in year 3 and year 5 (OR = 1.8 in both cases). NS in adjusted models. Crude ORs slightly lower than those in the adjusted models (e.g., OR = 1.6; 95% CI, 0.98–2.5; $p = .06$) for MA in year 3–5. Significant difference MA: 48 occasions of MA in 38 children in amalgam group at 3-year and/or 5-year visits, vs 33 occasions in 31 children in composite group. Ten children in

			amalgam group (0–12 amalgam surfaces; median, 3) had MA on both visits, but only two in composite group (p=.04 ; Fisher's exact test). No significant increase in MA with increasing numbers of amalgam fillings (p=.30) or U-Hg excretion (p=.71). However, when an interaction term BPb*U-Hg included in model with U-Hg as predictor, it was statistically significant in year 5 (p=.02) and nearly so in years 3–5 (p=.07). When urine samples with albumin > 30 mg/g creatinine but < 20 mg/L and creatinine < 0.3 g/L (i.e., samples with relatively low creatinine where classification of MA could be considered less clear) were excluded, results similar (34 children with MA in amalgam group and 9 of them on both visits, vs. 28 in composites group and 1 of them on both visits). Twelve children had urinary albumin > 200 mg/g creatinine (two in year 3 only, nine in year 5 only, and one at both visits). Eight belonged to amalgam group (including the one at both visits) and four to composite group
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Albumin levels (mg/g)	Albumin levels at year 5 did not differ significantly between treatment groups. Adjustment for additional covariates did not affect results. Repeated-measures model (yr3 and yr5) treatment group not statistically significant nor year or interaction between treatment group and year. Albumin levels did not change over time in either treatment group. PROGRESS-PLUS: Mean (median) albumin higher for girls than for boys (36.9 [7.3] vs 18.3 [3.4]; p=.02)
Barregard 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Kidney disorders other than diabetes occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 2 (0.8) vs 2 (0.8) p>.99.a
Martin 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹³	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal: Urinary creatine levels	NS differences were observed between treatment groups for creatinine excretion rates [No stats presented]. PROGRESS-PLUS: Race: effects of race on creatinine levels - significant (Wald test) (Z - 3.6, p =.0003) - blacks show higher excretion levels than whites. Sex: effects of sex on average creatinine levels - not significant (Wald test) (Z - 0.40, p=.70). Age: A Wald test for trend was significant (Z - 22, p =.0001), indicating that the increase in average urinary creatinine with age is significant
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Urinary GST	Did not find any extremely high observed values that might indicate kidney damage
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Urinary porphyrins (See Woods GPH)	Concentrations did not suggest substantial mercury accumulation in kidneys
De Rouen 2006 [RCT-Casa Pia] ²	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Creatinine-adjusted albumin (mg/g)	NS group differences in median values of creatinine-adjusted albumin over the 7 years of follow-up , with each annual comparisons at p>.14 and observed median values (6.5-9.9 mg/g) in normal range. Albumin level, median (IQR) mg/g of Creatine, Amalgam vs Composite: Year 1: 7.7 (3.1-11.5) vs 7.4 (4.2-12.5), Year 2: 8.6 (5.5-13.4) vs 9.4 (5.3-16.1), Year 3: 9.0 (5.5-17.9) vs 9.9 (6.8-16.7), Year 4: 8.7 (5.6-14.5) vs 9.2 (5.8-20.8), Year 5: 8.0 (5.4-12.5) vs 8.2 (5.1-14.3), Year 6: 6 7.3 (4.8-14) vs 7.5 (4.8-14.3), Year 7: 6.5 (4.3-12.3) vs 6.8 (4.4-13.7)
Woods 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ¹⁴	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Urinary GST-Alpha levels	Regression showed GST-a levels approx. 5% higher in amalgam vs composite group, not statistically significant [1.05 (95% CI 0.95, 1.17) p=.308]. PROGRESS-PLUS: Race: Non-whites had approx. 13% higher levels than whites (p =.04). Became non-significant, after adjustment for baseline values [0.96 (95% CI 0.85, 1.08) p=.502]. Gender: Females 11% higher GST-a levels than males (p=.05). Became non-significant, after adjustment for baseline values [1.03 (95% CI 0.91, 1.15) p=.653]

Woods 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ¹⁴	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Urinary GST-Pie levels	Creatinine-adjusted GST-p levels tended to increase over course of study by four- to six-fold from 9 to 18 years. Increase in all groups irrespective of treatment/gender. At each age, differences between groups in GST-p levels small+similar to those for GST-a. Regression analysis: Significant difference between groups: GST-p levels approx. 11% higher in amalgam group overall (p = .04) ^b [1.11 (95% CI 0.98, 1.26) p=.091]. PROGRESS-PLUS: Race: Whites slightly higher levels than non-whites, and this became significant following adjustment for baseline values [1.17 (95% CI 1.02, 1.34) p=.025 . Gender: Females GST-p levels approx. 2xhigh males (p<.0001). Gender difference unchanged by adjustment baseline values [2.01 (95% CI 1.78, 2.28) p<.001]
Woods 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ¹⁴	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Urinary Albumin levels	Differences between groups in creatinine adjusted albumin levels small for all years of age. Albumin levels slightly lower in amalgam group but not statistically significant in adjusted regression analysis [0.91 (95% CI 0.783, 1.07) p=.274]. PROGRESS-PLUS: Race: Significant difference between white's vs non-whites (with higher levels for whites than non-whites. Difference became non-significant after adjustment for baseline values [1.10 (95% CI 0.94, 1.28) p=.229 . Gender: Females approx. 39% higher albumin levels than males (p<0.0001). gender difference unchanged by adjustment for baseline values [1.39 (95% CI 1.18, 1.63) p<.001]
Woods 2008 [RCT-Casa Pia] ¹⁴	Amalgam vs Composite	Renal function: Overall summary	NS difference in any parameters between treatment groups. Progressive increase in GST-p occurs between ages 9-18 all groups. Significantly greater creatinine-adjusted GST-p and albumin, but not GST-a, excreted by female's vs males from ages 9-18. All parameters comparable as follow-up year instead of year of age
Study quality: Strong (green shade). aPercentages calculated from all randomized participants in each group (n = 267) and sum to more than 100% in each group because participants may be counted for more than 1 condition, bReported as 0.04 in text and 0.091 in table. ANCOVA=Analysis of Covariance, A1M=Alpha-1-microglobulin, CI=Confidence Interval, GST=Glutathione S-transferases, MA=Microalbuminuria, NAG=N-acetylglucose-aminidase, NECAT-New England Children's Amalgam Trial, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trials, U-Hg=Urinary Mercury, γ-GT=γ-glutamyl transferase			

Table 8: Amalgam vs Composite - other

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lin 2017 [Retrospective cohort] ¹⁵	Amalgam vs composite vs glass ionomer restorations	ADHD: Incidence rate	ADHD incidence rate for amalgam restorations was 33.3/100 000 person-years, similar to 31.5/100 000 person-years for people with composite resin or glass ionomer restorations (p=.19). 10-year ADHD hazard probability for amalgam restorations: 0.028 vs 0.025 for composite resin or glass ionomer restorations (p=.19). Cox proportional hazard regression analysis: crude HR for ADHD 1.06-fold higher for people with amalgam restorations (95% CI=0.97-1.15, p=.19) than composite resin or glass ionomer restorations. After adjustment for potential confounding factors (ie age, sex, number of tooth restorations during 2002-2011, fluoride varnish application, medical institution, urbanization level and systemic diseases), adjusted HR for ADHD amalgam restorations:1.05 (95% CI=0.96-1.14, p=.27 ; in univariate Cox model, those with 6 or more amalgam restorations higher risk of future ADHD (HR=1.20, 95% CI=1.04-1.38, p=.015) vs composite resin or glass ionomer restorations. However, multivariate model revealed risk of future ADHD in these people similar to people with other restorations (HR=1.00, 95% CI=0.86-1.15, p=.97). All study population with amalgam restorations:a N=44 034 Univariate: Hazard ratio: 1.06 95% CI: 0.97-1.15 p=.19 . Multivariate: Hazard ratio:1.05, 95% CI: 0.96-1.14 p=.27 . [Subgroup analysis data reported table 2]
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Allergy: Allergy occurrence during 5yr follow-up, N (%)	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 45 (16.9) vs 47 (17.6) p=.91
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ¹⁶	Amalgam vs Composite	Anthropomorphic: Body Fat (%)	No statistically significant associations between treatment group and body fat% . Adjustment for additional covariates or excluding children with prior composite fillings did not change results. Among both girls and boys, greater treatment levels on primary teeth were associated with greater changes in body fat % (boys, $\beta = 1.9$, 95% CI 0.4-3.3, $p=.01$; girls, $\beta = 1.4$, 95% CI 0.4-2.4, $p=.005$). However, results comparable with amalgam (boys, $\beta = 1.6$, 95% CI 0.4-2.9 p=.01 ; girls, $\beta = 1.7$, 95% CI 0.6-2.8, p=.003), suggesting that increased body fat % independent of dental material. PROGRESS-PLUS:a No significant association between material or BF% for either gender. Male: 5yr change (SE): 5.7(0.9). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): 0.57(0.82) $p=.49$. Female: 5yr Change (SE): 7.7(0.8). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): 0.05(0.83), $p=.95$
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ¹⁶	Health [Amalgam vs Composite]	Anthropomorphic: BMI-for age-z-score	No associations between treatment group and BMI-for-age-z-score . Adjustment for additional covariates or excluding children with prior composite fillings did not change results. PROGRESS-PLUS:a No significant association between material or BMI-for-age-Z-score for either gender. Male: 5yr change (SE): 0.25(0.07). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): -0.21(0.23) $p=.36$. Female: 5-year Change (SE): 0.21(0.07). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): 0.08(0.12), $p=.49$
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ¹⁶	Health [Amalgam vs Composite]	Anthropomorphic: Height velocity	No associations between treatment group and height . Adjustment for additional covariates or excluding children with prior composite fillings did not change results. PROGRESS-PLUS:a No significant association between material or height velocity for either gender. Male: 5yr change (SE): 33.5(0.6). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): 0.48(0.83)b $p=.56$. Female: 5yr Change (SE): 31.2(0.5). Composite vs amalgam: β (SE): 0.77(1.18)b, $P=.51$

Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Blood disorder: Anaemia occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 4 (1.5) vs 3 (1.1) p>.99.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Blood disorder: SCD occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 1 (0.4) vs 1 (0.4) p>.99.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Cancer: Cancer occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 1 (0.4) vs 0 (0.0) p>.99.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	CVD: CVD occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 12 (4.) vs 16 (6.0) p=.56.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Dermatological: Skin disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 23 (8.6) vs 23 (8.6) p>.99.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Endocrine: Diabetes occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 0 vs 0 p>.99.c
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ¹⁶	Health [Amalgam vs Composite]	Female health: Menarche (occurrence)	Significant difference between groups: Girls assigned to composites (n = 62) less likely to have reached menarche (48% vs. 67%) and had lower risk of menarche (multi-variable adjusted hazard ratio = 0.57, 95% CI 0.35-0.95, p=.03) during 5-year follow-up vs amalgam (N=113 in analysis) No associations among greater bisGMA-based, UDMA-based, or total composite (p=.29) treatment levels received at baseline and onset of menarche during the follow-up period
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT-NECAT] ¹⁶	Health [Amalgam vs Composite]	Female health: Mean age menarche (yrs)	NS different by treatment assignment (composites, 12.5 ± 1.1 yrs; amalgam, 12.3 ± 1.0 yrs; multivariable-adjusted p=.48). (N=64 in analysis)
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Gastrointestinal: Gastrointestinal disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 6 (2.3) vs 9 (3.4) p=.60.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	MSK: Joint pain occurrence	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 6 (2.3) vs 6 (2.3) p>.99.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Psychological: Psychological disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	No significant difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 24 (9.0) vs 18 (6.7) p=.42.c
Bellinger 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Psychological: CBCL global score	Significant group differences: Internalizing and Total Problem Behaviours, with scores of amalgam group decreasing > non-amalgam group . Greater improvement in amalgam group. Expected standard deviation: 10. Improvements in amalgam group scores correspond to 36% and 46% of a standard deviation for Internalizing and Total Problem Behaviours, respectively, vs 16% and 20% for children in non-amalgam group. Scale Amalgam Group mean (SD)a; Non-amalgam Group mean (SD); P-value - Competence b 0.8 (0.6) -0.9 (0.6) 0.13; Internalizing -3.8 (0.6) -2.1 (0.6) 0.03 ; Externalizing -1.8 (0.6) -1.5 (0.8) 0.06; Total problem behaviours -3.3 (0.7) -2.1 (0.7) 0.007

Bellinger 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Psychological: CBCL subscales, change scores	Significant treatment group difference in change score on one Competence subscale: Activities. Scores of children in amalgam group improved > non-amalgam scores. Significant treatment group differences on two Behaviour subscales , Anxious/Depressed and Delinquent Behaviours. For both, greater change in positive direction for amalgam group
Bellinger 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Psychological: BASC-SR Composite Scores, by Treatment Group	Regarding four composite scales of BASC-SR, treatment groups differed on the Emotional Symptoms Index and Personal Adjustment . Score of amalgam group significantly lower (better) on Emotional Symptoms Index and significantly higher (better) on Personal Adjustment Score; Amalgam Group; Non-amalgam Group; p-value: School maladjustment a 50.8 ± 0.7 b 50.4 ± 0.7 0.29 Clinical maladjustment 44.0 ± 0.6 45.7 ± 0.6 0.08 Personal adjustment 53.3 ± 0.6 51.3 ± 0.6 0.005 Emotional symptoms index 44.6 ± 0.6 46.3 ± 0.6 0.05
Bellinger 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ¹⁷	Amalgam vs Composite	Psychological: Hg Urinary excretion & CBCL global score	Mean urinary mercury excretion between years 3 and 5 of follow-up not significantly associated with CBCL global score
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Respiratory: Asthma occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 19 (7.1) vs 17 (6.4) p=.86.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Respiratory: Respiratory disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 13 (4.9) vs 7 (2.6) p=.25.c
Bellinger 2006 [RCT-NECAT] ¹	Amalgam vs Composite	Sensory: Sensory disorders occurrence during 5yr follow-up	NS difference between treatment groups [N (%), Amalgam vs Composite]: 36 (13.5) vs 28 (10.5) p=.35.c
Geier 2011 [Secondary analysis RCT-Casa Pia] ¹⁸	Amalgam vs Composite	Other: Urinary porphyrins (mg/L)	Significant dose-dependent correlations between cumulative exposure to Hg from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins associated with Hg body-burden (penta-carboxyporphyrin, precoproporphyrin, and coproporphyrin). 5–10% increases in Hg-associated porphyrins for subjects receiving average no.dental amalgam fillings vs only composite fillings over 8yrs. No significant correlations between cumulative exposure to Hg from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins not associated with Hg body-burden (uroporphyrin, heptacarboxyporphyrin, and hexacarboxyporphyrin)
Study quality: Strong (green shade). aFrom linear mixed-effects models, adjusted for randomization stratum, age, and baseline value of growth outcome. Models for body fat percentage included height as time-varying co-variable, and, among males, knot at age 13yrs (p < 0.001). Positive β (> 0) indicates composites arm increased growth vs amalgam arm. b‡Height velocity during follow-up outcome of interest in repeated-measures model for treatment arm effect estimates. cPercentages calculated from all randomized participants in each group (n = 267) and sum > 100%/group because participants could be counted for >1 condition. ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, ANOVA=Analysis of Variance, BASC=Behaviour Assessment Scale for Children, bisGMA=Bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate, BMI=Body Mass Index, CBCL=Child Behaviour Checklist, CI=CI, CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, Hg=Mercury, MSK=Musculoskeletal, N=Number, NECAT=New England Children's Amalgam Trial, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SCD=Sickle Cell Disease, SD=Standard Deviation, UDMA=Urethane dimethacrylate			

Amalgam tables

Dental professional studies

Table 9: Relationship between amalgam exposure as dental professionals and general physical health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Overall prescription use (N. prescriptions)	For each of five disease categories, Dentists Showed much higher frequency of pharmacy utilization of specific illness prescription medications than Controls p values ranging between .006 and <.0001 . Of 16/20 (80%) of instances where Dentists prescribed more illness specific prescription medication than Controls, 4 reached statistical significance at .05 level ; and 1 occurred at the 35-44 age level: Neurological illnesses- 5.3% utilization (Dentists) vs. 0% utilization (Controls), with Chi-Square (d), c2 = 8.82, p=.003 . remaining three results all occurred in 45-54 age grouping. Dentists used more illness specific prescription medications than Controls. 2 of these occurred in youngest Age Grouping (25-34), for Respiratory and Cardiovascular medications; four in 35-44 age groupings (Neuropsychiatric, Neurological, total Neuropsychiatric and Neurological, and Respiratory medications). In remaining 10 instances, Dentists in two highest age groupings, 45-54 and 55-64, purchased more prescription medications vs Controls for each specific illness category
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Copper amalgam assumed. Metallic mercury exposure – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Euroquest: Sleep disturbance	Statistically significant difference between groups (p<.05) . DA: n=604, Mean symptom score: 1.81 (SD 0.63)a, Control: n=423, Mean Symptom score: 1.66 (SD 0.60). Higher score=greater symptomology
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Euroquest: Sleep disturbance	No statistically significant difference dentist's vs controls . Male Dentists n=231, mean symptom score (SD); 1.49 (0.40) Female dentists n=172, Mean SS (SD): 1.47 (0.47); Male controls n=52, Mean SS(SD): 1.55 (0.39), Female control n=165, Mean SS(SD): 1.51 (0.50). Higher score=greater symptomology
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: Present-Sleep disturbances (%)	Significant difference between groups . Exposed 70.5% vs Control 46.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 402 p <.04]. Higher score=greater symptomology. (N=75 total) - higher score=greater symptomology
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Euroquest: Fatigue	Significant difference between groups: DA: n=605, Mean symptom score: 2.06 (SD 0.5) (p<.01)b, Control: n=422, Mean Symptom score: 1.87 (SD 0.69)

Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Euroquest: Fatigue	No statistically significant difference dentist's vs controls. Male Dentists n=231, mean symptom score (SD); 1.51 (0.53) Female dentists n=171, Mean SS (SD): 1.73 (0.61); Male controls n=52, Mean SS(SD): 1.61 (0.56), Female control n=165, Mean SS(SD): 1.77 (0.65)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control]	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: Unsteadiness (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 30.0% vs Control 6.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 402 p < .03]
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: Bloating (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 55% vs Control 26.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 408.5 p < .03]
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: Headaches (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 65.0% vs Control 46.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 403 p < .03]
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Symptom prevalence	DA did not report more of other health complaints (e.g. Migraine , respiratory symptoms, MSK, kidney diseases) than controls
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Sum symptom scores	N DA: 577. GLM: statistically significant relationship between max. urine value and sum of the symptom scores (B = 0.55, p < .001), but significance disappeared when age included in the model. Statistically significant relationship between no. yrs worked and sum symptom scores (B = 0.48, p < 0.001), significance disappeared when age included in model. For 490 participants who started to work as dental assistant before 1990, sum of symptom scores: 12.6 (SD = 2.7) while it was (SD = 3.5) for the 101 who started after 1990 (p = .024 adjusted for age)
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Symptom prevalence	Categorisation by looking at prevalence of subjects with three, four, or five of the seven symptoms occurring “often” or more frequently: Rate ratios between groups vary between 1.6 and 2.8, none reached statistical significance. % DA vs controls with: Three or more symptoms: 4.4 vs 2.8 Relative risk: 1.6; Four or more symptoms: 2.5 vs 0.9, Relative Risk: 2.8; Five or more symptoms: 1.0 vs 0.5 Relative Risk 2.0
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	General physical health: Symptom prevalence	Mean scores for each symptom low, made categorisation by looking at prevalence of subjects with three symptoms occurring “often” (value 3) or more frequently. Only female dentists between 41 and 60 years had slightly higher sum scores than controls. Among female dentists and controls, 5/173 (2.9%) vs 3/165 (1.8%) with three or more symptoms often or more frequently. Corresponding figures for males: 0/233 vs 1/52. No differences statistically significant. Unable to stratify analysis by age groups: small figures prevent meaningful comparison

Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: Illness symptoms: Present illness symptoms-Summary	26 illness symptoms NR: NS difference between groups
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	General physical health: General health	No significant difference , most women reported very good or excellent health: exposed group (M = 6.05, SD = 0.83) and control group (M = 6.02, SD = 0.81)
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade) a*p < 0.05 by general linear modelling adjusted for age and level of education. b < 0.01 by general linear modelling adjusted for age and level of education. c used the highest value ever for each person in an analysis by general linear modelling, controlling for level of education and age DA=Dental Amalgam, GLM=General Linear Models, Hg=Mercury, M=Mean, NR=Not reported, NS=Not Significant, SD=Standard Deviation			

Table 10: Relationship between amalgam exposure as a dental professional and musculoskeletal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	MSK: Symptom prevalence	DA did not report more of other health complaints (e.g. Migraine, respiratory symptoms, MSK , kidney diseases) than controls
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	MSK: physical injuries: Occupational overuse syndrome (%)	Significant difference between groups: 32.5% exposed group and 6.66% of the control group 2 (1, N=70) 6.80, p < .01 . PROGRESS-PLUS: All participants from exposed group reporting OOS medium-to-long duration of mercury exposure (medium exposure =2 years training, 3 years bonded employment and up to further 10 years employment; long duration exposure =criteria for medium but >10 yrs employment, not necessarily continuously)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg Dental professional vs No exposure	MSK: Arthritis (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 37.5% vs Control 16.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 443.5 p < .05]
Study quality: Low (red shade), DA=Dental Amalgam, Hg=Mercury, MSK=Musculoskeletal, N=Number, OOS=Occupational Overuse Syndrome			

Table 11: Relationship between amalgam exposure as a dental professional and neurological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals	Neurological Health: Overall prescription use (N. prescriptions)	For each of five disease categories, Dentists Showed much higher frequency of pharmacy utilization of specific illness prescription medications than Controls p values ranging between .006 and <.0001 . Of 16/20 (80%) of instances where Dentists prescribed more illness specific prescription medication than Controls, 4 reached statistical significance at .05 level ; and 1 occurred at the 35-44 age level: Neurological illnesses- 5.3% utilization (Dentists) vs. 0% utilization (Controls), with Chi-Square (d), c2 = 8.82, p=.003 . remaining three results all occurred in 45-54 age grouping. Dentists used more illness specific prescription medications than Controls. 2 of these occurred in youngest Age Grouping (25-34), for Respiratory and Cardiovascular medications; four in 35-44 age groupings (Neuropsychiatric, Neurological, total Neuropsychiatric and Neurological, and Respiratory medications). In remaining 10 instances, Dentists in two highest age groupings, 45-54 and 55-64, purchased more prescription medications that did Controls for each of five categories of specific illnesses
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals	Neurological: Neurological (N.prescriptions)	Dentists>Controls utilization of prescription medications statistically significant (p<.0001) across majority of age ranges. For Neurological medications (7.6% utilization for Dentists compared to 1.1% for Controls, producing Chi-Square (d), c2 = 7.82 and a corresponding p=.005. 16/20 (80%) of instances in which Dentists were prescribed more illness specific prescription medication than Controls, 4 reached statistical significance at .05 level; 1 occurred at 35-44 age level: Neurological illnesses- 5.3% utilization (Dentists) vs. 0% utilization (Controls), with Chi-Square (d), c2 = 8.82, p=.003. the remaining three results all occurred in the 45-54 age grouping
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals	Neurological: Neurologic (Frequency of utilisation prescription medication)	Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 24/396 (6.1%) vs 6/708 (0.8%), X2=24.17, p<.0001, RR=7.63, CI=3.08-18.88
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals	Psychiatric +Neurological: Psychiatric+ neurologic (Frequency of utilisation prescription medication)	Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 61/396 (15.4%) vs 39/708 (5.5%), X2=29.00, p<.0001, RR=2.8, CI=1.91-4.11
Franzblau 2012 [Cross sectional/longitudinal] ²³	Amalgam - no. fillings made/removed per wk	Neurological: Nerve function: Ulnar amplitude (mV)	No significant association between ulnar amplitude and urine mercury concentration at initial observations and when accounting for repeat observations
Franzblau 2012 [Cross sectional/longitudinal] ²³	Amalgam - no. fillings made/removed per wk	Neurological: Nerve function: Median amplitude (mV)	No significant association between median amplitude and urine mercury concentration at initial observations and when accounting for repeat observations

Franzblau 2012 [Cross sectional/longitudinal] ²³	Amalgam - no. fillings made/removed per wk	Neurological: Nerve function: Median peak latency (ms)	Urine mercury significant in models of median peak latency when based on initial observations and excluding subjects with imputed BMI. When repeat observations and subjects with imputed BMI are included in the latency models, parameter estimates are much smaller in magnitude and no longer significant
Franzblau 2012 [Cross sectional/longitudinal] ²³	Amalgam - no. fillings made/removed per wk	Neurological: Nerve function: Ulnar peak latency (ms)	Urine mercury significant in models of ulnar peak latency when based on initial observations and excluding subjects with imputed BMI. However, when repeat observations and subjects with imputed BMI are included in the latency models, the parameter estimates are much smaller in magnitude and are no longer significant
Hilt 2009 [Cross-sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Neurological: Euroquest: Neurological symptoms	Significant association ($p < 0.01$ by general linear modelling adjusted for age and level of education). DA: n=608, Mean symptom score: 1.49 (SD 0.49), Control: n=422, Mean Symptom score: 1.35(SD 0.40)
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	Neurological: Euroquest: Neurological symptoms	No statistically significant difference dentist's vs controls. Male Dentists n=231 mean symptom score (SD); 1.16 (0.28) Female dentists n=172, Mean SS (SD): 1.19 (0.28); Male controls n=52, Mean SS(SD): 1.22 (0.32), Female control n=164, Mean SS(SD): 1.25 (0.34)
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ²⁴	Mercury exposure - Dental professionals vs non-occupationally exposed	Neurological: Hospital admissions - Neurological disease (N)	Admission rates due to neurological disease among dental assistant's vs three control groups for four periods did not show any consistent pattern (Table 2). Tests for different period effects insignificant in all control groups (e.g., $p = .49$ for dental assistants compared with medical secretaries). For dentists' significant difference in period effects with increasing risk for dentists compared with general practitioners and lawyers over time (table 2). Among dental assistants, a negative association between cumulative exposure and neurological disease observed, although association not significant ($p = .21$). Among dentists: non-significant U-shaped association ($p = .51$)
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ²⁴	Mercury exposure - Dental professionals vs non-occupationally exposed	Neurological: Hospital admissions - Parkinson disease (N)	No. cases and age-standardised incidence rates showed dentists lower incidence of neurological and Parkinson's disease vs control groups (general practitioners and lawyers)
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ²⁴	Mercury exposure - Dental professionals vs non-occupationally exposed	Neurological: Hospital admissions - Parkinson's disease (N)	The numbers of cases and age-standardised incidence rates showed dentists had lower incidence of neurological and Parkinson's disease vs control groups (general practitioners and lawyers). Admission rates Parkinson's disease among dental assistant's vs medical and legal secretaries did not show any consistent pattern and no significant difference for period effects observed. Analysis not performed for nurses as only one nurse admitted to hospital due to Parkinson's disease. No consistent pattern for dentists. Among dental assistants, negative association shown between cumulative exposure and risk of Parkinson's disease, although association not significant ($p = .45$). Too few cases observed among dentists to perform meaningful analysis of association between cumulative exposure and Parkinson's disease
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). BMI=Body Mass Index, CI=CI, DA=Dental Amalgam, N=Number, RR=Risk Ratio, SD=Standard Deviation, SS=Standard Score,			

Table 12: Relationship between amalgam exposure as dental professionals and neuropsychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals	Neuropsych: Neuropsychological (N. prescriptions)	Dentists>Controls Utilization of prescription medications statistically significant (p<.0001) across majority of age ranges. For Neuropsychiatric medications (15.3 %) utilization for Dentists vs 6.3% Controls, with Chi-Square (d), Chi-squared= 6.25 and p=.012 . PROGRESS-PLUS: For Combined Neuropsychological and Neurological illnesses: 0.1% Dentists vs 6.3% Controls, resulting in a Chi-Square (d), value of 13.28 with chance probability of 0.0003 or 3/10,000
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals	Neuropsych: Health: Overall prescription use (N. prescriptions)	For each of five disease categories, Dentists Showed much higher frequency of pharmacy utilization of specific illness prescription medications than Controls p values ranging between .006 and <.0001 . Of 16/20 (80%) of instances where Dentists prescribed more illness specific prescription medication than Controls, 4 reached statistical significance at .05 level ; and also 1 occurred at the 35-44 age level: Neurological illnesses- 5.3% utilization (Dentists) vs. 0% utilization (Controls), with Chi-Square (d), c2 = 8.82, p=.003 . remaining three results all occurred in 45-54 age grouping. Dentists used more illness specific prescription medications than Controls. 2 of these occurred in youngest Age Grouping (25-34), for Respiratory and Cardiovascular medications; four in 35-44 age groupings (Neuropsychiatric, Neurological, total Neuropsychiatric and Neurological, and Respiratory medications). In remaining 10 instances, Dentists in two highest age groupings, 45-54 and 55-64, purchased more prescription medications that did Controls for each of five categories of specific illnesses
Hilt 2009 [Cross-sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Neuropsych: Euroquest: Memory – Symptom Score, Mean (SD)	Significant difference between groups: DA: n=605, Mean symptom score: 1.99 (SD 0.72)a, Control: n=424, Mean Symptom score: 1.79 (SD 0.63)
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	Neuropsych: Euroquest: Memory – Symptom Score, Mean (SD)	No statistically significant difference dentist’s vs controls. Male Dentists n=232, mean symptom score (SD); 1.60 (0.50) Female dentists n=173, Mean SS (SD): 1.69(0.58); Male controls n=52, Mean SS(SD): 1.68(0.47), Female control n=165, Mean SS(SD): 1.71(0.62)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Neuropsych: Memory (Rey-15) – Symptom Score, Mean (SD)	NS difference between groups: Exposed: M = 13.39, SD = 1.83; controls: M = 13.47, SD = 1.98, t=-0.175, p=- 0.86 (two-tailed), df -71]
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no	Neuropsych: Executive functioning: short-delay and long-	NS difference between groups. Typical CVLT examples: for total recall score of possible 80 from five trials [exposed: M=60.38, SD= 7.26; controls: M= 60.83, SD= 7.75, t=0.25, p=.81 (two tailed), df = 67]; immediate free recall following a distraction list possible score of 16 [exposed: M= 12.67, SD= 2.34; controls: M= 12.47, SD =2.60, t= 0.34, p=.74 (two-

	exposure - Dental professional	delay recall tasks, an interference task, free and cued recall and a recognition task. CVLT	tailed), df= 67] and free recall following a 20-min delay possible score of 16 [exposed: M= 13.18, SD= 2.14; controls: M=12.07, SD = 2.96, t = 1.71, p=.09 (two tailed), df= 67]
Hilt 2009 [Cross-sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Neuropsych: Euroquest: Concentration – Symptom score, Mean (SD)	Significant difference between groups: DA: n=603, Mean symptom score: 1.76 (SD 0.63) ^a , Control: n=423, Mean Symptom score: 1.58 (SD 0.52)
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	Neuropsych: Euroquest: Concentration – Symptom score, Mean (SD)	NS difference dentist's vs controls. Male Dentists n=231, mean symptom score (SD); 1.38 (0.45) Female dentists n=172, Mean SS (SD): 1.44 (0.51); Male controls n=52, Mean SS(SD): 1.47 (0.42), Female control n=165, Mean SS(SD): 1.51 (0.50)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Neuropsych: Overall summary	NS differences between groups on the cognitive tests
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Neuropsych: Higher executive function, concentration, attention - SDMT	NS difference between groups. Exposed: M = 38.1, SD =4.64; controls: M = 36.47, SD =6.71, t =1.23, p=.23 (two tailed), df = 71
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). ap <.01 by general linear modelling adjusted for age and level of education.aAdjusted for age, sex and calendar year. CVLT= California Verbal Learning Test (Adult Research Version), DA=Dental Amalgam, DF=Degrees of Freedom, M=Mean, N=Number, NS=Non-significant, SD=Standard Deviation, SDMT=Symbol Digit Modalities Test, SS=Symptom score			

Table 13: Relationship between amalgam exposure as a dental professional and psychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals	Psychological: Psychiatric (Frequency of utilisation prescription meds)	Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 46/36 (11.6%) vs 35/708 (4.9%), X ² = 15.66, p<.0001 , RR=2.37, CI=1.55-3.62
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals	Psychological: Psychiatric+neurologic (Frequency of utilisation)	Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 61/396 (15.4%) vs 39/708 (5.5%), X ² =29.00, p<.0001 , RR=2.8, CI=1.91-4.11
Hilt 2009 [Cross-sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Psychological: Euroquest: Mood	NS difference between groups: DA: n=605, Mean symptom score: 1.71 (SD 0.56), Control: n=421, Mean Symptom score: 1.62 (SD 0.54)
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	Psychological: Euroquest: Mood	NS difference dentist's vs controls. Male Dentists n=232, mean symptom score (SD); 1.35 (0.37) Female dentists n=172, Mean SS (SD): 1.47 (0.49); Male controls n=51, Mean SS(SD): 1.47 (0.43), Female control n=164, Mean SS(SD): 1.49 (0.42)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Agreeable-hostile POMS subscale	Exposed mean (SD): 28.76 (4.99), Control mean (SD): 26.22(5.89) t=2.09 p (two-tailed) .04a
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Composed-anxious POMS subscale	Exposed mean (SD): 24.61 (5.86), Control mean (SD): 27.72(5.78) t=2.26 p (two-tailed) .03a
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Elated-depressed POMS subscale	NS difference between groups: Exposed mean (SD): 25.27 (5.59), Control mean (SD): 25.72(5.94) t=-0.33 p (two-tailed) 0.74
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control]	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Confident-unsure POMS subscale	NS difference between groups: Exposed mean (SD): 24.07 (6.25), Control mean (SD): 25.31(6.24) t=-0.84 p (two-tailed) .40
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Clearheaded-confused POMS subscale	NS difference between groups: Exposed mean (SD): 28.27 (5.51), Control mean (SD): 28.66(4.41) t=-0.33 p (two-tailed) .75

Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood: Energetic-tired POMS subscale	NS difference between groups: Exposed mean (SD): 22.12 (6.16), Control mean (SD): 20.93(6.59) t=0.78 p (two-tailed) .44
Hilt 2009 [Cross-sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Psychological: Euroquest: Psychosomatic symptoms	NS difference between groups: DA: n=604, Mean symptom score: 1.59(SD 0.56) ^b , Control: n=421, Mean Symptom score: 1.50 (SD 0.41)
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ²¹	Copper amalgam assumed. Hg exposure - Dental professionals vs No exposure	Psychological: Euroquest: Psychosomatic symptoms	NS difference between groups: Male Dentists n=231, mean symptom score (SD); 1.23 (0.25) Female dentists n=171, Mean SS (SD): 1.37 (0.38); Male controls n=51, Mean SS(SD): 1.30 (0.29), Female control n=163, Mean SS(SD): 1.41 (0.31)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Psychological: Mood-POMS Overall summary	Two subscales, agreeable–hostile and composed–anxious, showed significant differences between groups . Exposed group more agreeable and more anxious than control group
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). a*Significant p<.05 (df= 71). b p<.05 by general linear modelling adjusted for age and level of education. CI=CI, DA=Dental Amalgam, DF=Degrees of Freedom, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, POMS=Profile of Mood States, SD=Standard Deviation, SS=Standard Score,			

Table 14: Relationship between amalgam exposure as dental professional and renal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Renal: Symptom prevalence	DA did not report more of other health complaints (e.g. Migraine, respiratory symptoms, MSK, kidney diseases) than controls
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ²⁴	Mercury exposure - Dental professionals vs non-occupationally exposed	Renal disease: Hospital admission (N)	Admission rate increasing among dental assistant's vs 3 control groups, although differences not statistically significant. No significant difference in period effects for dentists. No association between cumulative exposure and risk of renal disease for dental assistants, but for dentists non-significant increasing risk observed (p=.52). Repeated analyses with 5 and 10yrs of latency, showed the same relationships. Repeated analysis after excluding those employed in 1964, which did not change the main results
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). DA=Dental Amalgam, MSK=Musculoskeletal, N=Number, yrs=Years			

Table 15: Relationship between amalgam exposure as dental professional and respiratory symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Amalgam/Mercury assumed - Dental professionals vs Controls	Respiratory: Prescriptions (N)	NS difference between groups. Dentists>Controls utilization of prescription medications results closely approached statistical significance at .056
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals vs Controls	Respiratory: Frequency utilisation of respiratory medication (N)	Dentists used more illness specific prescription medications than Controls. 2 of these occurred in youngest Age Grouping (25-34), for Respiratory and Cardiovascular medications. four in 35-44 age groupings (Neuropsychiatric, Neurological, total Neuropsychiatric and Neurological, and Respiratory medications). In remaining 10 instances, Dentists in two highest age groupings, 45-54 and 55-64, purchased more prescription medications that did Controls for each of five categories of specific illnesses. Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 84/396 (21.2%) vs 103/708 (14.5%), X ² =7.55, p=.006 , RR=1.46, CI=1.13-2.12
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ²⁰	Amalgam assumed. Exposure metallic mercury – Female dental professionals vs No exposure	Respiratory: Symptom prevalence (N)	DA did not report more of other health complaints (e.g. Migraine, respiratory symptoms , MSK, kidney diseases) than controls
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CI=CI, DA=Dental Amalgam, MSK=Musculoskeletal, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RR=Risk Ratio, X ² =Chi-Squared			

Table 16: Relationship between exposure to amalgam as dental professionals and allergy, CVD, dermatological, endocrine, female health symptoms and adverse event

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Heratizadeh 2018 [Retrospective case-control] ²⁵	Methacrylate's/acrylates and amalgam/amalgam meals – Dental metals: Palladium chloride, amalgam, ammoniated mercury, Tin chloride, Gold sodium thiosulfate, amalgam alloy metals, ammonium tetra chloroplatinate, copper II sulphate pentahydrate Dental professionals	Allergy: Positive patch test, N (%)	Methacrylate's most common allergens, followed by acrylates, metal allergy observed less frequently. 67 patients reacted to methacrylate's and/or acrylates. Of these, 63 patients reacted to min. 1 methacrylate, and 24 patients to one or both of acrylates tested. Concomitant reactions frequent. In Study group: Substance, concentration (n tested). Acrylates: Ethyl acrylate 0.1 (n=174). Negative: n=151. % Positive: 10.9. Pentaerythritol triacrylate 0.1 (n=174). Negative: n=164. % Positive: 4.0. Methacrylates: 2-Hydroxyethyl methacrylate 1.0 (n=188). Negative: n=138. % Positive: 21.3. 2-Hydroxypropyl methacrylate 2.0 (n=188). Negative: n=137. % Positive: 21.3. Methyl methacrylate 2.0 (n=194). Negative: n=145. % Positive: 21.1. Ethyl methacrylate 2.0 (n=174). Negative: n=133. % Positive: 19.0. Ethylene glycol dimethacrylate 2 (n=189). Negative: n=145 % Positive: 17.5. Triethylene glycol dimethacrylate 2 (n=193) Negative: n=164. % Positive: 9.3. Tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate 2 (n=174). Negative: n=151 % Positive: 9.2. 1,4-Butanediol dimethacrylate 2 (n=187). Negative: n=166. % Positive: 8.6. Diurethane dimethacrylate 2 (n=147). Negative: n=144 % Positive: 0.0. In study group: Substance, concentration (n tested): Amalgam 5.0 (n=125). Negative: n=114. % Positive: 4.0%. Amalgam alloy metals 20 (n=127). Negative: 126. % Positive: 0.8
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals	CVD: CVD (N. prescriptions)	Dentists>Controls utilization of prescription medications statistically significant (p<.0001) across majority of age ranges
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ¹⁹	Exposure: Amalgam/Mercury assumed) - Dental professionals	CVD: CVD (Frequency utilisation of medication)	Usage (Dentists vs Controls): 107/396 (27%) vs 114/708 (16.1), X ² =18.23, P<.0001 , RR=1.68, CI=1.33-2.12. Dentists used more illness specific prescription medications than Controls. 2 of these occurred in youngest Age Grouping (25-34), for Respiratory and Cardiovascular medications
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Dermatological: Present-Dry skin, N (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 62.5% vs Control 46.6% [Mann Whitney: U = 369.5 p<.01]
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Endocrine: Present-Thyroid (%)	NS (Mann-Whitney U test, p=.07)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Female health: Hysterectomy , N (%)	Significant difference between groups: Total N: Exposed n=38, Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 10 (25%), Control n (%): 2(6.66%) p <.04a
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Oral health: Present-Metallic taste (%)	Significant difference between groups. Exposed 32.5% vs Control 10.0% [Mann Whitney: U = 400 p <.02]

Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Female health: Breast cancer , N (%)	NS difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 1(2.5) vs Control n (%): 0(0)0
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ²⁴	Mercury exposure - Dental professionals vs non-occupationally exposed	Serious Adverse Events: Death (N)	By the end of follow-up, deaths dental clinic: 304 dentists and 1406 dental assistants (total population: 41328=4.14%) vs deaths GP clinic: 266 GPs & 290 nurse, 2254 secretaries (total population: 38584=7.28%), vs Lawyers office: 1062 lawyers, 3527 secretaries (total population: 53398=8.59%) (Uncertain if outcome of exposure, may be natural causes). NB some participants employed across all three categories.
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). aPearson's Chi square (1, N=70) = 4.06, p=.04. CI=CI, CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, N=Number, RR=Risk Ratio			

Maternal exposure studies

Table 17: Relationship between maternal amalgam and child ADHD/Autism

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lygre 2018 [Prospective cohort] ²⁶	Maternal exposure Amalgam during pregnancy	ADHD: Child ADHD symptoms at 90% percentile at 3 yrs (Sum score)	<p>No significant difference in ADHD score and different amalgam groups vs group no maternal amalgam fillings [N=42163 children) Adjusted model: 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.99 (0.92, 1.11), p=.86; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.02 (0.94, 1.11), p=.63; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.02 (0.92, 1.12), p=.73. No significant relationship between ADHD symptoms and having amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy. Adjusted model- Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.07 (0.77, 1.50), p=.69; Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.96 (0.82, 1.14), p=.66. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: No increased risk ADHD symptoms and no. teeth amalgam fillings when analysing the girls and boys separately nor together. Girls adjusted (n=20615): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.01 (0.90, 1.12), p=.93; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.04 (0.93, 1.18), p=.50; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.94 (0.81, 1.09), p=.40. Boys adjusted (n=21548): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.98 (0.89, 1.10), p=.78; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.00 (0.89, 1.12), p=.97; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.09 (0.96, 1.25), p=.20. No statistically significant associations between ADHD symptoms (sum score ≥10) and amalgam fillings placed or removed found analysing girls and boys separately and together or when using the separate 90th percentiles. Girls adjusted- Placed: OR (95% CI) 1.31 (0.84, 2.04), p=.24; Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.88 (0.69, 1.13), p=.33. Boys adjusted-Placed: OR (95% CI) 0.87 (0.53, 1.43), p= .58; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.03 (0.83, 1.29), p=.77. Age: No statistically significant associations between ADHD symptom sum score at/above 90th percentile and one or more amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy at 3yrs of age</p>

Lygre 2018 [Prospective cohort] ²⁶	Maternal exposure Amalgam during pregnancy	ADHD: Child ADHD symptoms at 90% percentile at 5 yrs (Sum score)	No increased risk was found (crude or adjusted) between ADHD symptom and number of maternal teeth with amalgam fillings (both grouped and as continuous variable) [N=23302 children]. Adjusted model: 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.04 (0.93, 1.16), p=.48; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.96 (0.85, 1.09), p=.45; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.11 (0.96, 1.30), p=.11. No significant relationship between ADHD symptoms and having amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy. Adjusted model- Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.24 (0.72, 2.11), p=.44; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.13 (0.89, 1.44), p=.32. For those with valid data both in child aged three and five years (n=19 220), mean sum score of symptoms associated with ADHD at five years was 4.2 (SD 4.5). PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: No statistically significant associations (crude or adjusted) between ADHD symptoms and no. of teeth with amalgam fillings neither when analysing the girls and boys separately nor together or when using the separate 90th percentiles for girls (sum score ≥9) and boys (sum score ≥11). Girls adjusted (n=11472): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.08 (0.90, 1.29), p=.42; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.03 (0.84, 1.26), p=.79; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.27 (1.00, 1.62), p=.050. Boys adjusted (n=11830): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.01 (0.88, 1.16), p=.84; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.92 (0.78, 1.08), p=.29; 9 &above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.05 (0.86, 1.33), p=.63. No statistically significant associations between ADHD symptoms (sum score ≥10) and amalgam fillings placed or removed were found when analysing girls and boys separately and together or when using separate 90th percentiles. Girls adjusted- Placed: OR (95% CI) 1.04 (0.41, 2.65), p=.93; Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.93 (0.61, 1.42), p=.72. Boys adjusted-Placed: OR (95% CI) 1.36 (0.70, 2.64), p=.37; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.25 (0.93, 1.69), p=.14
Lygre 2018 [Prospective cohort] ²⁶	Maternal exposure Amalgam during pregnancy	ADHD: Child ADHD symptoms at 90% percentile at 3&5 yrs (Sum score)	No significant difference in ADHD symptoms between different maternal amalgam groups vs group no amalgam fillings [n=19220] Adjusted model: 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.90 (0.95, 1.09), p=.28; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.92 (0.75, 1.14), p=.45; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.03 (0.80, 1.33), p=.79. No significant relationship between ADHD symptoms and having amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy. Adjusted model- Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.84 (0.31, 2.29), p=.73; Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.83 (0.56, 1.25), p=.37. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: No increased risk (crude or adjusted) between ADHD symptom score at two time points and number of teeth with amalgam fillings (both grouped and as continuous variable), neither when analysing girls and boys separately nor together. Girls adjusted (n=9419): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.95 (0.70, 1.29), p=.73; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.04 (0.74, 1.46), p=.82; 9&above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 1.30 (0.87, 1.95), p=.20. Boys adjusted (n=9801): 1-4 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.87 (0.69, 1.09), p=.22; 5-8 amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.86 (0.66, 1.12), p=.27; 9 &above amalgam: OR (95% CI): 0.89 (0.64, 1.25), p=.51. No statistically significant associations between ADHD symptoms and amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy found when analysing boys and girls separately and together. Girls adjusted- Placed: OR (95% CI) 0.52 (0.07, 3.82), p=.52; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.75 (0.99, 3.12), p=.056. Boys adjusted-Placed: OR (95% CI) 1.13(0.35, 3.68), p=.84; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.11 (0.62, 1.96), p=.73
Adams 2008 [Case control] ²⁷	Maternal exposure Amalgam individuals with autism vs neurotypical controls	Child: Hair Hg (mcg g-1)	Autism and control groups had similar mean values of Hg in hair (0.87 (2.6) versus 0.95 (0.87) mcg g1 respectively. Median value for autism group lower than control (0.38 versus. 0.72 mcg g1)

Adams 2008 [Case control] ²⁷	Maternal exposure Amalgam individuals with autism vs neurotypical controls	Autism: Autism diagnosis (N)	Logistic regression analysis: children with lower levels of metal in hair (defined as below 0.55 mcg g⁻¹) were 2.5-fold more likely to manifest autism (p < .05) than children with higher levels of Hg (arbitrarily defined as above 0.55 mcg g ⁻¹). Severity of autism vs level of baby hair Hg: No statistically significant correlations found with ATEC total score or ATEC subscales. Re: Autism severity: weak negative correlation (-0.18) with Hg levels (excluding four outliers), but not statistically significant. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: Females in both groups lower baby hair Hg levels than males, difference not statistically significant. Four samples from boys with autism with high levels of Hg (6, 6.5, 8.5, and 19.7 mcg g ⁻¹) (indicative Hg toxicity+ > highest level for controls, 3.6 mcg g ⁻¹): account for large difference in SD between the two groups (2.6 versus 0.87 mcg g ⁻¹ , respectively)
Adams 2008 [Case control] ²⁷	Maternal exposure Amalgam individuals with autism vs neurotypical controls	Autism: Autism diagnosis (N)	No major differences between two groups in terms of number of maternal Hg amalgams present during pregnancy. Hg amalgam placement during pregnancy rare both groups (3–4%)
Adams 2008 [Case control] ²⁷	Maternal exposure Amalgam individuals with autism vs neurotypical controls	Hg exposure: Relationship between amalgam and Hair Hg (mcg g ⁻¹)	Hg in baby hair significantly correlated with no. maternal Hg amalgam fillings for children with autism (0.27) , but not significant for controls (0.15)
Study quality: Low (red shade). ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, CI=CI, Hg=Mercury, OR=Odds Ratio, SD=Standard Deviation, yrs=Years			

Table 18: Relationship between maternal amalgam exposure and child neuropsychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Prenatal amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): Comprehensive Battery test for overall intelligence [LEL]	Prenatal amalgam surfaces not significantly associated with any outcome , either without or with adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Significant interaction of sex by LEL amalgam surfaces for GCI endpoint (p=.04) after adjusting for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg and covariates. For GCI, amalgam slope positive for females (0.31, 95% CI: -0.09 to 0.72) and negative (-0.24, 95% CI: -0.59 to 0.12) for males, but neither slope was significantly different from zero . For small no. amalgam surfaces, GCI outcomes similar for both sexes. As no. maternal amalgam surfaces increases, males predicted to perform less well, females predicted better performance. SES: GCI: higher SES significant predictors of improved scores in some models. Higher HOME score very significant predictor of improved scores in all models and caregiver IQ also significant predictors of improved scores in some models
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Prenatal amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): Comprehensive Battery test for overall intelligence [UEL]	UEL amalgam surface metric not significant predictor for any outcomes. When adjusting for UEL amalgam surfaces, increasing recent postnatal MeHg exposure associated with significant improvement in both sexes in the same outcomes: GCI (0.35, p=.02), PLS Total Score (0.22, p=.01), and W-J Applied Problems (0.57, p=.01). PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Fewer Bender Gestalt Errors with increasing postnatal MeHg exposure (-0.20, p=.01) in male children
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Prenatal amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): General Cognitive Index (GCI) of McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities (MSCA)] ³	Amalgam surfaces not significantly associated with any outcome, either without or with adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: significant interaction of sex by LEL amalgam surfaces for GCI endpoint (=.04) after adjusting for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg and covariates. For GCI, amalgam slope positive for females (0.31, 95% CI: -0.09 to 0.72) and negative (-0.24, 95% CI: -0.59 to 0.12) for males, but neither slope was significantly different from zero . Suggests for a small number of amalgam surfaces, GCI outcomes similar for both sexes. However, as no. maternal amalgam surfaces increases, males perform less well, while females' better performance. SES: Higher SES significant predictors of improved scores in some models. Higher HOME score very significant predictor of improved scores in all models and caregiver IQ also significant predictors of improved scores in some models

Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Adverse effect - Comprehensive Battery test for overall intelligence	In primary analysis including 48 models, no adverse association between exposure using either surfaces or occlusal point scores and 46 endpoints. Significant adverse association between amalgam points and Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Achievement for males only. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Prenatal Hg0 exposure (occlusal point score), showed a significant slope of -0.16 (p=.04) in males indicating adverse association. This finding present only using UEL and was present in two models [without (data not shown) and with (Table 5) adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg exposure]. No other adverse associations between any of 4 dental amalgam scores and 6 endpoints either without or with adjustment for MeHg. The UEL carries a higher degree of uncertainty than the LE as derived by including 'possible' restorations. Considering fit 48 primary models, presence of two adverse associations could be chance finding and does not imply prenatal exposure to Hg0 from dental amalgams results in neurobehavioral consequences
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): General Cognitive Index (GCI) of McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities (MSCA)] ³	Results for both LEL and UEL adjusting for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg and covariates (Model 2) in Table 5. Amalgam occlusal points-by-sex interaction term significant for the GCI (LEL and UEL). PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: significant improvement in scores for females on GCI (with LEL and UEL)
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ^{28, 29}	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Adverse effect - Comprehensive Battery test for overall intelligence	In primary analysis including 48 models, no adverse association between exposure using either surfaces or occlusal point scores and 46 endpoints. Significant adverse association between amalgam points and Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Achievement for males only. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Prenatal Hg0 exposure (occlusal point score), showed a significant slope of -0.16 (p=.04) in males indicating adverse association. This finding present only using UEL and was present in two models [without (data not shown) and with (Table 5) adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg exposure]. No other adverse associations between any of 4 dental amalgam scores and 6 endpoints either without or with adjustment for MeHg. The UEL carries a higher degree of uncertainty than the LE as derived by including 'possible' restorations. Considering fit 48 primary models, presence of two adverse associations could be chance finding and does not imply prenatal exposure to Hg0 from dental amalgams results in neurobehavioral consequences
Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁹	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam surface)	Neuropsych (child): Mental Developmental Index of Bayley Scales of Infant Development-II (BSID-II) 9mths	Overall model for MDI at 9mths not significant and none of a priori selected covariates significant predictors of MDI. Amalgam surfaces not a significant predictor at 9mths in models adjusted for MeHg and PUFA. No statistically significant association between amalgam surfaces and developmental outcomes
Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁹	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Mental Developmental Index of Bayley Scales of Infant Development-II (BSID-II)	Overall model at 9 months not significant (p=.08). However, model did show significant occlusal points by sex interaction (p=.05) and adverse association in girls only (p=.03; slope = -0.20, 95% CI: -0.38, -0.02). Overall model at 30 months significant, but neither occlusal points by sex interaction (p=.39), nor association with occlusal points for both sexes combined significant (p=.07)

Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁹	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam surface)	Neuropsych (child): Mental Developmental Index of Bayley Scales of Infant Development-II (BSID-II) 30mnths	At 30 months, model significant and child's sex and PROCESS were significant predictors. Amalgam surfaces not a significant predictor at 30 months in models that adjusted for MeHg and PUFA. No statistically significant association between amalgam surfaces and developmental outcomes.
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/during pregnancy - maternal exposure	Neuropsych: MCDI communication development score: Vocab comprehension and social communication at 15 mnths	Early MCDI communicative development scores not associated with dental amalgam before or during pregnancy. Odds scoring low (lowest 10th percentile of age adjusted z-scores) on assessments generally not associated with maternal dental history, although odds low social activity score slightly reduced among children whose mothers had dental amalgams in place at time of conception. These relationships not modified by infant's term/preterm status, gestational age or birthweight
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Neuropsych: MCDI communication development score: Vocab comprehension at 15 months	72.1 mean (31.6 SD) - NS
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ^{28, 30}	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Neuropsych: MCDI communication development score: Social communication at 15 months	17.4 mean (5.6 SD); Early MCDI communicative development scores not associated with receiving any dental care , or specific procedures e.g. amalgam fillings or x-rays (Table 3). Odds scoring low (lowest 10th percentile of age adjusted z-scores) on assessments generally not associated with maternal dental history, although odds of low social activity score slightly reduced among children whose mothers had dental amalgams in place at conception. These relationships were not modified by infant's term/preterm status, nor when adjusted for gestational age and birthweight
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort]	Maternal exposure Hg (no. amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): Expressive and receptive language ability [Preschool Language Scale (PLS) Total Score]	UEL amalgam surface metric not a significant predictor for any outcomes. When adjusting for UEL amalgam surfaces, increasing recent postnatal MeHg exposure associated with significant improvement in both sexes in the same outcomes: GCI (0.35, p=.02), PLS Total Score (0.22, p=.01)
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Preschool Language Scale (PLS) Total Score] total score	Amalgam occlusal points-by-sex interaction term was significant at UEL. For these outcomes, the slope for amalgam points was significantly different for males and females. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Males performed less well on each outcome compared to females as occlusal points increased. Significant improvement in scores for females (UEL)
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Linguistic understanding 1: Dentist vs physician	No statistically significant difference. Dentist n=365, Mean: 6.87, SE: 0.08 vs Physician n=378, Mean: 6.91, SE: 0.08. Unadjusted regression coefficient: -0.033, 95% CI: -0.263-0.196, p=.775 . Adjusted regression coefficient: 0.085, 95% CI: -0.156-0.325, p=.489
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Linguistic understanding 2: Dentist vs physician	No statistically significant difference. Dentist n=365, Mean: 6.63, SE: 0.08 vs Physician n=378, Mean: 6.84, SE: 0.08. Unadjusted regression coefficient: -0.210, 95% CI: -0.427-0.006, p=.056 . Adjusted regression coefficient: -0.121, 95% CI: -0.348-0.106, p=.296

Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Linguistic understanding 1: Dental nurse vs Assistant nurse	Statistically significant difference. Dental nurse n=3181, Mean: 5.52, SE: 0.03 vs Assistant nurse n=12667, Mean: 4.91, SE: 0.02. Unadjusted regression coefficient: 0.610, 95% CI: 0.539–0.681, p=.000 . Adjusted regression coefficient: 0.432, 95% CI: 0.360–0.503, p=.000
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Linguistic understanding 2: Dental nurse vs Assistant nurse	Statistically significant difference. Dental nurse n=3181, Mean: 5.38, SE: 0.03 vs Assistant nurse n=12667, Mean: 4.79, SE: 0.01. Unadjusted regression coefficient: 0.593, 95% CI: 0.528–0.658, p=.00 . Adjusted regression coefficient: 0.420, 95% CI: 0.354–0.485, p=.000
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (no. amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): Drawing and copying to measure visual-spatial ability (Bender Gestalt test using Koppitz scoring protocol)	UEL amalgam surface metric not a significant predictor for any outcomes. When adjusting for UEL amalgam surfaces, increasing recent postnatal MeHg exposure was associated with significant improvement in male children. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Fewer Bender Gestalt Errors with increasing postnatal MeHg exposure (-0.20, p=.01) in male children
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Spatial recognition: Dental nurse vs Assistant nurse	Statistically significant difference. Dental nurse n=3181, Mean: 5.34, SE: 0.03 vs Assistant nurse n=12667, Mean: 4.86, SE: 0.02. Unadjusted regression coefficient: 0.478, 95% CI: 0.406–0.550, p=.000 . Adjusted regression coefficient: 0.327, 95% CI: 0.254–0.401, p=.000
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Spatial recognition: Dentist vs physician	No statistically significant difference. Dentist n=365, Mean: 660, SE: 0.09 vs Physician n=378, Mean: 6.63, SE: 0.09. Unadjusted regression coefficient: -0.031, 95% CI: -0.274–0.212, p=.802 . Adjusted regression coefficient: -0.0135, 95% CI: -0.271–0.245, p=.920
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (no. amalgam surfaces)	Neuropsych (child): Reading and arithmetic achievement [Letter Word Recognition and Applied Problems subtests of the Woodcock-Johnson (W-J) Tests of Achievement]	The UEL amalgam surface metric was not a significant predictor for any outcomes. When adjusting for UEL amalgam surfaces, increasing recent postnatal MeHg exposure was associated with significant improvement in both sexes in the same outcomes: W-J Applied Problems (0.57, p=.01)
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁸	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Reading and arithmetic achievement [Letter Word Recognition and Applied Problems subtests of the Woodcock-Johnson (W-J) Tests of Achievement]	Amalgam occlusal points-by-sex interaction term significant at UEL. For these outcomes, slope for amalgam points significantly different for males and females. PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: Males performed less well on each outcome vs females as occlusal points increased; Significant adverse association of UEL occlusal point score in males on a single outcome (W-J Letter Word Recognition; slope = -0.16; p=.04 ; 95% CI: -0.31, -0.01); Significant improvement in scores for females (UEL) on W-J Applied problem subtest

Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁹	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam surface)	Neuropsych (child): Psychomotor Developmental Index of Bayley Scales of Infant Development-II (BSID-II)	At 9 and 30mnths, models significant, but Amalgam surfaces for both sexes together not significantly predictive of PDI in any model. At 9 months, child's sex, birth weight, PROCESS, and n-3 PUFA significantly predicted PDI. At 30 months, only child's sex significantly predicted PDI. Prenatal n-3 PUFA positively associated with PDI at 9mnths. No statistically significant association between amalgam surfaces and developmental outcomes. At 9mnths, child's sex significantly predicted PDI. At 30mnths, only child's sex significantly predicted PDI
Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ²⁹	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych (child): Psychomotor Developmental Index of Bayley Scales of Infant Development-II (BSID-II)	All models significant, but occlusal points not a significant predictor of PDI in any model
Watson 2013 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ³²	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam surface)	Neuropsych: Neurodevelopment outcomes	Prenatal dental amalgam surfaces not significantly (bivariately) correlated with any of ten outcomes (correlations ranged from -0.06 to 0.10; p-values all >.10).
Watson 2013 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ³²	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam surface)	Neuropsych: Neurodevelopment outcomes ^a	Regression analysis: association amalgam surfaces as exposure metric with developmental outcomes. Interaction of Hg0 with sex not significant in any model. All models significant except for finger tapping non-dominant hand indicating that the covariates including exposures significantly predicted all outcomes. Prenatal dental amalgam surfaces not associated with any developmental outcome. Child's age and sex associated with outcomes in several models, as were maternal age at delivery, maternal K-BIT, PROCESS score, and prenatal status of n-6
Watson 2013 [Prospective longitudinal cohort] ³²	Maternal exposure Hg (Amalgam occlusal points)	Neuropsych: Neurodevelopment outcomes ^a	Occlusal points the exposure measure and developmental endpoints. All models significant apart from finger tapping non-dominant hand. Prenatal occlusal points not associated with any developmental outcomes. Models using either amalgam surfaces or occlusal points with an alternate metric for prenatal PUFA status (DHA and AA instead of n-3 and n-6) were examined. The use of these alternate metrics for PUFA status did not meaningfully change the exposure-response relationship
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Overall summary: dentists vs physicians	No statistically significant difference: Univariate analysis: dentist cohort slightly lower scores vs physician cohort for all four cognitive tests
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Overall summary: dental nurses vs. assistant nurses	Statistically significant difference: Dental nurses significantly higher scores (p<.001) vs assistant nurse cohort for all four cognitive tests. Almost unaltered after adjustment for father's educational level, mother's age at birth, presence of older siblings and decade of birth
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed-different levels exposure	Neuropsych: Overall summary: dentists vs dental nurses	No statistically significant difference. Linear regression - Categorised high vs low exposure (duration of maternal employment prior to delivery). No association between duration working in dentistry prior to delivery and test scores. Largest non-significant differences among offspring of dental nurses, for technical comprehension test: mean score for those with mothers working in dentistry for <5 years: 5.32, vs

			s5.41 for those with mothers who worked for longer. Adjustment for potential confounding factors made no difference to results
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Technical comprehension: Dentist vs physician	No statistically significant difference. Dentist n=365, Mean: 6.58, SE: 0.09 vs Physician n=378, Mean: 6.64, SE: 0.09. Unadjusted regression coefficient: -0.060, 95% CI: -0.302-0.181, p=.624 . Adjusted regression coefficient: -0.015, 95% CI: -0.270-0.239, p=.905
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³¹	Dental professional maternal exposure- Amalgam exposure assumed vs No amalgam exposure	Neuropsych: Technical comprehension 1: Dental nurse vs Assistant nurse	Statistically significant difference. Dental nurse n=3181, Mean: 5.35, SE: 0.03 vs Assistant nurse n=12667, Mean: 4.88, SE: 0.02. Unadjusted regression coefficient: 0.473, 95% CI: 0.403-0.543, p=.000 . Adjusted regression coefficient: 0.326, 95% CI: 0.255-0.397, p=.000
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (greens shade). achildren’s test battery included: finger tapping [(FT) dominant and non-dominant hands]; three subtests of Preschool Language Scale-Revised Edition [Total Language Score (PLS-TL), Verbal Ability Score (PLS-VA), and Auditory Comprehension (PLS-AC)]; two subtests of Woodcock-Johnson Scholastic, Achievement Test, second edition (Letter-Word Identification and Applied Problems); two subtests of the Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test [Verbal Knowledge (KBIT-VK) and Matrices (KBIT-M)]. Mothers completed Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL), Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test [Matrices (KBIT-M)], and Pediatric Review of Children’s Environmental Support and Stimulation (PROCESS). Higher scores indicate improved performance, except for FT and CBCL. CI=Confidence Interval, GCI=General Cognitive Index, HOME=Home Observation for Measurement of the Environment, IQ=Intelligence Quotient, Hg=Mercury, LEL=Lower Exposure Limit MCDI=MacArthur Communicative Development Inventory, MeHg=Methylmercury, PDI=Psychomotor Development Index, NS=Not Significant, PDI=Psychomotor Development Index PLS=Pre-School Language Scales, PUFA=Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids, SE=Standard Error, SES=Socio-economic Status, UEL=Upper Exposure Limit			

Table 19: Relationship between maternal amalgam exposure and pregnancy outcomes

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2018 [Prospective longitudinal] ³³	Health (Amalgam) vs NA	Pregnancy outcomes: Perinatal death general cohort	Adjusted OR: 1.041 (95% CI 1.008 to 1.076, p=.015), indicating increased risk for perinatal death associated with higher numbers of teeth filled with amalgam. OR almost doubled (OR 1.915, 95% CI 1.12 to 3.28) for participants with 16 teeth filled with amalgam vs participants without amalgam fillings. No major effect from clustering of pregnancies within mothers. Analyses by exposure group: For highest exposure group (participants with 13 or more teeth filled with amalgam) adjusted OR: 2.341 (95% CI 1.267 to 4.324; p=.007)
Bjorkman 2018 [Prospective longitudinal] ³³	Health (Amalgam) vs NA	Pregnancy outcomes: Perinatal death (sensitivity analyses)	In restricted sample excluding mothers with >20 teeth filled with amalgam, adjusted OR: 1.044 (95% CI 1.009 to 1.081, p=.013). Results from analyses of samples excluding pregnancies 30 weeks or shorter, children with malformations, and mothers with preeclampsia/eclampsia, chronic hypertension, and gestational diabetes, showed generally similar, and consistent, results. When children small for gestational age excluded, adjusted OR: 1.063 (95% CI 1.019 to 1.107, p=.004) for continuous measure. For participants with 13 or more teeth with amalgam, adjusted OR: 2.847 (95% CI 1.356 to 5.976; p=.006). PROGRESS-PLUS: Sex: When girls/boys analysed separately, increased risk for girls, but not boys. Adjusted OR girls: 1.053 (95% CI 1.007 to 1.101, p=.024). For boys adjusted OR: 1.032 (95% CI 0.983 to 1.083, p=.203). 5 pregnancies sex of child unknown. Education: In participants with low education (12 years or less) adjusted OR significantly elevated for those in highest exposure group (OR adj 4.28, 95% CI 1.15 to 15.89; p=.030). For participants with high education (more than 12 years) adjusted OR for the highest exposure group 2.08 (95% CI 0.99 to 4.38, p=.053). Association between risk of perinatal death of child and mother's exposure to dental amalgam not statistically significant for participants with high education when continuous exposure measure used and adjusted for covariates. Personal characteristics: Non-smokers who had 13 or more teeth filled with amalgam had an adjusted OR of 2.074 (95% CI from 0.910 to 4.728, p=.083). Adjusted OR using continuous exposure measure higher for non-smokers analysed separately than for entire cohort (OR adj 1.059, 95% CI from 1.021 to 1.099, p=.002). For smoking mothers (n = 5,285) there was less evidence of association. Adjusted OR using continuous exposure measure: 1.013 (95% CI from 0.934 to 1.098, p=.758). When only participants with normal body mass index (BMI from 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m ²) included in analysis, adjusted OR for continuous measure: 1.025 (95% CI 0.974 to 1.080, p=.346). For participants with BMI>25 kg/m ² (overweight and obese), adjusted OR: 1.060 (95% CI 1.016 to 1.105, p=.007)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Stillbirth, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 2(5.26) vs Control n(%): 0(0)

Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Stillbirth, N (%)	Higher prevalence of stillbirth when mothers higher n. teeth with amalgam fillings. In mothers with five teeth or more with amalgam fillings, risk for stillbirth increased. However, after adjustment, OR was reduced and not statistically significant. [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.97 (0.59–1.59), 5-8 amalgam: 1.24 (0.75–2.06), 9+amalgam:1.38 (0.80-2.39) p=.13]. No cases stillbirth in women who had amalgam fillings placed during pregnancy. Removed: adjusted n=147, OR (95%CI): 1.31 (0.61-2.82) p=.49
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Miscarriage, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 9(23.68) vs Control n (%): 4(13.33)
Lindbohm 2007 [Retrospective/cross-sectional with control group] ³⁵	Dental professionals exposure: Dental restorative materials containing acrylate compounds, mercury amalgam vs NA-	Pregnancy outcomes (maternal exposure): Odds ratio of miscarriage for exposure to mercury amalgam (number of amalgam fillings made and removed per week).	Adjusted OR of miscarriage: 2.0 (95% CI 1.0 to 4.1) for moderate exposure to mercury amalgam, but lower for high-exposure category (OR 1.3, 95% CI 0.6 to 2.5). Combining intermediate-exposure and high-exposure categories gave adjusted OR of 1.5 (95% CI 0.8 to 2.8). Distributions of exposed and unexposed miscarriage cases examined by week of pregnancy. Proportion miscarriages systematically higher for unexposed than exposed cases during early pregnancy (10 weeks). For those exposed to mercury amalgam, 30% miscarriages occurred before 10th week of pregnancy, 52% 10-12 weeks and 17% during 13thwk or later. Unexposed: 51%, 34% and 15% respectively
Lindbohm 2007 [Retrospective/cross-sectional with control group] ³⁵	Dental professionals exposure: Dental restorative materials containing acrylate compounds, mercury amalgam vs NA-	Pregnancy outcomes (maternal exposure): Odds ratio of miscarriage for cumulative mercury exposure (number of years of amalgam use before pregnancy daily or nearly daily)	No consistent association found: Not used or stopped 1 or more year earlier (OR 1.0, 95% CI ref); 5 years or more (OR 1.3, 95% CI 0.6 to 2.8); 6-10 years (OR 1.7, 95% CI 0.8 to 3.5); > 10 years (OR 1.3, 95% CI 0.6 to 2.5)
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1960s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	Statistically significant difference in non-adjusted and adjusted analyses. Events dental nurse n=25, Events Assistant nurse n=55. Unadjusted HR: 1.70, 95% CI: 1.02-2.83. Adjusted HR: 1.83, 95% CI: 1.04-3.22
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1960s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=26, Events Assistant nurse n=67. Unadjusted HR: 1.45, 95% CI: 0.89-2.37. Adjusted HR: 1.54, 95% CI: 0.90-2.62
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1960s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=34, Events Assistant nurse n=105. Unadjusted HR: 1.21, 95% CI: 0.80-1.85. Adjusted HR: 1.26, 95% CI: 0.79-1.99

Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1970s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=23, Events Assistant nurse n=97. Unadjusted HR: 0.95, 95% CI: 0.59-1.51. Adjusted HR: 0.98, 95% CI: 0.61-1.58
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control]	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1970s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=30, Events Assistant nurse n=129. Unadjusted HR: 0.93, 95% CI: 0.61-1.41. Adjusted HR: 0.98, 95% CI: 0.64-1.49
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1970s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=45, Events Assistant nurse n=185. Unadjusted HR: 0.97, 95% CI: 0.69-1.36. Adjusted HR: 1.02, 95% CI: 0.72-1.43
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1980s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=19, Events Assistant nurse n=132. Unadjusted HR: 0.67, 95% CI: 0.41-1.09. Adjusted HR: 0.68, 95% CI: 0.42-1.09
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1980s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=31, Events Assistant nurse n=174. Unadjusted HR: 0.83, 95% CI: 0.57-1.22. Adjusted HR: 0.82, 95% CI: 0.56-1.20
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1980s [Dental nurse vs assistant nurse]	No statistically significant difference. Events dental nurse n=40, Events Assistant nurse n=247. Unadjusted HR: 0.79, 95% CI: 0.54-1/05. Adjusted HR: 0.76, 95% CI: 0.54-1.06
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1960s [Dentist vs physician]	Insufficient data to support statistical comparison. Events Dentist n=0, Events Physician n=1
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control]	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1960s [Dentist vs physician]	Insufficient data to support statistical comparison. Events Dentist n=0, Events Physician n=3
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1960s [Dentist vs physician]	Events Dentists n=1, Events Physician n=5. Unadjusted HR: 0.17, 95% CI: 0.02-1.48. Adjusted HR: 0.32, 95% CI: 0.04-2.68
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1970s [Dentist vs physician]	Events Dentists n=3, Events Physician n=1. Unadjusted HR: 3.54, 95% CI: 0.37-33.61. Adjusted HR: 3.78, 95% CI: 0.28-50.95

Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1970s [Dentist vs physician]	Events Dentists n=3, Events Physician n=1. Unadjusted HR: 3.54, 95% CI: 0.37-33.61. Adjusted HR: 3.78, 95% CI: 0.28-50.96
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1970s [Dentist vs physician]	Events Dentists n=4, Events Physician n=4. Unadjusted HR: 1.18, 95% CI: 0.30-4.68. Adjusted HR: 1.38, 95% CI: 0.30-6.36
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Neonatal mortality (N): 1980s [Dentist vs physician]	No significant association between maternal profession and mortality among offspring and hazard ratios were all close to unity (Events Dentists n=8, Events Physician n=11. Unadjusted HR: 1.35, 95% CI: 0.54-3.34. Adjusted HR: 1.19, 95% CI: 0.48-2.96
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Infant mortality (N): 1980s [Dentist vs physician]	No significant association between maternal profession and mortality among offspring and hazard ratios were all close to unity. Events Dentists n=10, Events Physician n=14. Unadjusted HR: 1.32, 95% CI: 0.59-2.97. Adjusted HR: 1.23, 95% CI: 0.55-2.74
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Childhood mortality (N): 1980s [Dentist vs physician]	No significant association between maternal profession and mortality among offspring and hazard ratios were all close to unity. Events Dentists n=11, Events Physician n=18. Unadjusted HR: 0.13, 95% CI: 0.54-2.39. Adjusted HR: 1.11, 95% CI: 0.52-2.37
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Overall summary: Dentists vs Physicians	No significant association between maternal profession and mortality among offspring and hazard ratios all close to unity ^a
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ³⁶	Dentist vs physician: maternal exposure - Mercury assumed	Pregnancy outcomes: Overall summary dental nurse vs assistant nurse	Statistically significant difference in non-adjusted and adjusted analyses for neonatal mortality in 1960s. No statistically significant difference for neonatal mortality for other decades. Pattern of reducing mortality risk over time: HR (95% CI): 63 (0.44–0.90) demonstrates a reduction in mortality. Results for infant and childhood mortality show same pattern, but not statistically significant^a

Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Overall summary: birth outcomes	Low birth weight, preterm birth and multiple births increased over time, SGA, stillbirth and prenatal death decreased over time (p<.001 for all). Offspring of dental personnel did not have excess risks of low birth weight, SGA, being disproportionately of male gender, stillbirth, and prenatal death in any of time periods. However, occasional significantly lower risks of some outcomes observed for dental personnel in some stratified analyses e.g. where dental assistants (all) had reduced risk of SGA in time period 1967–1976 (adjusted RR 0.78, 95% CI 0.63–0.95) and dental assistants (in employment) had reduced risk of low birth weight time period 1997–2006 (adjusted RR 0.46, 95% CI 0.23–0.90). Since level of significance not adjusted for multiple testing, results must be interpreted with care. Performed analyses with dental personnel stratified into groups based on years in employment prior to delivery, which did not influence the results. PROGRESS-PLUS: Preterm birth and multiple births: dental assistant increasing risk over time vs controls, dentists had decreasing risk. However, in analyses stratified by 10-year periods, risks of these outcomes for dental personnel not significantly different from control group in any time period. Gender: No change in proportion male births
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Exposure to amalgam prior to pregnancy (number of fillings) and birthweight	0 (n=531, 7.2%); 1 (n=383, 5.2%); 2-3 (n=1196, 16.2%); 4+ (5265, 71.4%) Women who had more amalgams in place at conception had lower probability of having a term low birthweight infant (p=.02). When restricted to mothers who received dental care during pregnancy, results associated with each type of dental procedure were unchanged (data not shown).
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Birthweight (grams)	3450 mean (521 SD) Odds of term low birthweight or preterm birth not associated with maternal history of dental care during pregnancy or having an amalgam filling placed or removed
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Low birth-weight baby, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 4(10.52) vs Control n (%): 1(3.33)
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Low birthweight (<2500 g)	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.06 (0.93–1.21), 5-8 amalgam: 1.01 (0.87–1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.17 (0.99–1.38) p=.19]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=1719: Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.60 (0.30, 1.21), p=.15 Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.07 (0.82, 1.40), p=.61]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Low birthweight at 37-42 weeks	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.16 (0.91–1.47), 5-8 amalgam: 0.97 (0.74–1.28), 9+amalgam: 0.97 (0.70–1.35) p=.56]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=483: Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.01 (0.38, 2.73), p=.98 Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.95 (0.55, 1.62), p=.84]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Birthweight (grams)	Statistically significant positive correlation between birthweight and number of amalgams in place during pregnancy (Pearson correlation: 0.046, p <.001)

Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Small for gestational age	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.96 (0.89–1.05), 5-8 amalgam: 0.96 (0.87–1.05), 9+amalgam:0.98 (0.88–1.09) p=.59]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=4488: Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.16 (0.83, 1.62, p=.40 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.16 (0.98, 1.37), p=.080] PROGRESS-Plus: Sex: Girls born by mothers who had removed one or more amalgam fillings had slightly elevated risk for being small for gestational age (below 10th percentile). Unadjusted OR=1.28 (95% CI from 1.01 to 1.61; p=.039), adjusted OR=1.30 (95% CI from 1.02 to 1.64; p=.031)
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Very small for gestational age	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.96 (0.80–1.14), 5-8 amalgam: 0.97 (0.80–1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.06 (0.85–1.32) p=.64]. No significant association found with amalgam placed/removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=964: Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.37 (0.72, 2.57, p=.34 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.02 (0.71, 1.46), p=.93]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Length (cm)	Significant positive correlation between height and n.teeth with amalgam fillings. (Test for trend p <.001)
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Mercury concentration in umbilical cord at birth	0.013 geometric mean (1.03 Standard Error); Although mean umbilical cord mercury concentration slightly higher among those whose mothers had any dental care (p=.07), did not differ markedly in relation to amalgam fillings during pregnancy (p=.34) or by no.amalgams in place prior to conception (p=.32) . Total mercury levels in umbilical cord tissue low for this population (median=0.01 µg/g wet weight) and not associated with gestational age (β=0.03, p=.63), birthweight (β=-18.6, p=.22) or developmental scores
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy (Maternal exposure)	Pregnancy outcomes: Mercury concentration in umbilical cord at birth	0.013 geometric mean (1.03 Standard Error); Although mean umbilical cord mercury concentration slightly higher among those whose mothers had any dental care (p=.07), did not differ markedly in relation to amalgam fillings during pregnancy (p=.34) or by no. amalgams in place prior to conception (p=.32) . Overall, total mercury levels in umbilical cord tissue low for this population (median=0.01 µg/g wet weight) and not associated with gestational age (β=0.03, p=.63), birthweight (β=-18.6, p=.22) or developmental scores
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Conception difficulties, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 8(21) vs Control n (%): 2(6.66)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Child with learning difficulties, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 5(13.5) vs Control n (%): 2(6.66)
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Child with developmental delay, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%): 2(5.26) vs Control n (%): 1(3.33)

Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Late preterm delivery (33-37wks)	No significant association found with n.teeth amalgam or amalgam placed/removed in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.07 (0.96-1.19), 5-8 amalgam: 1.03 (0.91-1.16), 9+amalgam: 1.11 (0.97-1.27) p=.28]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=2605: Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.59 (0.33, 1.04), p=.07 Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.06 (0.85, 1.32), p=.59]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Early Pre-term delivery (at or before 32wks)	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.87 (0.66-1.16), 5-8 amalgam: 1.01 (0.75-1.36), 9+amalgam: 1.08 (0.77-1.52) p=.47]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=378: Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.34 (0.47, 2.42), p=.28 ; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.43 (0.87, 2.33), p=.16]
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control] ²²	Copper amalgam/Hg exposure vs no exposure - Dental professional	Pregnancy outcomes: Child with birth defect, N (%)	No significant difference between groups. Total N: Exposed n=38 vs Control n=30. Exposed N (%):7(18.42) vs Control n (%): 3(10)
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Malformations	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol. [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.03 (0.94-1.14), 5-8 amalgam: 1.05 (0.94-1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.07 (0.95-1.21) p=.26]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=3234: Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.93 (0.60, 1.42), p=.73 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.98 (0.80, 1.21), p=.87]
Hegglund 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Overall summary: Congenital birth malformations	When adjusting for potential confounders: no statistically significant differences in occurrence of congenital malformations between groups, except for reduced risk of children with clubfoot in all dental assistants. Analyses stratified by 10-year periods for all congenital malformations: no significant differences in adverse outcomes risk between groups in any time periods. No excess risk found for any time periods in other malformation categories in stratified analyses. Other adverse pregnancy outcomes: no statistically significant differences between dental personnel vs control. PROGRESS-PLUS: Reduced risk of children with clubfoot in all dental assistants [All: n=11, per 1000: 1.2, RR: 0.66, 95% CI: 0.36-1.19, Adj RR:b 0.24, 95% CI: 0.06-0.94]. Time trend analysis: statistically significant increase in no. registered congenital malformations (all and major) over time was observed (p<.001), which did not differ between occupational groups^b

Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): All malformations	No significant difference between groups (except clubfoot, see below). All Dental personnel (including dental personnel not in employment): Control group N=75163, per 1000: 32.4, RR: 1.00, 95% CI NR, Adjusted RR: 1.00, 95% CI NR; Dental Assistants: N=258, per 1000: 27.5, RR: 0.85, 95% CI 0.75-0.96, Adjusted RR: 0.90, 95% CI 0.76-1.08; Dentists: N=79, per 1000: 38.1, RR: 1.19, 95% CI 0.95-1.49, Adjusted RR: 0.89, 95% CI 0.62-1.28. Dental personnel in employment: Control group N=75163, per 1000: 32.4, RR: 1.00, 95% CI NR, Adjusted RR: 1.00, 95% CI NR; Dental Assistants: N=114, per 1000: 30.5, RR: 0.94, 95% CI 0.78-1.14, Adjusted RR: 0.95, 95% CI 0.74-1.23; Dentists: N=56, per 1000: 35.6, RR: 1.10, 95% CI 0.84-1.45, Adjusted RR: 0.86, 95% CI 0.57-1.28b
Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Major malformations	No significant difference between dental personnel vs control (both all dental personnel and those in employment) See Table 2 in paper (all dental personnel & those in employment)
Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Malformations of the CNS	No significant difference between dental personnel vs control (both all dental personnel and those in employment) See Table 2 in paper (all dental personnel & those in employment)
Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Dysplasia of the hip	No significant difference between dental personnel vs control (both all dental personnel and those in employment) See Table 2 in paper (all dental personnel & those in employment)
Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ³⁷	Amalgam/mercury vapour vs no exposure - dental professionals	Pregnancy outcome (dental professionals): Overall summary: birth outcomes	Low birth weight, preterm birth and multiple births increased over time, SGA, stillbirth and prenatal death decreased over time (p<.001 for all). Offspring of dental personnel did not have excess risks of low birth weight, SGA, being disproportionately of male gender, stillbirth, and prenatal death in any of time periods. However, occasional significantly lower risks of some outcomes observed for dental personnel in some stratified analyses e.g. where dental assistants (all) had reduced risk of SGA in time period 1967–1976 (adjusted RR 0.78, 95% CI 0.63–0.95) and dental assistants (in employment) had reduced risk of low birth weight time period 1997–2006 (adjusted RR 0.46, 95% CI 0.23–0.90). Since level of significance not adjusted for multiple testing, results must be interpreted with care. Performed analyses with dental personnel stratified into groups based on years in employment prior to delivery, which did not influence the results. PROGRESS-PLUS: Preterm birth and multiple births: dental assistant increasing risk over time vs controls, dentists had decreasing risk. However, in analyses stratified by 10-year periods, risks of these outcomes for dental personnel not significantly different from control group in any time period. Gender: No change in proportion male births
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (greens shade). aAll adjusted outcomes adjusted for the father's educational level and mother's age at delivery, bPROGRESS PLUS: Adjusted for maternal age, educational level, parity and year of birth. Births clustered by mother. BMI=Body Mass Index, CI=Confidence Interval, CNS=Central Nervous System, HR=Hazard Ratio, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, OR=Odds Ratio, RR=Risk Ratio, SGA=Small for Gestational Age			

Table 20: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and pregnancy outcomes

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Early Pre-term delivery (at or before 32wks)	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.87 (0.66–1.16), 5-8 amalgam: 1.01 (0.75–1.36), 9+amalgam: 1.08 (0.77–1.52) p=.47]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=378: Placed: OR (95% CI)=0.34 (0.47, 2.42), p=.28 ; Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.43 (0.87, 2.33), p=.16]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Late preterm delivery (33-37wks)	No significant association found with n.teeth amalgam or amalgam placed/removed in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.07 (0.96–1.19), 5-8 amalgam: 1.03 (0.91–1.16), 9+amalgam: 1.11 (0.97–1.27) p=.28]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=2605: Placed: OR (95% CI) =0.59 (0.33, 1.04), p=.07 Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.06 (0.85, 1.32), p=.59]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Low birthweight (<2500 g)	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.06 (0.93–1.21), 5-8 amalgam: 1.01 (0.87–1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.17 (0.99–1.38) p=.19]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=1719: Placed: OR (95% CI) =0.60 (0.30, 1.21), p=.15 Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.07 (0.82, 1.40), p=.61]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Low birthweight at 37-42 weeks	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.16 (0.91–1.47), 5-8 amalgam: 0.97 (0.74–1.28), 9+amalgam: 0.97 (0.70–1.35) p=.56]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=483: Placed: OR (95% CI) =1.01 (0.38, 2.73), p=.98 Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.95 (0.55, 1.62), p=.84]

Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Birthweight (grams)	Statistically significant positive correlation between birthweight and number of amalgams in place during pregnancy (Pearson correlation: 0.046, p < .001)
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Small for gestational age	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.96 (0.89–1.05), 5-8 amalgam: 0.96 (0.87–1.05), 9+amalgam:0.98 (0.88–1.09) p=.59]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=4488: Placed: OR (95% CI) =1.16 (0.83, 1.62, p=.40 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.16 (0.98, 1.37), p=.080] PROGRESS-Plus: Sex: Girls born by mothers who had removed one or more amalgam fillings had slightly elevated risk for being small for gestational age (below 10th percentile). Unadjusted OR=1.28 (95% CI from 1.01 to 1.61; p=.039), adjusted OR=1.30 (95% CI from 1.02 to 1.64; p=.031)
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Very small for gestational age	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.96 (0.80–1.14), 5-8 amalgam: 0.97 (0.80–1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.06 (0.85–1.32) p=.64]. No significant association found with amalgam placed/removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=964: Placed: OR (95% CI)=1.37 (0.72, 2.57, p=.34 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 1.02 (0.71, 1.46), p=.93]
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Malformations	No statistically significant associations with n.teeth with amalgam fillings in model controlling for age education, BMI, parity, smoking, alcohol. [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 1.03 (0.94–1.14), 5-8 amalgam: 1.05 (0.94–1.17), 9+amalgam: 1.07 (0.95–1.21) p=.26]. No significant relationship with amalgam placed or removed during pregnancy [Adjusted model, n=3234: Placed: OR (95% CI) =0.93 (0.60, 1.42), p=.73 . Removed: OR (95% CI): 0.98 (0.80, 1.21), p=.87]

Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Stillbirth, N (%)	Higher prevalence of stillbirth when mothers higher n.teeth with amalgam fillings. In mothers with five teeth or more with amalgam fillings, risk for stillbirth increased. However, after adjustment, OR was reduced and not statistically significant. [OR (95% CI): 1-4 amalgam: 0.97 (0.59–1.59), 5-8 amalgam: 1.24 (0.75–2.06), 9+amalgam:1.38 (0.80-2.39) p=.13]. No cases stillbirth in women who had amalgam fillings placed during pregnancy. Removed: adjusted n=147, OR (95%CI): 1.31 (0.61-2.82) p=.49
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ³⁴	Maternal exposure Amalgam	Pregnancy outcomes: Length (cm)	Significant positive correlation between height and n.teeth with amalgam fillings. (Test for trend p <.001)
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Exposure to amalgam prior to pregnancy (No. fillings) and birthweight	0 (n=531, 7.2%); 1 (n=383, 5.2%); 2-3 (n=1196, 16.2%); 4+ (5265, 71.4%) Women who had more amalgams in place at conception had lower probability of having a term low birthweight infant (p=.02). When restricted to mothers who received dental care during pregnancy, results associated with each type of dental procedure were unchanged (data not shown).
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Mercury concentration in umbilical cord at birth	0.013 geometric mean (1.03 SE); Although mean umbilical cord mercury concentration slightly higher among those whose mothers had any dental care (p=.07), it did not differ markedly in relation to amalgam fillings during pregnancy (p=.34) or by no.amalgams in place prior to conception (p=.32). Total mercury levels in umbilical cord tissue low for this population (median=0.01 µg/g wet weight) and not associated with gestational age (β=0.03, p=.63), birthweight (β=-18.6, p=.22) or developmental scores
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ³⁰	Amalgam restoration before/after pregnancy - maternal exposure	Pregnancy outcomes: Birthweight (grams)	3450 mean (521 SD) Odds of term low birthweight or preterm birth not associated with maternal history of dental care during pregnancy or having an amalgam filling placed or removed
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Strong (green shade). BMI=Body Mass Index, CI=Confidence Interval, OR=Odds Ratio, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, wks=Weeks,			

Patient studies

Table 21: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and adverse events

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2023 [Prospective longitudinal] ³⁸	Amalgam removal+replacement in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No replacement	Adverse event: Aggravation of symptoms (N)	9/31 patients (28.1%; three women and six men; mean age 49.9yrs, SD 5.5) reported aggravation of symptoms within 1wk after treatment session. Reported symptoms: urticaria, headache, fatigue, facial pain/jaw pain/sinusitis, exhaustion, sound sensitivity, dizziness, flu-like symptoms and facial eczema. Experienced aggravation of symptoms within 1wk after treatment not predictor for change score of GHC index above median 10.95 (odds ratio 0.7, 95% CI 0.2 to 3.4, p= .695)
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement in individuals with MUPS with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, Metallo ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Adverse events/Dental treatment: Replacement of filling	During treatment period, 282 amalgam restorations replaced with other dental restorative materials. 18 (6.4%) of new restorations revised during 5yr follow-up period. 14 of these were restorations with polymer-based composites. Main reason for revision: new caries lesions in conjunction with the restoration (secondary caries)
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement in individuals with MUPS with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, Metallo ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Adverse event: Aggregation symptoms (Relationship increased GHC Health variables with Personality variables])	8/20 participants (40%) reported increased health complaints in conjunction with amalgam removal. Index scores for GHC were available for 7 of these participants+for 10 who did not report increased health complaints. Change in GHC over time showed slightly different patterns for two groups, although interaction between time and reaction status not statistically significant (p= .126) . Analysis of MMPI-2 profile at pre-treatment revealed participants who reported increased symptoms had slightly different profiles vs those who did not. Depression, Hysteria, and Psychopathic Deviate scales significantly lower in those who did not report increased symptoms (p< .05) . However, mean PSY-5 scores scales showed no significant difference between the two groups
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Amalgam removed, restoration with ceramic or gold inlays, or composite restoration vs Removal +biological detoxification vs No removal	Adverse events: Complaints (N)	43 participants (removal: 12/30 (40%), removal+bio detox: 14/29 (48%), no removal: 17/31 (55%), respectively, for three groups) reported 73 complaints as 'new'. Overall, 16% of complaints were gastrointestinal symptoms, 15% arthralgia/back pain, 11% dental problems due to replacement of restorations (only in the removal groups), 10% skin diseases, 7% infections, 7% sensory disturbances, and 34% other complaints. Four women (all in removal-plus group) became pregnant
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and Metallo ceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Adverse event: Complaints (N)	Seven participants in treatment group (35%) experienced increased health complaints following removal of amalgam fillings , including: gastric pain, pain in joints and muscles, oral ulcers, sore throat, pain in legs, hands and feet, dizziness, tachycardia, nausea, diarrhoea, depression, fatigue, chills, burning sensations in the face, cold hands, increased blood pressure and submandibular lymphadenopathy. Complaint increases transient and disappeared within a week or two
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and Metallo ceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Adverse events: Complaints (N)	7 participants treatment group (35%) experienced increased health complaints in connection with removal amalgam fillings. Laboratory tests of blood samples collected within few days after treatment session showed values within reference intervals . Health complaints reported: gastric pain, pain in joints and muscles, oral ulcers, sore throat, pain in legs, hands and feet, dizziness, tachycardia, nausea, diarrhoea, depression, fatigue, chills, burning sensations in face, cold hands, increased blood pressure and submandibular lymphadenopathy. Increase in complaints transient, disappeared within 2wks

Bjorkman 2023 [Prospective longitudinal] ³⁸	Amalgam removal+replacement in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs no replacement	SAE (N)	No SAE registered, but 3 patients had to terminate project participation before finished treatment due to health reasons
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Amalgam removed, restoration with ceramic or gold inlays, or composite restoration vs Removal +biological detoxification vs No removal	SAE: SAE (N)	3 SAE (in-patient surgical treatments considered unrelated to study condition and intervention) documented; all persons continued trial
Study quality: Low (red shade). CI=CI, GHC=General Health Complaints, GIC=Glass Ionomer Cement, MMPI=Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, psy-5=Personality Psychopathology Five scales, SAE=Serious Adverse Events, SD=Standard Deviation, wks=Weeks			

Table 22: Patient amalgam exposure - allergy

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Ahlgren 2014 [Case control] ⁹	Exposure: Amalgam or composite restoration in individuals with OLL vs DP or PSFF	Allergy: Hg allergy, N (%)	Significant difference between groups: 9 patients (10.8 %) OLL group and one from DP group tested positively for mercury (Fisher's exact test: p=.03). All 9 patients with contact allergy to mercury had OLL adjacent to amalgam filling. 4 patients showed a solitary day 7 reaction to mercury 0.5 % (w/w) in petrolatum. 3 of them retested with 1.6 % Hg Softisan. 8 OLL patients retested with 1.6 % Hg Softisan because of doubtful reactions on day 3; 3 had contact allergy to mercury after retesting. These patients showed positive reactions to 0.5 % mercury on day 7
Ahlgren 2014 [Case control] ⁹	Exposure: Amalgam or Composite restoration in individuals with OLL vs DP or PSFF	Allergy: Nickel sulphate allergy	No significant difference between groups: Contact allergy to nickel sulphate more common in DP vs OLL group but not statistically different: (Pearson's chi-square test: p=.054). PSFF vs OLL groups, no statistically significant difference re: nickel sulphate
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Allergy: Hg allergy (N)	All subjects reporting oral symptoms (n = 27) patch tested using the European Standard and Dental Material Series and all but one found to have negative response. One subject had weak response to mercury amalgam
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Blood & Urine Hg - those with/without allergies	Allergy: Relationship blood/urine Hg and Allergies	Complaints n=26 vs No complaints n=30. No sig. difference in blood/urine Hg levels and those experiencing allergies vs those not. Blood=Mean: 22.48 (13.84) vs 17.46 (9.09), p=.1469 , urinary=Mean: 16.65(13.54) vs 17.38 (9.75), p =.8432
Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁴³	Exposure: Amalgam in women with diagnosis 'Allergic stomatitis' vs women with 'Noninflammatory oral complaints'	Allergy: Amalgam, ammoniated mercury	Significantly higher rates of sensitization detected for those with stomatitis vs those not (10.9% vs. 3.1%; 3.5-fold).
Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁴³	Exposure: Women with diagnosis 'Allergic stomatitis' vs women with 'Noninflammatory oral complaints'. Allergen: Multiple	Allergy: Patch test results: Allergen- metals	Allergic stomatitis (n=444) vs Non-inflammatory oral complaints (n=1231) Allergen, Concentration, Tested (N), Positive (N), Positive (%), 95% (CI): N.S: Amalgam alloy metals (Si, Cu, Sn, Zn) 20% pet. 441 1 0.2 (0.0-1.3) 1210 2 0.2 (0.0-0.6). Women with 'allergic stomatitis' showed no significant differences in co-/cross-sensitization vs control group women with 'noninflammatory oral complaints'
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Health (amalgam)	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to amalgam in Atopic vs Non-atopic patients (%)	Amalgam: No statistically significant difference in sensitization between Atopic vs Non-atopic group (17.5% vs 2.5%)
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Exposure: Mercury in patients diagnosed Atopic vs Non-atopic	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to ammoniated mercury in Atopic vs Non-atopic patients - (%)	Ammoniated mercury: No statistically significant difference in sensitization between atopic vs Non-atopic group (25% vs. 15%)

Weber 2012 [Prospective longitudinal with control] ⁴⁵	Exposure [Amalgam/Hg]: Patch testing 28 metal allergens commonly used in dental repairs in patients with history oral SCC vs Control no history oral disease:	Allergy/Cancer: OR Exposure to Metal Contact Allergen Groups in Control Patients versus SCC patients Whose Metal Dental Restoration Adjacent to SCC Sit	Of patients with history oral SCC, 12% (8 of 65) allergic to mercury and amalgam compounds. Patients with oral SCC>3 times as likely as control patients to have contact allergy to mercury (OR, 3.20; 95% CI, 0.42 to 33.20). Patients with oral SCC with an adjacent dental restoration had higher likelihood of allergy to silver compounds or mercury or amalgam compounds (OR, 3.23) than patients with no history of oral SCC
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (greens shade). DP=Dermatitis Patients, Hg=Mercury, N=Number, PSFF=Patients Selected From Files, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OR=Odds Ratio, N=Number, SCC=Squamous Cell Carcinoma			

Table 23: Patient amalgam removal/replacement - allergy

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 [Prospective clinical observational] ⁴⁶	Amalgam removed, replacement with composite (OLL) vs Min. 1 amalgam (no OLL)	Allergy: Patch test reaction, N (%)	Patch testing was only positive in 2 patients (28.57%); positive results obtained with thimerosal (organic component of mercury) and nickel. No correspondence found between these cases and those presenting direct contact with the amalgam
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷	Partial/complete replacement of amalgams vs No removal/replacement	Allergy: Positive patch test reaction to mercury, N (%)	10 (32%) patients tested positively to mercury. OLL: Reticular pattern (n=6), erosive/atrophic pattern (n=4) of OLL. Four patients had clinically corroded amalgams
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷		Allergy: Negative patch test reaction to mercury, N (%)	21 (68%) patients with negative reactions to mercury
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷		Allergy: Positive Reactions to Allergens in British Society of Cutaneous Allergy Standard Series, Dental Series, Amalgam Series, and Methacrylate Series, N (%)	0.5% Mercury 10 (32) 5% Nickel sulphate 7 (23) 0.5% Gold sodium thiosulfate 3 (10) 1% Cobalt chloride 3 (10) 2% Palladium chloride 2 (6) 2% Copper Sulphate 2 (6) 2% Toluidine diethanolamine 1 (3) 1% Camphorquinone 1 (3) 3% Carba mix 1 (3) 0.1% Potassium dicyanoaurate 1 (3)

Marell 2016 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁸	Replacement/partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars vs No replacement among individuals with OLP/OLR	Allergy: Hg Allergy+Remission of lesion, N (%)	OLP group 5/6 = 83% allergic Hg. No remission upon removal dental amalgam. LCR group: 7/12 (58%) reacted to mercury. All seven patients with positive reactions to mercury had regression of all lesions after a total replacement of amalgams. Not possible to determine whether choice of replacement material had sign. impact on lesion remission
Marell 2016 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁸	Replacement/partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars vs No replacement among individuals with OLP/OLR	Allergy: Summary	Baseline: 31/44 patients (70%) patch-tested with dental screening series and 18 /31 (58%) showed positive reactions, 12 with LCR (12/31 = 39%) and 6 with OLP (6/13 = 41%). Most frequent allergens: mercury (12/31 = 39%) and gold (7/31 = 22%), followed by nickel (5/31 = 16%). Patch-test positive in LCR group: 7/12 (58%) reacted to mercury, 6/12 (50%) reacted to gold, 3/12 (25%) reacted to nickel. 11 of these 12 patients with LCR had partially/totally exchanged restorations, and nine (82%) showed total remission
Marell 2016 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁸	Replacement/partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars vs No replacement among individuals with OLP/OLR	Allergy: Summary	Most frequently identified allergens among patients with positive patch test reactions in OLP group: mercury (5/6 = 83%), gold (1/6 = 17%) and nickel (2/6 = 33%)

<p>Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 [Retrospective cohort]⁴⁹</p>	<p>Amalgam restoration replacement for individuals with OLR. Complete replacement of all amalgam fillings with fillings based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these vs Healthy controls no OLR</p>	<p>Allergy: Positive patch test reaction to mercury/amalgam (N)</p>	<p>16/20 patients showed sensitization to inorganic mercury or amalgam. 4 patients showed positive reaction to min.1 organic derivatives of mercury</p>
<p>Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups]⁵⁰</p>	<p>Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal</p>	<p>Allergy: Allergic reactions Munich Amalgam Scale (Within group: Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)</p>	<p>Baseline to 1yr Follow-up: Non-significant change. Amalgam cohort: 1.06, 0.28, p=.071, 0.33, 95% CI= -0.03, 0.68</p>
<p>Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)]⁵¹</p>	<p>Amalgam removal vs non-removal among individuals patch test positive vs negative</p>	<p>Allergy: Summary</p>	<p>Patch test: 79.1% patients positive min. 1 allergen tested and 67.8% to allergy specifically related to dental materials. 60 patients (52.2%) positive to amalgam-related allergen (ammoniated mercury 1%, amalgam 5%, amalgam alloying metal 20%, nickel sulphate 5%). Among suspected OLR group (n = 94), 70 (74%) tested positive to dental allergens, eight (38%) tested positive among smaller group diagnosed as atypical OLR or OLP (n = 21) resistant to therapy (p=.003, Fisher's exacttest). Significantly more women reacted positive to patch testing (p<.001), in men, distribution between positive and negative skin patch test similar. No statistically significant differences between skinpatch-test-positive and patch-test-negative patient groups found re: age, ethnicity and smoking habits. Lateral margin of tongue affected significantly more frequently in patients tested positive to any dental material than in patch-tested-negative patients(p=.008), dorsum of tongue less frequently affected (p=.036). Bilateral localisation tended to appear more often in the patch-negative group (p=.07). 31 patients (27.0%) reacted positive to one agent tested, 25 patients (21.7%) to two and 22 (19.1%) to >3 allergens in dental materials. Most frequent dental material allergens: ammoniated mercury 1% in 27.0%, cobalt chloride 1% in 26.1%, nickel sulphate 5% in 23.5% and amalgam 5% in 23.5% of patients. Of 98 patients presenting with dental amalgam fillings, 29 (29.6%) reacted to ammoniated mercury 1%, 26 (26.5%) to amalgam 5% and 4 (4.1%) to amalgam alloying metal 20%. Overall, 18 positive test results to allergens found in synthetic dental materials occurring in 16 patients (13.9%)</p>
<p>Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)]⁵¹</p>	<p>Amalgam removal vs non-removal among individuals patch test positive vs negative</p>	<p>Allergy: Ammoniated mercury 1% Positive skin patch test, N (%)</p>	<p>Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=15) 31 (27.0)</p>

Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Amalgam removal vs non-removal among individuals patch test positive vs negative	Allergy: Amalgam positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=15): 27 (23.5)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Amalgam removal vs non-removal among individuals patch test positive vs negative	Allergy: Amalgam alloying Metal, 20%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=15): 4 (3.5)
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). Cl=Cl, Hg=Mercury, LCR=Lichenoid Contact Reactions, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus, OLR=Oral lichenoid reactions, SRM=Standardized Response Mean			

Table 24: Patient amalgam exposure and cardiovascular symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Blood/Urine Hg Exposure Amalgam vs No Amalgam	CVD: N complaints	Complaints n=13 vs No complaints n=53. No sig. difference in blood/urine exposure and those experiencing CVD vs those not. Blood=Mean: 17.30 (9.49) vs 20.62 (12.37), p =0.4358; urinary=Mean: 8.56 (5.17) vs 19.41 (11.85), p=.0113
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	CVD: N CVD complaints (%)	Amalgam vs control Self-reported symptoms - 121 (35.4) vs 87 (25.4) p=.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	CVD: Heart/chest problem, N (%)	No significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 74 (22.0%) vs 49 (14.5%) p=.026
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	CVD: Oedema legs, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 70 (20.8%) vs 47 (13.9%) p=.019
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	CVD: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS Stomach ache - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS (amalgam<environmental) Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', 'skin reactions', 'frequent toilet urge', 'memory disturbance', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, N=Number, NS=Not Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SS=Statistically significant			

Table 25: Patient removal/replacement amalgam and CVD symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal+replacement of amalgam vs external reference group	CVD: Intensity of CVD complaints from pre-treatment to 3 yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: Mean:2.4(2.90) vs 1.08(2.46) p=.538 , Standardized Response Mean: 0.162
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	CVD: GHC Symptoms at 1yr (Q2) and 5yr (Q3) after removal compared to before removal (Q1) (mean intensity)	Amalgam cohort- Significant at both follow-ups: Before removal: 2.0 (0.3); 1 year after removal: 0.8 (0.3), p <.001 ; 5 years after removal: 1.1 (0.3), p= 0.018. MUPS cohort No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: - Baseline (Q1): 1.4 (0.3) ; 1-st follow-up (2 years after Q1): 1.2 (0.3), p= 0.414; 2nd follow-up (4 years after Q2): 1.3 (0.3), p= 0.658 Healthy cohort (no MUPS)- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1-st follow-up (2 years after Q1):0.1 (0.3) ; 2nd follow-up (4 years after Q2): 0.2 (0.6), p= 0.778
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	CVD: Arrythmia Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Amalgam cohort: 0.75, 0.28, p= 0.027, 0.41, 95% CI= 0.05, 0.77
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	CVD: Reduction of symptoms over time	Amalgam cohort: Highest ESs (estimated by SRM) found for ‘metallic taste’ (0.93), ‘stress at the job’ (0.83), ‘skin rash’ (0.57), ‘sensitivity to cold and wind’ (0.54), ‘worries – restlessness’ (0.53), and ‘irritability’ (0.52); and significant reduction of intensity of symptoms was shown Moderate ESs (around 0.4) were found for items ‘feeling of walking next to oneself’, ‘ arrythmia ’, ‘diarrhoea’, ‘increased urge to toilet’, ‘indecision’, ‘abdominal pain’, ‘lack of concentration’, ‘fluctuating mood’, ‘anxiety’, and ‘burning sensation in tongue’, all being statistically significant
Study quality: Low (red shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, ES=Effect Size, M=Mean, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, SD=Standard Deviation, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, yr=Year			

Table 26: Patient amalgam exposure and dermatological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Dermatological: N (%)	Significant difference between groups. Amalgam vs control SS - 86 (25.1) vs 60 (17.5) p<.05
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Dermatological: Skin problem, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 85 (25.2%) vs 62 (18.4%) p=.032
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Dermatological: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS Stomach ache - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', ' skin reactions ', 'frequent toilet urge', 'memory disturbance', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). N=Number, NS=Not Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SS=Standard Score			

Table 27: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and dermatological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam + replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Dermatological: Intensity of facial skin problems from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	NS change pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: Mean:1.4(2.22) vs 1.0 (1.87) p=. 306, SRM: 0.242
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam + replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Dermatological: Intensity of general skin problems from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	NS pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: Mean:2.2(2.59) vs 1.0(1.41) p=. 053, SRM: 0.476
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal in MUPS/Healthy cohorts	Dermatological: General skin problems (GHC: mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort- Significant reduction from baseline at follow-up 1 but not significant at follow-up 2. Before removal: 2.7 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 1.8 (0.4), p=. 020; 5yrs after removal: 1.9 (0.4), p=. 076. MUPS cohort- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: - Baseline (Q1): 1.7 (0.4); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 1.4 (0.4), p=. 514; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 1.7 (0.4), p=. 896. Healthy cohort (no MUPS)- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.9 (1.4); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.5 (1.1); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.5 (0.8), p=. 769
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal in MUPS/Healthy cohorts	Dermatological: Munich amalgam scale: Skin rash (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant change Baseline to 1 year follow-up: Amalgam cohort: 0.97, 0.34, p=. 003, 0.57, 95% CI=0.19, 0.94
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal in MUPS/Healthy cohorts	Dermatological: Munich amalgam scale: Skin itching (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change Baseline to 1 year follow-up: Amalgam cohort: 1.16, 0.28, p=. 059, 0.35, 95% CI= -0.01, 0.70
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal in MUPS/Healthy cohorts	Dermatological: Reduction of symptoms over time	Amalgam cohort: Highest ESs (estimated by SRM) found for ‘metallic taste’ (0.93), ‘stress at the job’ (0.83), ‘skin rash’ (0.57), ‘sensitivity to cold and wind’ (0.54), ‘worries – restlessness’ (0.53), and ‘irritability’ (0.52); and significant reduction of intensity of symptoms shown.
Study quality: Weak (red shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=CI, ES=Effect Size, GHC=General Health Complaints, N=Number, M=Mean, MUPS=Medically unexplained physical symptoms, NS=Non-significant, SD=Standard Deviation, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, SS=Standard Score, yr=Year			

Table 28: Patient amalgam exposure and ear, nose and throat (ENT) symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	ENT: Auditory problem, N %	Amalgam vs control SS - 99 (28.9) vs 89 (26.0) NS
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	ENT: Auditory problem, N %	NS difference between groups , amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 98 (29.1%) vs 87 (25.8%)
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade). ENT=Ear, Nose and Throat, N=Number, NS=Not-Significant, SS=Standard Score			

Table 29: Patient's amalgam restoration/replacement and ENT symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	ENT: Hearing disorders- Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change Amalgam cohort: 0.72, 0.06, p=.423, 0.14, 95% CI= -0.21, 0.49
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	ENT: Tinnitus-Munich amalgam scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change Amalgam cohort: 1.19, 0.19, p=.110, 0.29, 95% CI= -0.07, 0.64
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	ENT: Symptoms from ear/nose/throat-General Health Complaints (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	NS change Amalgam cohort at both follow-ups- Before removal: 3.5 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 2.8 (0.4), p=.069; 5yrs after removal: 2.8 (0.4), p=.140 . MUPS cohort – NS changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 1.9 (0.4); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 1.5 (0.4), p=.415 ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 2.1 (0.4), p=.614. Healthy cohort (no MUPS)-NS changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.0 (0.1); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.1 (0.3), p=.111
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	ENT: Intensity of complaints for symptoms from ear/nose/throat [m] (pretreatment)	Intensity of complaints for symptoms from ear/nose/throat in treatment group vs external reference group - 4.0 (n=19) vs 1.8 (n=441)
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	ENT: Intensity of ENT complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	Statistically significant reduction pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: (paired sample t-test) Mean: 4.0(2.54) vs 2.2(2.15) p=.002, Standardised Response Mean: 0.833 (n=19)
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	ENT: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with p≤0.05 (memory loss and stomach problems) and with p≤0.1 an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion, loss of sense of smell or taste , shakiness in hands). Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms (confusion, stomach problems, loss of sense of smell or taste , shakiness in hands, coordination problems) were statistically significant when p≤.05 and another two (headache, muscle weakness) when p≤0.1 . Loss sense of smell or taste. Treatment group symptoms improve: 1.588[0.0727] (p<.1) Treatment group symptoms get worse: 0.376 (p<.05) [0.000508] 369
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=CI, ENT=Ear, Nose and Throat, m=Mean, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SS=Standard Score, yrs=Years			

Table 30: Patient amalgam exposure and gastrointestinal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Gastrointestinal: Complaints, N %	Amalgam vs control SS - 112 (32.7) vs 65 (19.0) p<.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Gastrointestinal: Stomach-ache, N (%)	Significant difference between groups , amalgam related complaints vs control: 81 (24.0%) vs 51 (15.1%) p=.004
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Gastrointestinal: Constipation, N (%)	Significant difference between groups , amalgam related complaints vs control: 40 (11.9%) vs 19 (5.6%) p=.004
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Gastrointestinal: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS Stomach ache - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', 'skin reactions', ' frequent toilet urge ', 'memory disturbance', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade). Hg=Mercury, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, SS=Statistically significant			

Table 31: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and gastrointestinal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metaloceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Gastrointestinal: GHC index	Analyses of changes in complaint intensity from pre-treatment to 5yr follow-up: six items significantly reduced: increased salivation, pain from muscles and joints, gastrointestinal symptoms , fatigue, memory problems, and difficulty concentrating. No items significantly increased vs pre-treatment value
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Symptoms GHC questionnaire (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups. Before removal: 3.4 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 3.0 (0.4), p=.226 ; 5yrs after removal: 2.8 (0.5), p=.140. MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups. Baseline (Q1): 3.2 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 2.9 (0.5), p=.551 ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 2.7 (0.5), p=.360. Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.6 (0.9); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.7 (1.3); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.6 (1.1), p=.842
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+ replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Gastrointestinal: Intensity of complaints for gastrointestinal symptoms [M] (pretreatment)	Intensity of complaints for gastrointestinal symptoms in treatment group vs external reference group - 4.8 (n=19) vs 1.8 (n=441) Statistically higher scores at 3yr follow-up for treatment group than reference group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+ replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Gastrointestinal: Intensity of gastrointestinal complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [M, SD, p-value] [Within group]	Statistically significant reduction pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: (paired sample t-test): Mean: 4.8 (2.54) vs 3.5 (2.57), p=.038 , SRM: 0.512 (n=19)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: diarrhoea (Munich amalgam scale): (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant improvement from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.75, 0.28, p=.027 , 0.41, 95% CI=0.05, 0.77
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Vomiting (Munich amalgam scale): (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.13, -0.03, p=.662 , -0.08, 95% CI= -0.42, 0.27

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Increased urge to toilet (Munich amalgam scale): (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant improvement from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 1.09, 0.28, p=.027 , 0.41, 95% CI=0.05, 0.77
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Reduction of symptoms over time-GHC questionnaire	Amalgam cohort: Highest ESs (estimated by SRM) found for 'metallic taste' (0.93), 'stress at the job' (0.83), 'skin rash' (0.57), 'sensitivity to cold and wind' (0.54), 'worries – restlessness' (0.53), and 'irritability' (0.52); and significant reduction of intensity of symptoms was shown Moderate ESs (around 0.4) were found for items 'feeling of walking next to oneself', 'arrythmia', ' diarrhoea ', ' increased urge to toilet ', 'indecision', ' abdominal pain ', 'lack of concentration', 'fluctuating mood', 'anxiety', and 'burning sensation in tongue', all being statistically significant
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Constipation (Munich amalgam scale): (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.59, 0.06, p=.601 , 95% CI=0.09 -0.26, 0.44
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Gastrointestinal: Abdominal pain (Munich amalgam scale): (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant improvement from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.94, 0.28, p=.027 , 0.41, 95% CI=0.05, 0.77
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	Gastrointestinal: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with p ≤ .05 (memory loss and stomach problems) and with p ≤ 0.1 an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands). Symptom worsening: Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms (confusion, stomach problems , loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands, coordination problems) were statistically significant when p ≤ 0.05
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, ES=Effect Size, GHC=Global Health Complaints, GIC=Glass Ionomer Cement, M=Mean, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, SE=Standard Error, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, yr=Year			

Table 32: Patient amalgam exposure and general physical health symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Amalgam in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No amalgam	General physical health: Other disorders/ comorbidities (N)	Complaints n=13 vs No complaints n=43. No sig. difference in blood/urine Hg exposure and those experiencing other disorders vs those not. Blood=Mean: 14.33 (11.18) vs 21.83 (11.55), p=.4641 ; urinary=Mean: 8.56 (5.17) vs 19.41 (11.85), p=.7724 . PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: After adjusting for age/gender, blood/urine HG not significantly related to other disorders (OR, 95% CI, p value): Blood: 0.941 (0.874, 1.013) 0.1043, Urine: 0.823 (0.696, 0.974) p=.0233 . Unrelated to n.amalgams: 1.032 (0.222, 4.786) p=.9681
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Summary Self-Reported symptoms (mean number)	Mean no.symptoms for amalgam group: 5.4 (SD = 3.3), vs 3.7 (SD = 2.8) for control individuals (p <.001) Participants with self-reported amalgam-related complaints also reported multiple symptoms more often (p<.001). Of those in the amalgam group, 26% reported having 8 or more symptoms, compared with 9% among control individuals
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Reported symptoms (mean number)	Amalgam-related complaints: 5.4 (SD = 3.3), vs 3.6 (SD = 2.8) for controls (p<.001); 42% reported they did not feel well vs 24% Controls. Difference statistically significant (p< .001) , 26% amalgam group report eight or more symptoms vs 9% Controls (p<.0001). N=337 both groups
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Dizziness, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 81 (24.0%) vs 49 (14.5%) p=.002
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Loss of appetite, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 12 (3.6%) vs 4 (1.2%) p=.04

Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Sleeplessness, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 96 (28.5%) vs 67 (19.9%) p=.009
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Fatigue, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 58 (46.9%) vs 98 (29.1%) p<.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Self-reported symptom change over 5 yrs, mean (SD)	N=81 each group. Amalgam group had mean of 4.9 (SD 3.2) self-reported symptoms before the onset of amalgam-related complaints, and 5.5 (SD 3.4) symptoms at test occasion after the onset 5yrs later. Difference not significant. Matched controls for same period reported mean 3.6 (SD 2.7) symptoms at first occasion, and 3.6 (SD = 2.9) at second
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	General physical health: Self-reported symptoms	NS before and after for amalgam
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	General physical health: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Overall 16 symptoms matched from the 50-item list for sample 1 and SOMS for sample 2)	With respect to the selected symptoms, amalgam patients reported statistically significantly fewer symptoms on average than patients suspecting their complaints to other causes , also after controlling for age, sex, and education. Out of the predefined list of 16 symptoms, the mean (SD) sum of existing symptoms was 3.3 (2.1), while the 'other group' showed a mean (SD) of 5.3 (3.1) symptoms.
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	General physical health: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS Stomach ache - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS <i>Shortness of breath</i> - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms ' sweating ', 'skin reactions', 'frequent toilet urge', 'memory disturbance', and ' shortness of breath ', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group

Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	General physical health: Other symptoms in moderate to strong intensity, 10 with highest prevalence	Amalgam Group (Symptom List): General faintness - 56.7% Susceptibility to stress - 47.2% Susceptibility to infections - 46.7% Restlessness/acathisia - 40.0% Lack of concentration - 37.8% Allergic reactions - 37.1% Testiness - 35.6% Nervousness - 34.4% Itching - 33.7% Indecisiveness - 30.3%
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). Hg=Mercury, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SD=Standard Deviation, SOMS= patient-administered questionnaire to screen for somatoform disorders, SS=Standard Score			

Table 33: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and general physical health symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2023 [Prospective longitudinal] ³⁸	Amalgam removal+replacement in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No replacement	General physical health: Amalgam surface and GHC index	No. amalgam surfaces baseline: small and non-significant correlation with GHC change score. Increase by 10 amalgam surfaces increased odds ratio by 1.2 (95% CI 0.6 to 2.4; p= .524, n=32). Analyses mean GHC over time from Q1 to Q3 in three cohorts using linear mixed models: results consistent with analyses of change from Q1 to Q2. Amalgam cohort: Q3 mean GHC score significantly lower vs Q1 (p< .001). NS change over time for other two cohorts. Decrease GHC score not significantly associated with change in concentration of serum I-Hg from Q1 to Q2 (p= .605). Amalgam cohort effect size: 0.70 change from Q1 to Q2 (95% CI 0.41 to 0.99), 0.87 change from Q1 to Q3 (95% CI from 0.53 to 1.20)
Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ⁵⁷	Removal+ replacement other materials vs No removal/ healthy	General physical health: GHC index (12-month follow-up)	Baseline to follow-up: GHC index significantly reduced in Amalgam cohort, (p< .001), No significant change observed for MUPS or Healthy cohorts. GHC-index change score (GHC index at Q1 minus GHC index at Q2) significantly higher in Amalgam cohort (mean 12.8, SD 15.9) vs MUPS cohort (mean 1.2, SD 12.3; p= .004), indicating more symptom reduction in Amalgam cohort. After adjustment for covariates (gender, age, education and baseline GHC index), significant difference between mean difference in GHC-index change score between Amalgam cohort and MUPS cohort: -8.0 (95% CI from -15.4 to -0.5; p= .036). PROGRESS-PLUS: Amalgam cohort, predictors of change of GHC index at follow-up analysed. Significant effects found for GHC index at baseline (p< .001) and education. Participants with higher education had significantly more improvement (measured by GHC index)
Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ⁵⁷	Removal+ replacement other materials vs No removal/ healthy	General physical health: SF 36 Physical and Mental Component Summary scores (12-month follow-up)	Baseline to follow-up, scores increased significantly in Amalgam cohort (p=.001 and p=.009, respectively), indicating improved health status. MUPS and Healthy cohorts: no significant changes from baseline to follow-up

Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ⁵⁷	Removal+ replacement other materials vs No removal/ healthy	General physical health: SF 36 Physical Component Summary (12 month follow-up)	Change score Amalgam cohort (mean -5.1, SD 7.9): significantly larger vs MUPS cohort (mean 0.9, SD 7.1; p= .004) indicating more improvement in Amalgam cohort. Mean adjusted difference between amalgam cohort and MUPS cohort for SF 36 Physical Component Summary: 5.9 (95% CI from 1.5 to 10.3, p= .009)
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference SF-36 physical health between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	No significant differences between groups re: mean differences. Removal (n=26): 3.9 (8.5); removal+biol. Detox (n=24): 2.4 (11.5); no removal (n=21): 1.0 (6.9); p=.546
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	General physical health: Summary scores for SF-12: physical health component score (PCS)	NS inter-group differences between men and women, younger and older age groups, replacement and non-replacement groups or application approval and rejection with respect to PCS . Compared with general population in Sweden, subjects significantly lower HRQoL in terms of PCS (mean, 37.2; CI 95%, 35.6–38.87 compared to 50.2; CI 95%, 50.0–50.4 in the general population). Post hoc analysis excluding subjects on disability pensions disclosed PCS still significantly lower than for corresponding ages in general population (P < 0.0001)
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	General physical health: Health improvement over time – self reported poor, moderate, good	2yrs post application year, self-rated health replacement vs non-replacement: improved: 23.6% vs 6.5%, remained same: 72.1% vs 77.4%, deteriorated 4.3% vs 16.1%. Three years after application year, self-rated health replacement vs non replacement: improved: 32.6% vs 16.1%, unchanged: 62.7% vs 67.7%, deteriorated: 4.7% vs 16.1%. Significantly higher proportions improved health rating over time in replacement vs non-replacement group, both 2 and 3yrs after application year (year 0) (p=.005 and .015 , respectively). Two and 3 years after submission of application, proportions of subjects in replacement and non-replacement groups reporting improved, unchanged or deteriorated health status over time remained relatively constant, though no longer statistically significant (p=.111 after 2 years; p= 0.082 after 3 yrs).
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metallo-ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	General physical health: GHC index	Following amalgam removal: significant reduction of GHC index from 44.6 at pre-treatment to 32.8 at 5yr follow-up (p= .001). Mean change scores for GHC index were -11.3 (SD 14.3), -12.0 (SD 15.7), and -11.0 (SD 14.7) at follow-up after 1, 3, and 5yrs, respectively (n = 18). Negative numbers indicate improved health/reduction of health complaints. Effect sizes (SRM): 0.79, 0.76, and 0.75. Decrease complaint intensity most pronounced for pain from muscles and joints, GI symptoms, fatigue, and memory problems. Analyses of changes in complaint intensity from pre-treatment to 5yr follow-up: six items significantly reduced: increased salivation, pain from muscles and joints, gastrointestinal symptoms, fatigue, memory problems, and difficulty concentrating. No items significantly increased vs pre-treatment value

Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metaloceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	General physical health: GHC index and SHC correlation	Correlation between GHC index score SHC total scale score highly significant. Total SHC score decreased from 22.7 at pre-treatment to 20.6 at 5yr follow-up (N.S). No significant changes of any SHC subscales over time
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference main complaints sum score between baseline and 12 months (mean, SD)	No significant difference between groups: Where missing values replaced by baseline values, 'main complaints' sum score decreased by average 3.5 (SD = 2.2) points each in removal and removal-plus groups (n=30 and n=29 respectively), and by 2.5 (SD = 2.4) in no-removal group (n=31) (non-adjusted p=.152; ITT population) (p-value non-significant). P-value for ANCOVA among groups adjusted for baseline values: 0.091 (non-significant)
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference total symptoms score (0-150) between Baseline and Month 12 - mean (SD)	No significant differences between groups re: mean differences. Removal (n=27) -21.8 (17.6); removal+biol.Detox (n=25): - 24.0 (16.5); no removal (n=23): -16.3 (12.2) p=.230
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference no. of complaints (0-50) between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	No significant differences between groups re: mean differences. Removal (n=27): -9.7 (8.4); removal+biol. Detox (n=25): - 10.5 (9.2); no removal (n=23): - 7.6 (7.7); p=.487
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference no. of strong complaints between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	No significant differences between groups re: mean differences. Removal (n=27): -4.5 (3.2); removal+biol.Detox (n=25): -4.7 (3.0); no removal (n=23): - 3.6 (2.5) p=.437
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	General physical health: Difference between 12 month and 18 months	Descriptive analyses indicated persistent improvements up to month 18

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Fatigue – General Health Complaints (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort-Significant reduction in symptoms at both follow-ups: Before removal: 5.9 (0.5); 1yr after removal: 4.7 (0.5), p=.003; 5yrs after removal: 3.2 (0.5), p<.001 . MUPS cohort-No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 5.4 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 4.9 (0.5), p=.313; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 5.3 (0.5), p=.742 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS)-No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.7 (1.0); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.4 (0.7); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.3 (0.6), p=.879. PROGRESS-PLUS: Amalgam cohort- An increase of 10yrs age associated with lower ‘fatigue’ symptom intensity (1.5; 95% CI 0.4 to 2.6; p=.008)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Fatigue – Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 1.72, 0.28, p=.059 , 0.35, 95% CI= -0.01, 0.70
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	General physical health: Intensity of complaints for fatigue [m] (pretreatment)	Intensity of complaints for fatigue in treatment group vs external reference group - 5.6 (n=19) vs 3.0 (n=441)
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	General physical health: Intensity of fatigue complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	Statistically significant reduction pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: (paired sample t-test) Mean: 5.6,(2.91) vs 3.83 (2.27), p=.006 SRM: 0.717 (n = 19)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Dizziness (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort-Significant change in symptoms: Before removal: 2.7 (0.4); 1yr after removal:1.6 (0.4), p=.004; 5yrs after removal: 1.7 (0.4), p=.024 . MUPS cohort -No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 2.6 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 2.5 (0.4), p=.763; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 2.6 (0.5), p=.997 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS)- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.2); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.2 (0.4), p=.444
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	General physical health: Intensity of dizziness complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:2.3(3.0) vs 1.5(1.81) p=.135, SRM: 0.359
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Dizziness (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort:0.97, 0.19, p=.083, 0.32, 95% CI= -0.04, 0.67

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Headache (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort-Significant change in symptoms: Before removal:2.8 (0.5); 1yr after removal: 2.3 (0.5), p=.261; 5yrs after removal: 1.6 (0.5), p=.008 . MUPS cohort- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 3.5 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1):3.8 (0.5), p=.479 ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 4.2 (0.5), p=.117. Healthy cohort (no MUPS) No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.2 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.4 (0.5); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.2 (0.6), p=.194
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	General physical health: Intensity of headaches complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:3.5(3.70) vs 2.7(2.50) p=.284, SRM: 0.253
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Symptom reduction at 1yr (Q2) and 5yr (Q3) after removal compared to before removal (Q1) (mean intensity)	Amalgam cohort: mean intensity of each of all 23 items reduced at first follow-up (Q2) vs baseline; 14 symptoms significantly reduced. Largest reductions (ES about 0.6) observed for intraoral pain/tenderness, taste disturbance, cardiovascular complaints, difficulty concentrating, and anxiety/depression. At second follow-up (Q3), reduction in mean intensity observed for all but one item vs baseline (Q1)
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	General physical health: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with p≤0.05 (memory loss and stomach problems) and with p≤0.1 an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands). Worsening of symptoms: Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms (confusion, stomach problems , loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands, coordination problems) were statistically significant when p ≤ 0.05 and another two (headache, muscle weakness) when p ≤ 0.1
Weidenhammer 2010 [Retrospective data analysis of RCT] ⁵⁹	Amalgam removal vs No removal	General physical health: Baseline physical component of HRQoL (SF-36 score PCS)	Before intervention, both groups mean score on physical component of HRQoL (SF-36 score PCS) similar to norm samples. NS between groups. PROGRESS-PLUS: The SF-36 PCS improved more in male patients (r =0.23, p<0.05)
Weidenhammer 2010 [Retrospective data analysis of RCT] ⁵⁹	Amalgam removal vs No removal	General physical health: Post intervention physical component of HRQoL (SF-36 score PCS)- changes from baseline to month 12?	NS difference between groups. No correlation of the dummy variable (removal of fillings, 0 = no, 1 = yes) with any psychometric outcome variables
Weidenhammer 2010 [Retrospective data analysis of RCT] ⁵⁹	Amalgam removal vs No removal	General physical health: Post intervention Symptoms - changes from baseline to 12 months?	Both groups showed symptom score reduction of approx. 50% at month 12. Larger reductions in mercury level after intervention associated with larger decrease in symptom scores (r =0.24–0.42). No statistically significant differences between groups

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Trembling (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 0.50, 0.16, p=.096 , 0.30, 95% CI= -0.05, 0.66
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Sleeplessness (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 1.25, 0.22, p=.198 , 0.23, 95% CI= -0.12, 0.58
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Getting tired fast (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 1.88, 0.13, p=.423 , 0.14, 95% CI= -0.21, 0.49
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Susceptible to infection (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 0.66, 0.16, p=.407 , 0.15, 95% CI= -0.20, 0.50
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Loss of appetite (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 0.47, 0.19, p=.083 , 0.32, 95% CI= -0.04, 0.67
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Headache (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 1.06, 0.00, p=1.000 , 0.00, 95% CI= -0.35, 0.35
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Cough attacks (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 0.41, 0.00, p=1.000 , 0.00, 95% CI= -0.35, 0.35

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups]	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Hair loss (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 0.41, 0.13, p=.458 , 0.13, 95% CI= -0.22, 0.48
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Increased sweating (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS Change: Amalgam cohort: 1.03, 0.25, p=.088 , 0.31, 95% CI= -0.05, 0.66
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	General physical health: Sensitivity to cold, wind (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Statistically significant change: Amalgam cohort:1.25, 0.41, p=.005 , 0.54, 95% CI= 0.16, 0.91
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison group] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	General physical health: Changes in health complaints related to changes in mercury concentration in serum and orofacial complaints	Secondary explorative analyses of correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in health complaints 3yrs after treatment showed positive but not significant correlations . Pearson correlation coefficients were 0Æ320, 0Æ193 and 0Æ127 for correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in intra-oral, extra-oral and general indices, respectively. Corresponding P-values were 0Æ182, 0Æ428 and 0Æ604 (n = 19), leaving no statistically significant support for mercury as a cause of the complaints
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison group] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	General Physical Health: Changes in health complaints related to changes in mercury concentration in serum and	Secondary explorative analyses of correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in health complaints 3yrs after treatment showed positive but not significant correlations . Pearson correlation coefficients were 0Æ320, 0Æ193 and 0Æ127 for correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in intra-oral, extra-oral and general indices, respectively. Corresponding P-values were 0Æ182, 0Æ428 and 0Æ604 (n = 19), leaving no statistically significant support for mercury as a cause of the complaints
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison group] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	General physical health: Changes in health complaints in treatment group-General index	Treatment group: significant reductions in mean index scores for general health complaints from Questionnaire 1 to the 3yr follow-up. ITT analysis showed similar results as per-protocol analysis. In repeated measures analysis, data from pre-treatment examination and all follow-ups included. Per-protocol repeated measures analysis showed significant overall effects of time for all three index scores

Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison group] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	General physical health: Comparisons of changes in health complaints in the treatment group and reference group – general index	Per-protocol comparisons changes in health complaints, from Questionnaire 1 to the 3-yr follow-up in the treatment group and Questionnaire 3 in reference group: changes in mean index scores for intra-oral and general health complaints significantly different in the two groups. After adjusting for gender, age and complaint intensity reported in Questionnaire 1, changes in in general health complaints remained significantly different. ITT analysis: similar to results from per-protocol analyses. Results from analyses based on data from the reference group after post hoc application of exclusion criteria showed no major differences compared with the analyses using all 13 participants from initial reference group. Unadjusted per-protocol differences in changes in index scores between treatment group and the reference group after application of exclusion criteria were 19Æ9 (95% CI: 8 Æ1 to 31Æ7, p=.002) for general indices,
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	General physical health: Receiving disability pension (N)	No.subjects receiving disability pensions much higher than general population (23% and 10%, respectively)
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, CR=Composite Resin, ES=Effect Size, GHC=General Health Complaints, HRQOL=Health Related Quality of Life, ITT=Intention to Treat, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, PCS=Physical Component Score RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SD=Standard Deviation, SF-36=Short Form Survey, SHC=Subjective Health Complaints, SRM=Standardised Response Mean, yrs=Years			

Table 34: Patient amalgam exposure and immune function

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Chen 2021 [Retrospective observational] ⁶⁰	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Immune function: Primary Sjogren's syndrome (Diagnosis)	No statistically significant difference in AMF between Non-pSS and pSS (adjusted OR: 0.974, 95% CI = 0.904–1.049). AMF (n=3282) vs non-AMF (n=2566)
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Immune function: Mean blood Hg level (nmol/L) and autoimmune disease	19.9 ± 11.8 (range 0–47) nmol/L. Mean values significantly lower than normal threshold value for blood/urine mercury of 50 nmol/L. N amalgams 0-5 (8 people). Mean blood Hg: 23.75 (SD17.10), N amalgams 6-10 (18 people). Mean blood Hg: 16.93 (SD 8.35), N amalgams >10 (19 people). Mean blood Hg: 19.81 (SD13.16). No sig difference blood Hg based on no. amalgams (p=.4641) . PROGRESS-PLUS: Relatively higher blood mercury levels in subjects with presenting complaints in oral cavity (23.65 vs 16.33, p=.0320) and blood mercury levels of two patients with MS higher than those without MS (47.00 vs 19.33, p=.0186). Hg levels in blood or urine, or N.amalgams not significant for MS or previously diagnosed autoimmune disease
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Immune function: Autoimmune disease (%)	Significant difference in N. Amalgams between subjects reporting autoimmune diseases vs those not (p=.0317). Previously diagnosed autoimmune disease more common in group with >10 amalgams (26.3%), vs those 6-10 amalgams (5.6%) or 0-5 amalgams (0%)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a4}	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Total WBC count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Granulocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %DHE+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.7

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %Rho+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -1.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %DHE+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %Rho+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Total WBC count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Granulocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT]	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte cell count	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell: %CD69+ PHA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.5
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell: %CD25 + PHA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD69+PWM	Significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -2.1 (-3.8, -0.4) p=.01
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD23+PWM	Significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -3.8(-6.2, -1.4) p=.002

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %DHE+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function %Rho+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.6
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a5}	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Immune function: Functional status monocytes (free radicals O ₂ ⁻ = ethidium fluorescence)	Monocytes amalgam population: responsiveness within 5–7 days (7.8%); this trend did not persist beyond this time point. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %DHE+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative permanent teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %Rho+PMA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.2
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁵	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Immune function: Functional status neutrophils (free radicals H ₂ O ₂ =dihydrorhodmine fluorescence)	Neutrophil responses exhibited fluctuation within and between both treatment groups however none of these were statistically significant. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell %CD69 + PHA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell %CD25 + PHA	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:b -0.3
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT]	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Immune function: Responsiveness T-cells (Activation markers CD69/CD25)	Amalgam slight NS decline in responsiveness T-cells at 5-7 days. No differences consistently observed at 6, 12 or 60mnths. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁵	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Immune function: Proliferative responses T-cells	NS difference between groups. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion. [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD69+PWM	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: b 0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Amalgam (Restorative primary teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD23+PWM	NS association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: b 0.3
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁵	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Immune function: B-cell function (expression of CD69/CD23)	NS difference between groups. No consistent trends or statistically significant differences in immune function measures comparing children with low, medium, or high levels of urinary mercury excretion [Statistical detail: see paper Table 3]
Study quality: Strong (green shade) aNew England Amalgam Trial, bMultivariable models for resin-composite materials were adjusted for each type of resin-composite material (number of surfaces currently treated with sealant/preventive resin restoration, compomer, or composite), age, time from baseline visit, study site, baseline blood lead level, and parent-reported asthma or allergy. Models for amalgam were created to parallel models for composites, and therefore mutually adjusted for amalgam on primary and permanent teeth, as well as sealant/preventive resin restorations, age, time from baseline visit, study site, baseline blood lead level, and parent-reported asthma or allergy. Models included immune function changes from pretreatment at 6-months, 1-year, 1.5-year, and 5-year follow-up visits. AMF=Amalgam Fillings, CI=Confidence Interval, DHA=Docosahexaenoic Acid, DHE=Dehydroepiandrosterone, Hg=Mercury, MS=Multiple Sclerosis, N=Number, NR=Not Reported, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, PHA=Phytohaemagglutinin, PMA=Phorbol Myristate Acetate, PSS=Primary Sjögren syndrome, PWM=Pokeweed Mitogen, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, WBC=White blood Cell			

Table 35: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and immune function

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2012 [Pilot: CBA] ⁶¹	Amalgam restorations removed+replacement other dental restorative materials in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam vs Blood donors	Immune function: Concentration cytokines in serum - concentration (pg/ml)	Baseline: patient group significantly higher values for IL-2R, IFN-alpha, IL-7, and IL-12p40/p70 vs reference group. Minor significant differences between groups for GM-CSF and IL-6. No significant differences of values reference vs patient group over time. Patient group: Statistically significant, decrease over time towards median value of reference group for GM-CSF, IL-8, and IL-7. Baseline median concentration GM-CSF 17 pg/ml. Median value 3mnths after amalgam removal unchanged , but at 1yr median below 15 pg/ml (p=.041; Friedman test). Concentration IL-8 decreased median 17 pg/ml baseline to 11 pg/ml and 13 pg/ml at 3 and 12mnths, respectively (p=.013; Friedman test). For IL-7 serum concentration 49 pg/ml baseline. 3mnths after amalgam removal median value decreased to 39 pg/ml, which was unchanged 1yr after removal (p=.027; Friedman test)
Bjorkman 2012 [Pilot: CBA] ⁶¹	Amalgam restorations removed+replacement other dental restorative materials in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam vs Blood donors	Immune function: Anti-nuclear antibodies - antibody levels against antigens	Antinuclear antibodies detected in one patient. Reference group: No antinuclear antibodies detected

Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs No intervention	Immune function: WBC (109/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 5.9 (1.7); Before: 6.5 (2.2); After: 5.9 (1.9); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<.05
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs No intervention	Immune function Blood neutrophil count (109/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 3.1 (1.2); Before: 3.7 (1.6); After: 3.3 (1.5); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<.001
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Immune function: Blood eosinophil count (108/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 2.0 (1.2); Before: 1.9 (1.5); After: 2.2 (1.9); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<.001
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs No intervention	Immune function: Blood basophil count (107/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 5.0 (4.9); Before: 5.5 (3.0); After: 3.3 (2.9); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<.001
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs No intervention	Immune function: blood lymphocyte count (109/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 2.0 (0.7); Before: 2.1 (0.6); After: 1.9 (0.5); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<0.01
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs No intervention	Immune function: Blood monocyte count (108/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 4.5 (1.8); Before: 3.6 (1.1); After: 4.8 (1.5); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<0.001
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	Immune function: Susceptibility to infection (N)	Significantly higher proportion replacement group reported symptoms than non-replacement group (p=.007)
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 [Retrospective cohort] ⁴⁹	Amalgam restoration replacement for individuals with OLR. Complete replacement of all amalgam fillings with fillings based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these vs Healthy controls no OLR	Immune function: Levels of IL-6: 10–2 pg/mL (median (IQR))	Levels IL-6 pre-filling replacement significantly > IL-6 levels following replacement. Before: 43.1 (24.1-55.4) vs After: 0.5 (0.2-2.2) (p=.003) (n=20). Values pro-inflammatory cytokines returned to levels similar to control group (n=20). Levels IL-6 measured before and after intervention in control subjects did not differ significantly (p=.226)
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 [Retrospective cohort] ⁴⁹	Amalgam restoration replacement for individuals with OLR. Complete replacement of all amalgam fillings with fillings based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these vs Healthy controls no OLR	Immune function: Levels of IL-8: 10–2 pg/mL (median (IQR))	Levels of IL-8 measured pre-filling replacement significantly > IL-8 levels following replacement. Before: 58.1 (43.5–77.6) vs After: 0.3 (0.9–12) (p< 0.001). Values pro-inflammatory cytokines returned to levels similar to control group. Levels IL-8 measured before and after intervention in control subjects did not differ significantly (p=.199)

Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CR=Composite Resin, GM-CSF=Granulocyte Macrophage-Colony Stimulating Factor, IL=Interleukin, IQR=Inter-Quartile Range, mnths=Months, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, OLR=Oral Lichenoid Reactions SD=Standard Deviation, WBC=White Blood Cell

Table 36: Patient amalgam exposure and musculoskeletal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam	MSK: Blood/urinary Hg and MSK complaints (N)	Complaints n=34 vs No complaints n=22. No sig. difference in blood/urine Hg levels and those experiencing MSK complaints vs those not. Blood=Mean: 19.07 (10.99) vs 21.16 (13.12), p=.5578 ; urinary=Mean: 16.56(11.69) vs 17.93 (11.83), p=.7244
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	MSK: Musculoskeletal, N (%)	Amalgam vs control standard score - 266 (77.7) vs 217 (63.5) <.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	MSK: Back pains, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 169 (50.1%) vs 103 (30.6%) p<.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	MSK: Aching shoulders, arms, or legs, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 220 (65.3%) vs 163 (48.4%) p<.001
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	MSK: Aching joints, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 165 (48.8%) vs 100 (29.7%) p <.001
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	MSK: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS <i>Stomach ache</i> - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', 'skin reactions', 'frequent toilet urge', 'memory disturbance', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). MSK=Musculoskeletal, N=Number, NS=Not Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SS=Statistically Significant			

Table 37: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and musculoskeletal symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metaloceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) in people with complaints attributed to amalgam vs NA	MSK: GHC index	Decrease complaint intensity most pronounced for pain from muscles and joints. Analyses of changes in complaint intensity from pre-treatment to 5yr follow-up: six items significantly reduced: increased salivation, pain from muscles and joints , gastrointestinal symptoms, fatigue, memory problems, and difficulty concentrating. No items significantly increased vs pre-treatment value
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	MSK: Mean intensity complaints pains from muscles/joints (pre-treatment)	Pretreatment: Intensity of complaints for pains from muscles and joints in treatment group vs external reference group - 6 (n = 19) vs 3.6 (n = 441). Statistically higher scores 3yr follow-up for treatment group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	MSK: Intensity muscle/ joint pain complaints pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	Statistically significant reduction: pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up: (paired sample t-test) Mean: 6.0 (2.60] vs 5.0(2.38), p=.04 , Effect size SRM: 0.507 (n=19)
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	MSK: Joint/muscle pain (N)	Significantly higher proportion replacement group reported symptoms than non-replacement group (p=.031)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	MSK: Pain from muscles and joints GHC (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant changes from baseline at both follow-up. Before removal: 6.2 (0.5); 1yr after removal 4.9 (0.5), p=.003 ; 5yrs after removal: 4.2 (0.5), p<0.001. MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 6.1 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 6.1 (0.5), p=.942; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 6.2 (0.5), p=.666 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS)-No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 1.6 (2.0); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 1.8 (1.8); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 2.6 (2.1), p=.292. PROGRESS-PLUS: Amalgam cohort- Women higher overall intensity of 'pain from muscles and joints' (mean 1.8; 95% CI [CI] from 0.4 to 3.4, p=.016). Increase of 10yrs of age associated with lower intensity of 'pain from muscles and joints' (mean 1.3; 95% CI from 0.2 to 2.3; p=.014)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	MSK: Joint complaints Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change over time: Amalgam cohort: 1.75, 0.22, p=.129, 0.28, 95% CI= -0.08, 0.63

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	MSK: Muscle weakness legs Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change over time: Amalgam cohort: 1.00, 0.22, p=.129, 0.28, 95% CI- -0.08, 0.63
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	MSK: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with $p \leq 0.05$ (memory loss and stomach problems) and with $p \leq 0.1$ an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands). Worsening of symptoms: Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms (confusion, stomach problems, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands, coordination problems) were statistically significant when $p \leq 0.05$ and another two (headache, muscle weakness) when $p \leq 0.1$
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, GHC=General Health Complaints, GIC=Glass Ionomer Cement, NA=Not Applicable, M=Mean, MSK=Musculoskeletal, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, yrs=Years			

Table 38: Patient amalgam exposure and neurological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Eyson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam in subjects with complaints relating to mercury toxicity	Neurological: Mean blood mercury level (nmol/L)	19.9 ± 11.8 (range 0-47) nmol/L. Mean values significantly lower than normal threshold value for blood/urine mercury of 50 nmol/L. N amalgams 0-5 (8 people). Mean blood Hg: 23.75 (SD17.10), N amalgams 6-10 (18 people). Mean blood Hg: 16.93 (SD 8.35), N amalgams >10 (19 people). Mean blood Hg: 19.81 (SD13.16). No sig difference blood Hg based on no. amalgams (p=.4641) . PROGRESS-PLUS: Relatively higher blood mercury levels of two patients with MS higher than those without MS (47.00 vs 19.33, p=.0186). Hg levels in blood or urine, or no.amalgams not significant for MS
Eyson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Blood/Urine Hg for individuals with/without MS	Neurological: Blood/urine mercury level and MS	Complaints n=2 vs No complaints n=54. Blood mercury levels of two patients with multiple sclerosis (MS) was higher than those without MS (47.00 vs 19.33, p=.0186) as well as urine levels of those reporting MS (42.00 vs 15.74, p=.0011). PROGRESS-PLUS: After adjusting for age/gender, blood/urine HG not significantly related to MS (OR, 95% CI, p value): Blood: 2.551 (0.076, 85.205) p=.6009 , Urine Hg: 1.309 (0.925, 1.851) 0.1282. Also unrelated to n. amalgams: 1.835 (0.072, 47.003) p=.7137
Tseng 2020a [MS] [Retrospective observational: case-control study] ⁶³	Exposure: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Neurological: OR for amalgam fillings of those with a diagnosis MS	Difference between cases and controls not statistically significant (adjusted OR: 0.823, 95% CI = 0.648–1.046).
Tseng 2020b [ET] Retrospective observational: case-control study ⁶⁴	Exposure: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Neurological: Odds ratio for amalgam fillings of those with a diagnosis ET	No direct relationship between risk of ET and those with AMF (adjusted OR: 0.94, 95% CI = 0.85–1.04).
Eyson 2010 [Retrospective records review] ⁴²	Health (Blood/Urine Hg)	Neurological: Complaints (N)	Complaints n=15 vs No complaints n=41. No sig. difference in blood Hg levels and those experiencing neurological complaints vs those not. Blood=Mean: 17.00 (8.00) vs 21.03 (12.9), p=.3003 ; urinary=Mean: 16.18(9.47) vs 17.33 (12.43), p=.7824
Chen 2020 [Retrospective observational: Case control] ⁶⁵	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Neurological: Parkinson's Disease (Diagnosis)	PD and AMF not directly related (adjusted OR = 1.067, THE CI of 95%: 0.99–1.15). Parkinsons: n=5712 (AMF 2184, non-AMF 3528), Without Parkinsons: n=5712 (AMF 2108, Non-AMF 3604)

Hsu 2016 [Retrospective cohort] ⁶⁶	Exposure: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Neurological: Risk of PD (Incidence and Hazard risk)	Crude numbers of individuals with PD: 126 in amalgam vs 56, in non-amalgam cohort. Overall incidence PD significantly higher in amalgam filling cohort vs non-amalgam filling cohort (2.35 vs. 1.04 per 1000 person-years), with an adjusted HR (aHR) of 1.583 (95% CI = 1.122–2.234, p=.0089). For patients without diabetes, incidence of PD (HR = 1.680, 95% CI = 1.171–2.410, p<.01) significantly higher in amalgam filling cohort vs non-amalgam filling cohort. Similar results found in patients without hypertension, hyperlipidaemia, CVD, follow-up of min. 4 years, and moderate CCI score
Hsu 2016 [Retrospective cohort] ⁶⁶	Exposure: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Neurological: Probability of PD- free survival	Probability PD-free survival in non-amalgam filling cohort higher than amalgam filling cohort from 2002 to 2008 (log-rank test, p<.0001)
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	Neurological: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with $p \leq 0.05$ (memory loss and stomach problems) and with $p \leq 0.1$ an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands). Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms indicated worsening of symptoms (confusion, stomach problems, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands , coordination problems) were statistically significant when $p \leq 0.05$ and another two (headache, muscle weakness) when $p \leq 0.1$. NS difference for paraesthesia
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). AD=Alzheimer's Disease, AMF=Amalgam Filling, CCI=Comorbidity Index, CI=CI, CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, ET=Essential Tremor, HR=Hazard Ratio, MS=Multiple Sclerosis, N=Number, NS=Not Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, PD=Parkinson's Disease, SD=Standard Deviation			

Table 39: Patient amalgam exposure and neuropsychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes (Unit)	Outcome details
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Full scale IQ and surface years of amalgam	NS association between Full scale IQ test change scores and surface years of amalgam [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 434, 0.01, 0.02, 0.48
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Full scale IQ and urinary mercury excretion	NS association between Full scale IQ test change scores and urinary mercury excretion [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 433, 0.46, 0.53, 0.38
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: General Memory Index and surface years of amalgam	NS association between General Memory Index test change scores and surface years of amalgam [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 407, 0.03, 0.03, 0.20
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: General Memory Index and urinary mercury excretion	NS association between General Memory Index test change scores and urinary mercury excretion [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 401, 0.74, 0.55, 0.13
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Visual Motor Composite and surface years of amalgam	NS association between Visual Motor Composite test change scores and surface years of amalgam [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 406, -0.01, 0.03, 0.67
Bellinger 2007 dose effect analysis [RCT] ^{a67}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Visual Motor Composite and urinary mercury excretion	NS association between Visual Motor Composite test change scores and urinary mercury excretion [n, coefficient, standard error, p value] 400, 0.20, 0.65, 0.76
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] [RCT-NECAT] ⁸	Amalgam/Urinary Hg	Neuropsych: Test scores in relation to U-Hg concentrations	Urinary mercury concentration not significantly associated with any of the test scores
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function] ^{a8}	Amalgam vs Composite	Neuropsych: Test scores in relation to surface-years of amalgam (N. amalgam surfaces weighted by n of years present)	Coefficient for surface-years of amalgam was significant for three scores (Picture Memory and Number–Letter Memory of the WRAML and letter fluency). For all three scores, the sign was positive, indicating improvement with increasing exposure to amalgam.
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a68}	Amalgam vs NA [Secondary analysis RCT]	Neuropsych: Executive function: overall summary (WCST, Stroop, verbal fluency, trail making)	Amalgam posterior-occlusal surface-years exposure not associated with scores on executive function tests; all mean change scores were in the direction of improvement (10 surface-years, Letter Fluency $\beta=0.7$, $SE=0.4$, $p=.10$; perseverative errors $\beta= -2.0$, $SE=0.9$, $p=.02$; Trail-Making $\beta=1.0$, $SE=3.0$, $P=.70$; Colour naming $\beta=0.05$, $SE=0.6$, $p=.9$)
Mikhailichenko 2019 [Retrospective observational] ⁶⁹	Exposure: amalgam	Neuropsych: Correlation no.amalgams with dementia development	NS correlation between dementia development and no.amalgams: aOR values= 0.980 and 1.019 for subjects<3 fillings & >4 fillings, respectively

Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Semantic memory, mean Z score ± SD	Amalgam 0.06 ± 0.7 Control; 0.10 ± 0.7. No significant differences found between two groups on any cognitive variables (Wilks' lambda = 0.99, F _{3,679} = 2.40, p = .07 , partial eta-squared = 0.01, power = 0.69). PROGRESS-PLUS: NS by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Semantic memory, mean Z score ± SD	Both groups changed over time, both groups showed pattern of decline in cognitive performance over time, but consistent with finding that interaction was not significant, no significant differences in the slope of change observed - Amalgam Group (n = 81) Control Individuals (n = 81) Amalgam group- Time 1: 0.25 ± 0.7, Time 2: 0.21 ± 0.7; Control group- Time 1: 0.18 ± 0.7; Time 2: 0.15 ± 0.7. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: NS by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Episodic memory, mean Z score ± SD	Amalgam 0.10 ± 0.6; Control 0.10 ± 0.6. No significant differences between two groups on any cognitive variables (Wilks' lambda = 0.99, F _{3,679} = 2.40, p = .07 , partial eta-squared = 0.01, power = 0.69). PROGRESS-PLUS: N.S .by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Episodic memory, mean Z score ± SD	Both groups showed decline in cognitive performance over time, but consistent with finding that interaction was not significant, no significant differences in the slope of change observed - Amalgam Group (n = 81) Control Individuals (n = 81). Amalgam group- Time 1: 0.24 ± 0.6; Time 2: 0.22 ± 0.6; Control group- Time 1: 0.24 ± 0.5; Time 2: 0.25 ± 0.6. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: NS by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Visuo-spatial ability, mean Z score ± SD	Amalgam 0.15 ± 0.9 Control 0.02 ± 0.9. No significant differences found between two groups on any cognitive variables (Wilks' lambda = 0.99, F _{3,679} = 2.40, p = .07 , partial eta-squared = 0.01, power = 0.69). PROGRESS-PLUS: NS by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Visuo-spatial ability, mean Z score ± SD	Both groups showed decline in cognitive performance over time, but consistent with finding that interaction not significant, no significant differences in slope of change were observed - Amalgam Group (n = 81) vs Control Individuals (n = 81). Amalgam group- Time 1: 0.31 ± 0.8; Time 2: 0.19 ± 0.8; Control individuals- Time 1: 0.22 ± 0.8; Time 2: -0.05 ± 0.9. PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: NS by gender
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Neuropsych: Neuropsychological self-reported symptoms, N (%)	Amalgam vs control SS - 238 (69.6) vs 175 (51.2) p < 0.001
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Neuropsych: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - <i>NS Stomach ache</i> - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', 'skin reactions', 'frequent toilet urge', ' memory disturbance ', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more

			often, while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aNew England Amalgam Trial. N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SS=Symptom Score or Statistically Significant, WCST=Wisconsin Card Sorting Test, U-Hg=Urinary Mercury, WRAML=Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning			

Table 40: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and neuropsychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metaloceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Neuropsych: GHC index	Analyses of changes in complaint intensity from pre-treatment to 5yr follow-up: six items significantly reduced: increased salivation, pain from muscles and joints, gastrointestinal symptoms, fatigue, memory problems, and difficulty concentrating. No items significantly increased vs pre-treatment value
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Memory problems GHC questionnaire (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 3.8 (0.5); 1yr after removal: 2.6 (0.5), p=.005 ; 5yrs after removal: 2.2 (0.5), p=.001). MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: - Baseline (Q1): 2.8 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 3.1 (0.5), p=.556 ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 3.3 (0.5), p=.346 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1-t follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.3 (0.7); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.1 (0.3), p=.333
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Memory disorders Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 1.22, 0.06, p=.645 , 0.08, 95% CI= -0.27, 0.43
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Neuropsych: Intensity of memory complaints [m] (pretreatment)	Statistically higher scores at 3yr follow-up for treatment group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Neuropsych: Intensity of memory problems complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:3.5(2.41) vs 2.4(2.43) p=.101 , SRM: 0.397

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Difficult to concentrate (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 4.5 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 2.8 (0.4), p<0.001; 5yrs after removal: 2.6 (0.5), p=.001. MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 3.6 (0.5); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 3.2 (0.5), p=.295; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 4.0 (0.5), p=.353. Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.1 (0.3); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.3 (0.5); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.3 (0.4), p=.457
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Lack of concentration (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 1.50, 0.34, p=.039 , 0.38, 95% CI=0.02, 0.74
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Neuropsych: Intensity of complaints for difficulty in concentrating [m] (pretreatment)	Pretreatment: Intensity of complaints for difficulty in concentrating in treatment group vs external reference group: - 3.6 (n =19) vs 1.6 (n=441) Statistically higher scores at 3yr follow-up for treatment group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Neuropsych: Intensity of concentration complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:3.6(2.48) vs 2.5(2.34) p=.078, SRM: 0.465
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Reaction slowed down (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.47, -0.03, p=.786, -0.05, 95% CI= -0.40, 0.30
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Neuropsych: Symptom reduction at 1yr (Q2) and 5yr (Q3) after removal compared to before removal (Q1) (mean intensity)	Amalgam cohort: mean intensity of each of all 23 items reduced at first follow-up (Q2) vs baseline; 14 symptoms significantly reduced . Largest reductions (ES about 0.6) observed for intraoral pain/tenderness, taste disturbance, cardiovascular complaints, difficulty concentrating , and anxiety/depression. At second follow-up (Q3), reduction in mean intensity observed for all but one item vs baseline (Q1)
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	Neuropsych: OR self-reported symptom improvement	For all 14 symptoms, OR for symptom improvement for treatment group demonstrate greater odds of symptom improvement vs positive amalgam group. Two of these odds ratios are significant with p ≤ 0.05 (memory loss and stomach problems) and with p ≤ 0.1 an additional 4 symptoms were significant (fatigue/sleep disturbance, confusion , loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands). Symptom worsening: Removal of fillings reduced odds symptoms would worsen for all 14 symptoms. Odds ratios for five symptoms (confusion, stomach problems, loss of sense of smell or taste, shakiness in hands, coordination problems) were statistically significant when p ≤ 0.05 and another two (headache, muscle weakness) when p ≤ 0.1 . NS difference unintentionally dropping things

Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, ES=Effect Size, GHC=General Health Complaints, MCDI=MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventory, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Non-Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, SS=Symptom Score, yr=Year

Table 41: Patient amalgam exposure and oral health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Ahlgren 2014 [Cross-sectional with control] ^{9, 70}	Exposure: Amalgam/Hg allergy in OLL vs DP patients	Oral health: OLL diagnosis (N)	OLL patients: 71/74 OLL had amalgam adjacent to lichen lesions. Mean surfaces amalgam: 18.5 (range, 0–45) DP group: Mean surfaces amalgam 13.6 (range, 0–43; t test: p=.011). Mean no. amalgam surfaces higher in mercury allergic patients, 27.9 vs 17.3 (t test: p=.036)
Daume 2021 [Cross-sectional with control] ⁷⁰	Exposure: Amalgam	Oral health: Thornhill grading: grading of strength of association between mucosal lesions and amalgam/metal (correlation coefficient and p value)	Analysing relationship between gender, clinical form of OLP, age, and presentation form, NS differences between the four gradings of Thornhill (Thornhill Amalgam (-0.03 p=.82); Thornhill Metal (0.05 p=.16)) (Thus, grading did not differ between presentation forms or clinical form of OLP). Amalgam NS associated with lichen presentation form (correlation coefficient: 0.02, p=.79)
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Amalgam vs No amalgam	Oral health: Blood/urinary Hg and Oral cavity complaints	Complaints n=27 vs No Complaints n=29. Significant difference Blood Hg/Oral complaints. Relatively higher blood mercury levels found in subjects with presenting complaints in oral cavity vs those who did not (Mean: 23.65 (12.21) vs 16.33 (10.43), p=.0320). Urinary Hg levels did not differ significantly between those with vs without complaints (Mean: 17.21 (11.29) vs 16.86 (12.14), p=.9254). PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: After adjusting for age/gender, blood Hg positive significant factor for patients presenting with oral complaint (OR = 1.074, 95% CI = 1.005-1.149, p=.0362). Urinary=NS (Adjusted OR 1.01, CI= 0.953, 1.069, P95% p=.7451). Unrelated to n.amalgams: (Adjusted or 0.501, 95% CI 0.122, 2.055, p=.3372). Age/gender does not affect Hg as significant factor
Ma 2021 [Retrospective observational: nested case-control] ⁷¹	Exposure: Amalgam individuals with OLP	Oral health: OR developing OLP for times receiving amalgam fillings (95% CI, P-value)	Amalgam restorations not associated with altered odds of OLP. Among all included restorations categorized by restorative materials and total exposure, as measured by the number of received restorations, the aORs of developing OLP were 0.975 (95% CI =0.718–1.325, p=.8732), 1.011 (95% CI = 0.546–1.872, p=.9722), and 0.565 (95% CI = 0.215–1.481, p=.2456) in those who received amalgam fillings for 1–2, 3–4, and over 5 times/yr throughout study period, respectively, with a mean aOR of 0.948 (95% CI =0.853–1.053, p=.3170) per each additional amalgam restoration.
Ptak 2023 [Retrospective cohort] ¹¹	Exposure: Amalgam vs Composite	Oral health: Occurrence of pulpal disease, N (%)	Association pulpal disease: Amalgam: 65 (10.35%), p>.05 . PROGRESS-Plus: Not statistically significant difference in risk of developing pulpal disease based on patient sex. Male 108 (4.96) .05 Female 83 (3.81) .05. Statistically significant association between age and the occurrence of pulpal disease(p=.0001) . At time of treatment, mean age was 54 6 17.10 years. For each additional year of age, risk of pulpal disease increased by approximately 1.02%

Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Exposure to amalgam	Oral health: Frequency of patients with OLL	One atopic patient presented a lichenoid lesion on the inner surface of the cheek related to an amalgam restoration. The clinical diagnosis was confirmed by a biopsy, which showed a typical histological features of lichenoid reaction and by a positive reaction to ammoniated mercury (+++) and amalgam (++) in the patch test
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Oral health: Documentation of symptoms and complaints (Individual 16 symptoms)	Tiredness, loss of energy - SS Headache - SS Sweating - NS Joint complaints - SS Skin reactions - NS Dizziness - SS Frequent toilet urge - NS Stomach ache - SS Memory disturbance - NS Mouth dryness - SS Shortness of breath - NS Weak muscles, legs - SS Fluttering heart - SS Metallic taste - SS Vomiting - SS Appetite loss - SS With respect to the symptoms 'sweating', 'skin reactions', 'frequent toilet urge', 'memory disturbance', and 'shortness of breath', there was no statistically significant difference between either group in prevalence adjusted for age, sex, and education. Patients of the amalgam group reported 'metallic taste' significantly more often , while all other complaints showed markedly higher prevalence in the other patient group
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aOR=Adjusted Odds Ratio, CI=CI, DP=Dermatitis Patients, Hg=Mercury, N=Number, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus, N=Number, NS=Not Significant, OR=Odds Ratio, SS=Statistically Significant			

Table 42: Patient amalgam removal/restoration and oral health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 [Prospective clinical observational] ⁴⁶	Amalgam removed, replacement with composite (OLL) vs Min. 1 amalgam (no OLL)	Oral health: Mucosal lesions (oral lichenoid lesions)	Observed OLLs near AAg restorations in all instances. In 2 cases (28.6%) lesions in direct contact. In all other cases (71.4%) only adjacent, not in direct contact with restorations
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 [Prospective clinical observational] ⁴⁶	Amalgam removed, replacement with composite (OLL) vs Min. 1 amalgam (no OLL)	Oral health: Improvement in Mucosal lesions (oral lichenoid lesions)	All cases mucosal lesions reported: amalgams replaced with composite restorations. Improvements observed 3mths after replacing amalgams with amelioration of lesions in 5 (71.4%) patients. At 6mths, all lesions disappeared in 1 case although white residual papules persisted in all other cases.a
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷	Partial/complete replacement of amalgams vs No removal/replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLL upon amalgam removal - complete resolution, N (%)	Positive patch test result: 8/10 (80%) patients partial/complete replacement of amalgams. Complete resolution in 6 (75%) of these patients. Negative patch test result: 6/21 (29%) had amalgams replaced. 1 (5%) of these patients had complete resolution of OLL. 14 patients no amalgams replaced: 1 OLL completely resolved.

Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷	Partial/complete replacement of amalgams vs No removal/replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLL upon amalgam removal - partial resolution, N (%)	Positive patch test result group: 8/10 (80%) patients partial/complete replacement of amalgams. 2 (25%) patients' partial resolution after amalgam replacement. Negative patch test result: 6/21 (29%) amalgams replaced. 3 patients' partial resolution (50%). 14 (66%) patients no amalgams replaced, 1(7%) partial resolution of OLL
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁷	Partial/complete replacement of amalgams vs No removal/replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLL upon amalgam removal - unchanged, N (%)	Negative patch test result group: 6 (29%) amalgams replaced. 2 patients unchanged. 14 patients no amalgams replaced: OLL remain unchanged in 7 (50%)
Marell 2014 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁸	Replacement/partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars vs No replacement among individuals with OLP/OLR	Oral health: Regression of lichenoid lesions (LCR group)	Seven LCR patients with positive reactions to mercury: all lesions regressed after total replacement of amalgams. Lesion remission more frequent among patients with total replacement vs partial replacement or no replacement, although difference not significant (p=.186) . Not possible to determine whether replacement material had significant impact on lesion remission. (No exchange: Healed=3, Not healed=1; Partial exchange: Healed=7, not healed=6; Total exchange: Healed=12, Not healed=2). At follow-up patients reduced average number of amalgam surfaces from 29.7 to 9.7 (-20.0 surfaces)
Marell 2014 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ⁴⁸	Replacement/partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars vs No replacement among individuals with OLP/OLR	Oral health: Regression of lichenoid lesions (OLP group)	5/6 patients showed reaction to Hg. No remissions of lesions after removal dental amalgam. 1 patient complete remission of oral lesions and this patient only one not replaced any dental material. Remaining 12 patients (92%) undergone partial/total replacement and still had oral lesion (No exchange: Healed=1, Not healed=0; Partial exchange: Healed=0, Not healed=3; Total exchange: Healed=0, Not healed=9) At follow-up patients reduced average number of amalgam surfaces from 27.5 to 3.4 (-24.1 surfaces)
Montebugnoli 2012 [CBA] ⁷²	Replacement amalgam with composite in individuals with OLL/OLP vs NA	Oral health: Clinical healing, N (%); OR, 95% CI	After amalgam replacement, total regression of lesions observed in 14 (22%) patients within 3 months from amalgam removal. Significant difference (X2 4.7; p=.02) obtained considering 2 groups of patients. 9 patients (36%) healed OLL group vs 5 (13%) in OLP group (OR 3.8; 95% CI 1.1-13.6)

Montebugnoli 2012 [CBA] ⁷²	Replacement amalgam with composite in individuals with OLL/OLP vs NA	Oral health: Histologic healing, N (%); OR, 95% CI	All histologic criteria related to lichenoid reaction remained unchanged in 5 patients in clinically unchanged (control group) patients. Clinically healed patients (n=14): complete disappearance of all histologic criteria related to lichenoid reaction in 7 patients (50%). No significant difference between percentage of patients histologically healed in OLL group: 5 (20%) vs OLP group: 2 (5%)
Montebugnoli 2012 [CBA] ⁷²	Replacement amalgam with composite in individuals with OLL/OLP vs NA	Oral health: Clinical healing in relation to positive patch test- N (%)	Significant relationship (X2 6.3; p=.01) between clinical healing and positivity to patch test (OR 5.2; CI 1.4-19.6): 7/15 patch test–positive patients (47%) clinically healed vs 7/49 patch test–negative patients (14%). OLL patients: difference remained significant (2 7.7; p=.01): 5 patients (83%) of 6 who patch test positive healed vs 4 patients (21%) of 19 who patch test negative (OR 18.7; CI 1.5-239.5). OLP patients: difference did not reach significance: 2 patients (22%) of 9 who patch test positive healed vs 3 patients (10%) of 30 who patch test negative. Considering the combination of positive patch test and strict contact with amalgams (OLL patients), 5 patients (83%) of 6 with positive patch test and lesions in strict contact with amalgams healed, vs 9 (15%) of 58 of remaining population (2 11.7; p=.01 ; OR 27.2; CI 2.7-273.3).
Montebugnoli 2012 [CBA] ⁷²	Replacement amalgam with composite in individuals with OLL/OLP vs NA	Oral health: Histologic healing in relation to positive patch test- N (%)	Significant relationship among clinically healed patients between histologic healing and positivity to patch test. 6/7 histologically healed patients patch test positive vs 1 positive among 7 histologically unchanged cases (Fisher’s exact test p< .02). Combination positive patch test and strict contact with amalgams, 4 patients (66%) of 6 with positive patch test and lesions in strict contact with amalgams (OLL group) healed vs 3 (5%) of 58 of remaining population (Fisher’s exact test p=.01)
Montebugnoli 2012 [CBA] ⁷²	Replacement amalgam with composite in individuals with OLL/OLP vs NA	Oral health: Histologic healing in relation to proximity to filling, N (%)	Among clinically healed patients: no significant relationship between histologic healing and physical association between fillings and mucosal lesions. 5/7 histologically healed patient’s vs 4/7 histologically unchanged cases had strong physical association between fillings and mucosal lesions, and 2 histologically healed patients vs 3/7 histologically had weak physical association between fillings and mucosal lesions. No significant difference between 20% of patients histologically healed in first group (5/25) vs second group (5%, 2/39). Considering combination of positive patch test and strict contact with amalgams, 4/6 patients (66%) with positive patch test and lesions in strict contact with amalgams healed vs 3/58 (5%) of remaining population (Fisher’s exact test p=.01)
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	Oral health: Overall summary (N)	NS difference oral symptoms between replacement and non-replacement groups. Metallic taste and increased salivation more common among men than women (p <.05). Bleeding gums more common in youngest age group and dry mouth more common in oldest age group (p<.05)

Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 [Retrospective cohort] ⁴⁹	Amalgam restoration replacement for individuals with OLR. Complete replacement of all amalgam fillings with fillings based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these vs Healthy controls no OLR	Oral health: Healing of OLR- N (%)	Complete replacement of amalgam fillings (n=20). Complete healing (no lesions remaining): n=16 (80%); Marked improvement (> 80% improvement): n=3 (15%); no improvement: n=1 (5%). Complete healing was significantly the major outcome ($\chi^2= 16.94, p<0.001$). Patients with a positive patch test reaction to amalgam showed complete healing
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control] ⁵¹	Amalgam replaced other materials vs No replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLR N (%) - Complete	Patch test positive to amalgam-related allergen: Amalgam replaced (Total Amalgam replaced n=26, Total no amalgam replaced n=15): 5 (19.2); No amalgam replaced (Total Amalgam replaced n=6, no amalgam replaced n=36): 2 (13.3). Patch test negative to amalgam-related: Amalgam replaced 0; No amalgam replaced 0
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control] ⁵¹	Amalgam replaced other materials vs No replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLR N (%) - partial	Patch test positive to amalgam-related allergen: Amalgam replaced 16 (61.5); No amalgam replaced 1 (6.7). Patch test negative to amalgam-related: Amalgam replaced 2 (40.0); No amalgam replaced 10 (27.8). Note: (Positive patch test amalgam: Total Amalgam replaced n=26, Total no amalgam replaced n=15, Neg. patch test: Amalgam replaced n=26, no amalgam replaced n=15)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control] ⁵¹	Amalgam replaced other materials vs No replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLR N (%) - No change	Patch test positive to amalgam-related allergen: Amalgam replaced 5 (19.2); No amalgam replaced 11 (73.3). Patch test negative to amalgam-related: Amalgam replaced 3(60.0); No amalgam replaced 26 (72.2) Note: (Positive patch test amalgam: Total Amalgam replaced n=26, Total no amalgam replaced n=15, Neg. patch test: Amalgam replaced n=26, no amalgam replaced n=15)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control] ⁵¹	Amalgam replaced other materials vs No replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLR N (%) -Excised	Patch test positive to amalgam-related allergen: Amalgam replaced 0; No amalgam replaced 1 Patch test negative to amalgam-related: Amalgam replaced 1; No amalgam replaced 0 Note: (Pos patch test amalgam: Total Amalgam replaced n=26, Total no amalgam replaced n=15, Neg. patch test: Amalgam replaced n=26, no amalgam replaced n=15)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control] ⁵¹	Amalgam replaced other materials vs No replacement	Oral health: Resolution of OLR N (%) - Total	Patch test positive to amalgam-related allergen: Amalgam replaced 21 (80.8); No amalgam replaced 3 (20.0) p <0.001b , Patch test negative to amalgam-related: Amalgam replaced 2 (33.3); No amalgam replaced 10(26.3) p= - 0.62b Note: (Pos patch test amalgam: Total Amalgam replaced n=26, Total no amalgam replaced n=15, Neg. patch test: Amalgam replaced n=26, no amalgam replaced n=15)
aNo statistical test for significance conducted, bMean change: Baseline minus follow-up value; A positive value indicates reduction of symptoms P-value: 2-tailed significance from paired sample t-test SRM: Standardized response mean (mean difference divided with the standard deviation of mean difference). c(Suter): Fisher's exact test to compare resolution and no change between the groups with and without amalgam replacement, excised cases excluded. AAg=Silver Amalgam, CI=Confidence Interval, LCR=Lichenoid Contact Reaction, N=Number, NS=Not Significant, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus, OLR=Oral Lichenoid Reaction, OR=Odds Ratio			

Table 43: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and orofacial symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metallo ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Oral health: GHC index	No significant changes of index scores for local (intraoral and extraoral) health complaints over time (symptoms included intra oral burning sensation intraoral pain/tenderness, taste disturbances, intraoral stiffness/paraesthesia, dry mouth salivation, facial burning sensation, facial pain/tenderness, facial stiffness/paraesthesia, facial skin problems, pain from temporomandibular joints). Analyses of changes in complaint intensity from pre-treatment to 5yr follow-up: six items significantly reduced: increased salivation, pain from muscles and joints, gastrointestinal symptoms, fatigue, memory problems, and difficulty concentrating. No items significantly increased vs pre-treatment value
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Health (removal of amalgam)	Orofacial: Orofacial burning sensation (mean intensity score GHC questionnaire (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups. Before removal: 1.1 (0.2); 1yr after removal: 0.6 (0.2), p=.139; 5yrs after removal: 0.4 (0.3), p=.062. Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.1 (0.3); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.2); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.0 (0.0), p=.667
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of intraoral burning sensation complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 0.5 (0.91) vs 0.7 (1.72) p=.586 , SRM: -0.127
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of extraoral facial burning sensation from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 1.2(2.19) vs 0.9 (1.94) p=.685 , SRM: 0.094
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Health (removal of amalgam)	Orofacial: Orofacial pain/tenderness (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal:1.5 (0.3) ; 1yr after removal: 1.0 (0.3), p=.194 ; 5yrs after removal: 0.3 (0.3), p=.013. Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.2 (0.6); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.1 (0.3), p=.333

Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of complaints for facial pain/tenderness [m] (pretreatment)	Statistically higher scores at 3yr follow-up for treatment group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of intra-oral pain/tenderness from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:1.4(1.91) vs 1.2 (1.83) p=. 654, SRM: 0.105
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of facial pain/tenderness from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, sd, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 1.4(2.75) vs 1.2 (1.83) p=. 457, SRM: 0.174
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Health (removal of amalgam)	Orofacial: Orofacial stiffness/paraesthesia (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 1.5 (0.3); 1yr after removal: 0.7 (0.3), p=. 035; 5yrs after removal: 0.6 (0.3), p=. 034. Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.2 (0.3) ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.0 (0.0), p=. 111
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of intra-oral stiffness/paraesthesia complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, sd, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 0.6(1.12) vs 0.6(1.64) p=. 905, SRM: -0.028
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of facial stiffness/ paresthesia from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, sd, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 0.7(1.7) vs 0.5 (1.17) p=. 429, SRM: 0.186

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Health (removal of amalgam)	Orofacial: Orofacial skin problems (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-up. Before removal: 2.2 (0.4) ; 1yr after removal: 1.7 (0.4), p=.323 ; 5yrs after removal: 1.0 (0.4), p=.039 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 1.0 (1.4); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 1.2 (2.1); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.3 (0.9), p=.057
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of facial skin problems from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 1.4(2.22) vs 1.0 (1.87) p=.306 , SRM: 0.242
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Health (removal of amalgam)	Orofacial: Pain from temporomandibular joints (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant changes from baseline at first, not second follow-up: Before removal: 2.2 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 1.3 (0.4), p=.067 ; 5yrs after removal: 2.2 (0.5), p=.874 Healthy cohort (no MUPS)- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.3 (0.9) ; 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.4 (0.7); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.3 (0.8), p=.898 . PROGRESS-PLUS: Amalgam cohort: Increase 10yrs age associated with lower 'pain from temporomandibular joints' (1.3; 95% CI from 0.4 to 2.2; p=.005)
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of pain from temporomandibular joints [m] (pretreatment)	Statistically higher scores at 3yr follow-up for treatment group
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of pain from temporomandibular joints treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 2.4(2.90) vs 1.08(2.46) p=.538 , SRM: 0.144
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of taste disturbance complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	Statistically significant reduction from pre-treatment vs 3yr follow-up (paired sample t-test): Mean (SD):0.8(1.39) vs 0.2 (0.38), p=.05 , Effect size SRM:0.483 (n=19)

Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of dry mouth complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 1.6(2.14) vs 1.6 (12.43) p=. 9916 , SRM: 0.025
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Orofacial: Intensity of increased salivation complaints from pre-treatment to 3yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 1.6(1.98) vs 0.7 (1.86) p=. 064 , SRM: 0.452
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints related to changes in mercury concentration in serum and orofacial complaints	Secondary explorative analyses of correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in health complaints 3yrs after treatment showed positive but not significant correlations . Pearson correlation coefficients were 0.Æ320, 0.Æ193 and 0.Æ127 for correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in intra-oral, extra-oral and general indices, respectively. Corresponding P-values were 0.Æ182, 0.Æ428 and 0.Æ604 (n = 19), leaving no statistically significant support for mercury as a cause of the complaints
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Adverse events: complaints	Seven participants in the treatment group experienced increased health complaints in connection with removal of amalgam fillings. Laboratory tests of blood samples collected within a few days after the treatment session showed values within reference intervals. Health complaints reported in connection with amalgam removal were gastric pain, pain in joints and muscles, oral ulcers, sore throat, pain in legs, hands and feet, dizziness, tachycardia, nausea, diarrhoea, depression, fatigue, chills, burning sensations in the face , cold hands, increased blood pressure and submandibular lymphadenopathy . The increase in complaints was transient and disappeared within a week or two

Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Comparisons of changes in health complaints in the treatment group and reference group	Per-protocol comparisons of changes in health complaints, from Questionnaire 1 to the 3-yr follow-up in the treatment group and Questionnaire 3 in reference group, showed that changes in mean index scores for intra-oral complaints significantly different in the two groups, changes in extra-oral health complaints not significantly different. Adjusting for gender, age and complaint intensity reported in Questionnaire 1: changes in intra-oral complaints remained significantly different, changes in extra-oral health complaints remained not significantly different. ITT comparisons similar to per-protocol analyses. Results from analyses based on data from reference group after post hoc application of exclusion criteria showed no major differences compared with analyses using all 13 participants from initial reference group. Unadjusted per-protocol differences in changes in index scores between treatment group and reference group after application of exclusion criteria were 8Æ3 (95% CI: 1Æ2 to 15Æ3, p=0Æ024), 3Æ6 (95% CI:)3Æ7 to 10Æ7, p=0Æ320) for the intra-oral and extra-oral indices, respectively
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with group] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints in treatment group	In the treatment group, significant reductions in mean index scores for intra-oral complaints from Questionnaire 1 to the 3yr follow-up. Reduction mean index scores for extra-oral health complaints in this period was not significant. ITT analyses similar results as per-protocol analysis. In repeated measures analysis, data from pre-treatment examination and all follow-ups included. Per-protocol repeated measures analysis showed significant overall effects of time for all three index scores
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints in reference group	Reference group: slight not statistically significant increase in mean index scores for intra-oral and extra-oral complaints from Questionnaire 1 to Questionnaire 3. ITT analysis: no significant changes in mean index scores from Questionnaire 1 to Questionnaire 3. Data from Questionnaire 2 included in repeated measures analysis

Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Comparisons of changes in health complaints in treatment group and reference group	Per-protocol comparisons of changes in health complaints, from Questionnaire 1 to 3-yr follow-up in the treatment group and Questionnaire 3 in reference group, showed changes in mean index scores for intra-oral and general health complaints significantly different in two groups. Changes in extra-oral health complaints not significantly different. After adjusting gender, age and complaint intensity reported in Questionnaire 1, changes in intra-oral complaints remained significantly different, and changes in extra-oral health complaints remained not significantly different. Results from ITT comparisons similar to results from per-protocol analyses. Results from analyses based on data from reference group after post hoc application of exclusion criteria showed no major differences vs analyses using all 13 participants from initial reference group. Unadjusted per-protocol differences in changes in index scores between treatment group and reference group after application of exclusion criteria were 8.8 (95% CI: 1.2 to 15.4, p=0.024), 3.6 (95% CI: -3.7 to 10.7, p=0.320) for intra-oral and extra-oral respectively
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints related to changes in mercury concentration in serum and orofacial complaints	Secondary explorative analyses of correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in health complaints 3yrs after treatment showed positive but not significant correlations. Pearson correlation coefficients were 0.320, 0.193 and 0.127 for correlations between reduction in mercury in serum and reduction in intra-oral, extra-oral and general indices, respectively. Corresponding P-values were 0.182, 0.428 and 0.604 (n = 19), leaving no statistically significant support for mercury as a cause of the complaints
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints in treatment group	Treatment group: significant reductions mean index scores for intra-oral complaints from Questionnaire 1 to 3yr follow-up. Reduction in mean index scores for extra-oral health complaints in this period not significant. Intention-to-treat analysis showed similar results as per-protocol analysis. In repeated measures analysis, data from pre-treatment examination and all follow-ups included. Per-protocol repeated measures analysis showed significant overall effects of time for all three index scores
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a-comparison] ⁴¹	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Orofacial: Changes in health complaints in reference group	Reference group: NS increase in mean index scores for intra-oral & extra-oral general health complaints from Questionnaire 1 to Questionnaire 3. ITT analysis showed no significant changes in mean index scores from Questionnaire 1 to Questionnaire 3. Data from Questionnaire 2 included in repeated measures analysis. Per-protocol analysis changes in mean index scores over time showed significant overall effect of time for general health complaints

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Intraoral burning sensation GHC (mean intensity scores (SE), est. of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (before removal): 1.7 (0.3); First follow-up (1yr after removal): 0.6 (0.3), p=.003 ; Second follow-up (5yrs after removal): 0.3 (0.3). p=.002 Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.2 (0.6); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2):0.4 (1.4), p=.778
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Intraoral pain/tenderness (mean intensity scores (SE), est. of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (before removal): 2.5 (0.3); First follow-up (1yr after removal): 0.8 (0.3), p<0.001 ; 5yrs after removal: 0.5 (0.3), p<0.001 Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.2); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2):0.0 (0.0), p= 1.000
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Symptom reduction at 1yr (Q2) and 5yr (Q3) after removal compared to before removal (Q1) (mean intensity)	Amalgam cohort: mean intensity of each of all 23 items reduced at first follow-up (Q2)vs baseline; 14 symptoms significantly reduced. Largest reductions (ES about 0.6) observed for intraoral pain/tenderness, taste disturbance , cardiovascular complaints, difficulty concentrating, and anxiety/depression. At second follow-up (Q3), reduction in mean intensity observed for all but one item vs baseline (Q1)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Reduction of symptoms over time	Amalgam cohort: Highest ESs (estimated by SRM) found for ‘ metallic taste ’ (0.93), ‘stress at the job’ (0.83), ‘skin rash’ (0.57), ‘sensitivity to cold and wind’ (0.54), ‘worries – restlessness’ (0.53), and ‘irritability’ (0.52); and significant reduction of intensity of symptoms was shown Moderate ESs (around 0.4) were found for items ‘feeling of walking next to oneself’, ‘arrythmia’, ‘diarrhoea’, ‘increased urge to toilet’, ‘indecision’, ‘abdominal pain’, ‘lack of concentration’, ‘fluctuating mood’, ‘anxiety’, and ‘ burning sensation in tongue ’, all being statistically significant
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Taste disturbances (mean intensity scores (SE), est. of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 1.6 (0.2); 1yr after removal: 0.5 (0.2) p<0.001 ; 5yrs later removal: 0.4 (0.2), p=.001 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.0); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.3); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.0 (0.0), p=.333
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Intraoral stiffness/paraesthesia (mean intensity score (SE), est. of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups. Before removal:1.1 (0.2); 1yr after removal: 0.6 (0.2), p=.148 ; 5yrs after removal: 0.5 (0.2), p=.104 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS)- No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.0 (0.1); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.2 (0.6); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.0 (0.1), p=.667
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Dry mouth (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 2.8 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 1.8 (0.4), p=.046 ; 5yrs after removal: 1.5 (0.40), p=.019 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.3 (0.6); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.2); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.5 (0.9), p=.099
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Increased salivation/mucus (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Before removal: 1.7 (0.4); 1yr after removal:1.3 (0.4), p=.289 ; 5yr after removal: 1.8 (0.4), p=.812 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.1 (0.3); 1-st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.1 (0.3); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.2 (0.6), p=.889

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Bleeding of the gums (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.78, 0.13, p=.255 , 0.21, 95% CI= -0.15, 0.55
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Grinding one's teeth (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort- 0.59, 0.13, p=.255 , 0.21, 95% CI= -0.15 0.55
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Loosening of teeth (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.09, 0.06, p=.423 , 0.14, 95% CI= -0.21, 0.49
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Burning sensations tongue (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.56, 0.28, p=.048 , 0.36, 95% CI=0.00, 0.72
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Dry mouth (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.91, 0.16, p=.344 , 0.17, 95% CI= -0.18, 0.52
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Oral health: Metallic taste (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant change from baseline: Amalgam cohort: 0.91, 0.88, p<0.001 , 0.93, 95%CI=0.51, 1.34
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ^{b50}	Amalgam removal+Replacement with other materials (e.g. (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns) vs No intervention	Oral health: Adverse events: complaints	Seven participants in the treatment group experienced increased health complaints in connection with removal of amalgam fillings. Laboratory tests of blood samples collected within a few days after the treatment session showed values within reference intervals. Health complaints reported in connection with amalgam removal were gastric pain, pain in joints and muscles, oral ulcers , sore throat, pain in legs, hands and feet, dizziness, tachycardia, nausea, diarrhoea, depression, fatigue, chills, burning sensations in the face, cold hands, increased blood pressure and submandibular lymphadenopathy. The increase in complaints was transient and disappeared within a week or two
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, GHC=General Health Complaints, ITT=Intention to Treat, M=Mean, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Not Significant, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, SS=Statistically Significant, yr=Year			

Table 44: Patient amalgam exposure and psychosocial symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Total problem behaviours	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.3(2.1). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.7 (0.6) p=.20 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.4(1.0) p=.15
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Externalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 1.7(2.0). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.3 (0.5) p=.52 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.9(0.9) p=.34
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Withdrawn	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -1.4(1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.3 (0.3) p=.34 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.5(0.5) p=.33
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Delinquent behaviours	Statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.7(1.3). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.7 (0.3) p=.06 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.4(0.6) p=.02
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Aggression	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.7(1.1). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.3 (0.3) p=.38 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.5(0.5) p=.30
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Exposure Hg: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Psychological: Anxiety/Depression (N complaints)	Complaints n=6 vs no complaints n=50. No sig. difference in blood/urine Hg levels and those experiencing anxiety/depression complaints vs those not. Blood=Mean: 13.08(5.85) vs 20.64 (12.16), p=.2243 ; urinary=Mean: 10.67(6.03) vs 17.53 (11.84), p=.3307
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 45.8(1.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.6 (0.4) p=.16 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.2(0.8) p=.13

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety Change Score	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -5.4(2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.3 (0.7) p=.64 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(1.1) p=.70
Sundstrom 2011 [[Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Psychological: Anxiety, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 89 (26.4%) vs 59 (17.5%) p=.005
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁴²	Exposure Hg: Amalgam vs No amalgam	Psychological: Depression (N complaints)	Complaints n=6 vs No complaints n=50. No sig. difference in blood/urine Hg levels and those experiencing depression vs those not. Blood=Mean: 13.80 (5.85) vs 20.64 (12.16), p=.2243, urinary=Mean: 10.67(6.03) vs 17.53 (11.84), p =.3307
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial ⁷³ al [Secondary analysis RCT] ^a	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 50.8(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.4) p=.34 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.5(0.7) p=.49
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Psychological: Depression prevalence, N (%)	Significant difference between groups: Health complaints attributed amalgam vs control- Depression symptoms: 219 (65.0%) vs 164 (48.7%). No depression symptoms: 118 (35.0%) vs 173 (51.3%). N=337/Group
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Psychological: Depression, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 64 (19.0%) vs 36 (10.7%) p=.002
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Emotional symptoms index	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8yr or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 47.8(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1 (0.4) p=.72 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.5(0.7) p=.49

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Clinical maladjustment	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 47.5(1.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1 (0.4) p=.87 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(0.8) p=.58
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Personal adjustment	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 49.2(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.4) p=.31 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.7(0.7) p=.35
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Emotional symptoms index	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -5.1(2.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1 (0.6) p=.90 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.2(1.0) p=.85
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Clinical maladjustment	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -4.1(2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.3 (0.7) p=.63 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.6(1.1) p=.61
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Personal adjustment	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -1.6(2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): 1.2 (0.7) p=.09 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 2.1(1.1) p=.07
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression Change Score	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -2.9(2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.9 (0.7) p=.18 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.1(1.1) p=.33
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Internalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 0.2(2.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.8 (0.6) p=.16 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.6(1.0) p=.11
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT]a ⁷³	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Anxious/depressed	Statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.6(1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.5 (0.3) p=.08 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.1(0.5) p=.03

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, Permanent teeth	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Competence	Not statistically significant: N=225. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.4(2.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.4 (0.5) p=.40 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.3(0.9) p=.74
Sundstrom 2011 [[Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Psychological: Loneliness, N (%)	NS difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints: 35 (10.4%) vs 27 (8.0%))
Sundstrom 2011 [[Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Psychological: Positive life events, mean ± SD	NS difference Amalgam vs Control - Positive life events, mean ± SD 1.08 ± 1.2 0.99 ± 1.2
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records) ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Psychological: SCL-90-R: Symptom dimension (Mean T score) Symptoms measured: Somatization, obsessive compulsiveness, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, anxiety, hostility, phobic anxiety, paranoid ideation, psychoticism, global severity index, positive symptom distress index.	Both groups demonstrated similar profile patterns with no statistically significant differences in either of the symptom dimensions (somatization SOM - predominant factor in both groups reflects distress arising from perceptions of bodily dysfunction (mean t scores 60). T scores of all other factors were, on average, located within the upper normal range (50 to 60). In amalgam group: Obsessive-compulsiveness O-C - and interpersonal sensitivity I-S -slightly elevated mean scores; depression DEP; anxiety ANX; hostility HOS; phobic anxiety PHOB; paranoid ideation PAR; and psychoticism PSY). Findings of SCL-90-R analyzed in terms of raw scores. Neither simple group comparisons nor analyses of covariance controlling for age, sex, and education revealed any statistically significant difference between groups
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records) ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Psychological: SCL-90-R: Three global indices (Mean T score)	Three global distress indices (global severity index (GSI); positive symptom distress index (PSDI); and positive symptom total (PST)) did not differ between groups

Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁵⁴	Symptoms attributed to presence amalgam restorations vs symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals, not Hg from dental restorations	Psychological: SAM questionnaire (Mean T score)	“Sample 2” patients showed lower mean raw values for both sub scores of private and public self-consciousness than patients of amalgam group. Simple group comparisons as well as adjustments concerning age, sex, and education resulted in statistically significant differences (p<.001)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: School maladjustment	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 52.3(1.7). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.5 (0.5) p=.34 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.5(0.8) p=.56
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 51.6(1.8). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.5) p=.40 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.4(0.9) p=.67
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR Change Score: School maladjustment	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 1.8(2.9). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1 (0.8) p=.93 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(1.2) p=.73
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school Change Score	Not statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 1.1(3.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.04 (0.8) p=.97 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.5(1.4) p=.74
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations Change Score	Statistically significant: N=119. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 2.6(2.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): 1.3 (0.7) p=.06 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 2.3(1.1) p=.03
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ^{a73}	Amalgam, permanent teeth	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations	Not statistically significant: N=264. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 52.1(1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.3) p=.27 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.7(0.6) p=.25
Study quality: Low (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aNew England Amalgam Trial. BASC-SR=Behaviour Assessment System for Children-Revised, CBCL=Child Behaviour Check List, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SCL-90=Symptom Checklist, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SY=Surface Years, yr=Year			

Table 45: Patient amalgam removal/restoration and psychological outcomes

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ⁵⁷	Removal+replacement other materials vs No removal/ healthy	Psychological: SF-36 Mental Component change score	NS difference between Amalgam (mean -4.3, SD 8.7) and MUPS cohorts (mean -1.5, SD 10.4; p=.682)
Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post and control] ⁵⁷	Removal+ replacement other materials vs No removal/ healthy	Psychological: SF 36 Physical and Mental Component Summary scores	Baseline to follow-up, scores increased significantly in Amalgam cohort (p=.001 and p= 009, respectively) , indicating improved health status. MUPS and Healthy cohorts: no significant changes from baseline to follow-up
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	Psychological: Difference in SF-36 mental health between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	Groups did not differ significantly with regard to mean differences. Removal (n=26): 3.5 (8.3); removal+biol. detox (n=24): 4.4 (10.6); no removal (n=21): 5.0 (9.1); p= 0.858
Weidenhammer 2010 [Retrospective data analysis of RCT] ⁵⁹	Amalgam removal vs No removal	Psychological: Post intervention mental component of HRQoL (SF-36 score MCS)- changes from baseline to month 12	No significant differences between groups: both groups improved similarly. No correlation of the dummy variable (removal of fillings, 0 = no, 1 = yes) with any of the psychometric outcome variables
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	Psychological: Difference in SCL-90-R Global Severity Index between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	Groups did not differ significantly with regard to mean differences. Removal (n=26): - 5.5 (7.4); removal+biol. Detox (n=26): - 4.9 (8.9); no removal (n=22): - 6.9 (5.4), p= 0.633
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	Psychological: Summary scores for SF-12: mental health component score (MCS)	NS inter-group differences between men and women, younger and older age groups, replacement and non-replacement groups or application approval and rejection. Compared with Swedish general population, subjects significantly lower HRQoL in terms of MCS (mean, 46.2; CI 95%, 44.6–47.8 vs 52.8; CI 95%, 52.6–53.0 in population). Post hoc analysis excluding subjects on disability pensions disclosed MCS still significantly lower than corresponding ages in general population (p<.0001)
Weidenhammer 2010 [Retrospective data analysis of RCT] ⁵⁹	Amalgam removal vs No removal	Psychological: Post intervention global index for psychological distress (SCL-90 GSI)- changes from baseline to 12 months	No significant difference between groups: Psychological distress decreased. No correlation of dummy variable (removal of fillings, 0 = no, 1 = yes) with any psychometric outcome variables
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Psychological: Intensity of complaints for anxiety/depression – questionnaire [m, SD]	Statistically significant change: Between selection time (Questionnaire 1) and pre-treatment examination (before removal of amalgam), intensity of complaints decreased for anxiety/depression - 3.0 (SD = 3.2) to 2.2 (SD = 2.7) (paired t-test; p=.048, n = 19)

Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Psychological: Intensity of anxiety/depression complaints from pre-treatment to 3 yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean: 2.2(2.65) vs 2.1(2.72) p=.840, SRM: 0.047
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: GHC -Anxiety/depression (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant changes from baseline across both follow-ups: Before removal: 2.4 (0.4); 1yr after removal: 0.9 (0.4), p <0.001 ; 5yrs after removal: 0.7 (0.4), p <0.001 . MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 2.1 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 2.0 (0.4), p= 0.828 ; 2nd follow-up (4 yrs after Q2): 2.4 (0.4), p= 0.611 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.2 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.3 (0.6); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.4 (0.7), p= .670
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Intense nervousness (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Non-significant: Amalgam cohort: 0.56, 0.22, p=.070 , 0.33, 95% CI= -0.03, 0.69
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale - Sadness (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Non-significant: Amalgam cohort: 0.72, 0.09, p=.414 , 0.15, 95% CI= -0.20, 0.4
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Fluctuating mood (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant: Amalgam cohort: 1.06, 0.25, p= .044 , 0.37, 95% CI= 0.01, 0.73
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Depressed mood (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Non-significant: Amalgam cohort: 0.75, 0.19, p= 0.110 , 0.29, 95% CI= -0.07, 0.64
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Irritability (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant: Amalgam cohort: 1.09, 0.22, p=.006 , 0.52, 95% CI= 0.15, 0.89
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Anxiety (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant: Amalgam cohort: 0.78, 0.25, p=.044 , 0.37, 95% CI= 0.01, 0.73
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Worries -restlessness (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant: Amalgam cohort: 1.06 ,0.47, p=.005 , 0.53, 95% CI= 0.16, 0.90

	with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal		
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Stress at the job (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant change: Amalgam cohort: 1.63, 0.66, p <0.001 , 0.83, 95% CI= 0.43, 1.23
Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁵⁶	Removal amalgam restorations vs Positive amalgam group	Psychological: Odds ratio of self-reported symptom improvement	NS One year odds of symptom improvement and worsening in treatment group vs positive amalgam group: Depression, anxiety and unusually moody
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	Psychological: Difference in KKG internal locus of control between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	Groups did not differ significantly with regard to mean differences. Removal (n=26): - 0.2 (9.3); removal+biol. Detox (n=26): 2.3 (7.8); no removal (n=22): 4.1 (7.2), p= 0.197
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	Psychological: Difference in KKG external locus of control between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	Groups did not differ significantly with regard to mean differences. Removal (n=26): 1.1 (11.8); removal + biol. Detox (n=26): 0.2 (10.4); no removal (n=22): 0.7 (8.9), p= 0.947
Melchart 2008 [RCT] ⁴⁰	Removal+ replacement vs Removal+vitamins or no removal	Psychological: Difference in KKG fatalistic externality between baseline and month 12- mean (SD)	Groups did not differ significantly with regard to mean differences. Removal (n=26): 0.8 (12.1); removal+biol. Detox (n=26): - 0.4 (9.2); no removal (n=22): - 1.8 (11.0), p= 0.711
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post (control group results not included in this study)] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metallo-ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Psychological: Personality variable (MMPI-2)	NS change over time. Mean values MMPI-2 subscales stable over time (ANOVA for repeated measures; p>0.05). The scales Hypochondriasis ('Concern with bodily symptoms'), Depression ('Depressive Symptoms') and Hysteria ('Awareness of problems and vulnerabilities') slightly elevated vs norm (mean T-score >65)
Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre-post (control group results not included in this study)] ³⁹	Amalgam removal+replacement with other materials (composites, 79%, other: gold inlays, metallo-ceramic crowns/bridges, ceramic crowns/inlays, GIC) vs NA	Psychological: Life satisfaction (Cantril Ladder of Life Scale)	Current life satisfaction (Cantril Ladder of Life Scale) higher at 5yr follow-up than pre-treatment (mean 6.9 vs mean 5.8), but over time mean values NS different (p=.166) . Mean value for current life satisfaction higher than mean value for situation 12 months ago, and lower than imagined situation 12mnths ahead
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Indecision (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Statistically significant change: Amalgam cohort: 0.97, 0.28, p=.027 , 0.41, 95% CI=0.05, 0.77

Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Symptom reduction at 1yr (Q2) and 5yr (Q3) after removal compared to before removal (Q1) (mean intensity)	Amalgam cohort: mean intensity of each of all 23 items reduced at first follow-up (Q2) vs baseline; 14 symptoms significantly reduced. Largest reductions (ES about 0.6) observed for intraoral pain/tenderness, taste disturbance, cardiovascular complaints, difficulty concentrating, and anxiety/depression . At second follow-up (Q3), reduction in mean intensity observed for all but one item vs baseline (Q1)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Munich Amalgam Scale -Feeling of walking next to yourself (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Significant: Amalgam cohort: 0.63, 0.28, p=.018 , 0.44, 95% CI= 0.08, 0.80
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Psychological: Reduction of symptoms over time	Amalgam cohort: Highest ESs (estimated by SRM) found for 'metallic taste' (0.93), ' stress at the job ' (0.83), 'skin rash' (0.57), 'sensitivity to cold and wind' (0.54), ' worries – restlessness (0.53), and 'irritability' (0.52) ; and significant reduction of intensity of symptoms was shown Moderate ESs (around 0.4) were found for items ' feeling of walking next to oneself ', 'arrhythmia', 'diarrhoea', 'increased urge to toilet', ' indecision ', 'abdominal pain', 'lack of concentration', ' fluctuating mood ', ' anxiety ', and 'burning sensation in tongue', all being statistically significant
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade). ANOVA=Analysis of Variance, CI=Confidence Interval, GIC=Glass Ionomer, Cement, GSI=Global Score Index, HRQOL=Health Related Quality Of Life, M=Mean, NA=Not Applicable, MCS=Mental Component Score, MMPI=Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, OLR=Oral Lichenoid Reactions, PCS=Physical COMPONENT Score, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SCL-90=Symptom Checklist, SD=Standard Deviation, SF-36=Short-Form Survey			

Table 46: Patient amalgam exposure and respiratory symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Respiratory: Respiratory, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam vs control SS - 113 (33.0) vs 90 (26.3) p<.05
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Respiratory: Airway problem, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 93 (27.6%) vs 65 (19.3%) p=.011
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Respiratory: Short of breath, N (%)	NS difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control: 51 (15.1%) vs 48 (14.2%)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Respiratory: Dyspnoea (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	NS change: Amalgam cohort: 0.41, 0.03, p= 0.712 , 0.07, 95% CI= -0.28 0.41
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade). CI=Confidence Interval, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, SRM=Standardized Response Mean, SS=Symptom Score			

Table 47: Patient amalgam exposure and urinary problems

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Urinary: Urinating problem, N (%)	NS difference between groups: Amalgam vs control NS - 49 (14.3) vs 35 (10.2)
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Urinary: Urinating problem, N (%)	NS difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 47 (13.9%) vs 33 (9.8%)
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade). N=Number, NS=Non-significant			

Table 48: Patient amalgam exposure and visual/ocular problems

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵²	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Visual/Ocular: Visual problem, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam vs control SS - 100 (29.2) vs 64 (18.7) p< 0.05
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁵³	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam vs No health complaints attributed to amalgam	Visual/Ocular: Visual problem, N (%)	Significant difference between groups, amalgam related complaints vs control (non-amalgam related complaints): 98 (29.1%) vs 60 (17.8%) p=.001
Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade). N=Number			

Table 49: Patient amalgam removal/replacement and visual/ocular symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Visual/Ocular: Visual disturbances GHC (mean intensity score (SE), test of change from baseline (P-value))	Amalgam cohort: Significant change first follow-up, not second: Before removal: 3.3 (0.4); 1 year after removal: 2.4 (0.4), p= 0.042 ; 5 years after removal: 2.9 (0.4), p= 0.372 . MUPS cohort: No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 2.2 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 2.7 (0.4), p= 0.311 ; 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 2.6 (0.4), p= 0.507 . Healthy cohort (no MUPS): No significant changes from baseline at both follow-ups: Baseline (Q1): 0.3 (0.4); 1st follow-up (2yrs after Q1): 0.7 (1.3); 2nd follow-up (4yrs after Q2): 0.6 (0.9), p= 0.707
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Visual/Ocular: Eye infection-Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	No significant change: Amalgam cohort: 0.25, 0.03, p=.786 , 0.05, 95% CI= -0.30, 0.40 (1yr follow-up)
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Visual/Ocular: Visual disorders-Munich Amalgam Scale (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	No significant change: Amalgam cohort: 0.81, 0.13, p= 0.211 , 0.23, 95% CI= -0.13, 0.58 (1yr follow-up)
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁵	Removal amalgam+replacement other restorative materials vs Reference group	Visual/Ocular: Intensity of visual disturbances from pre-treatment to 3 yr follow-up [m, SD, p-value] [Within group]	No statistically significant change pre-treatment vs follow-up: Mean:3.0(2.79) vs 3.1(2.90) p=.882 , SRM: -0.035
Study quality: Weak (red shade). CI=Confidence Interval, GHC=General Health Complaints, M=Mean, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms N=Number, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, yr=Year			

Table 50: Patient amalgam exposure and other symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Wright 2012 [Case control] ⁷⁴	Amalgam vs No amalgam fillings in individuals with/without autism	Autism: Uncorrected Urinary mercury level and autism [nmol/l]	Table 1 gives data on urine mercury level for the ASD and control groups. Mercury levels attained for 230 of the 251 children (92%). Of these, 28 below LOD replaced by either 0.35 or zero. No significant differences between 4 groups in uncorrected mercury level regardless of how the values below LODs treated [mercury level with blanks given zero (KW(3) = 5.135, p=.162), or mercury level with blanks given 0.35 (KW(3) = 5.223, p=.56]. No difference between the groups and creatinine levels (KW(3) = 1.734, p=.630)
Wright 2012 [Case control] ⁷⁴	Amalgam vs No amalgam fillings in individuals with/without autism	Autism: Creatinine corrected urinary mercury level and autism [mmol/l]	No significant differences between four groups regardless of the values below LODs treated (mercury level with blanks given zero (KW(3) = 6.889, p=.076) or mercury level with blanks given 0.35 (KW(3) = 7.450, p=.059). Even after removing outliers with extreme values (children with values >3 box lengths from upper or lower edge of box/IQR, No significant differences between groups (mercury level with blanks given zero (KW(3) = 5.738, p=.125) or mercury level with blanks given 0.35 (KW(3) = 6.333, p=.096)). After adjusting for age, gender and number of fillings, still no statistically significant difference between the groups (mercury level with blanks given zero: F (3) = 2.587, p=.056 ; mercury level with blanks given 0.35: F (3) = 2.570, p=.056), even after removing extreme values (mercury level with blanks given zero: F (3) = 0.897, p=.444
Wright 2012 [Case control] ⁷⁴	Amalgam vs No amalgam fillings in individuals with/without autism	Autism: Other metals and autism	NS Tests of other heavy metals find no differences between groups. This includes lithium (p=.344), vanadium (p=.951), manganese (p=.613), cobalt (p=.392), copper (p=.391), cadmium (p=.586), antimony (p=.216), barium (p=.328) and lead (p=.203)*
Geier 2013 [Subset RCT] ^{a75}	Amalgam	Renal: (PT damage) GST-alpha	Statistically significant relationship: Adjusted significant dose-dependent correlation between increasing Hg exposure from amalgams and increasing urinary GST-a levels Beta-co-efficient =0.0047 (standard error: 0.002) df: 358 T statistics: 2.04 p <0.05 . Unadjusted analyses: Beta-co-efficient = 0.0041 (standard error: 0.002) df: 584 T statistics: 1187 p=.062b
Geier 2013 [Subset RCT] ⁷⁵	Amalgam	Renal: (DT damage) GST-pie	No significant adjusted correlation between increasing Hg exposure from amalgams and increasing urinary GST-pie levels. Adjusted: Beta-co-efficient =0.0042 (standard error: 0.002) df: 697 T statistics: 1.88 p =.060 . Unadjusted: Beta-co-efficient =0.0064 (standard error: 0.002) df: 826 T statistics: 2.71 p <0.01b

Cabana-Munoz 2015 [Cross sectional with control] ⁷⁶	Exposure: Amalgam restorations min.10yrs. Women divided 2 groups: <4 dental amalgam restorations (n= 27); >4 amalgam restorations; (n=15)	Oxidative stress: Antioxidant marker: SOD-1	SOD-1 activity increased in women with dental amalgam fillings vs control subjects (p<0.05). Strong correlation between SOD-1 activity and presence of Hg (r = 0.6; p<.05)
Cabana-Munoz 2015 [Cross sectional with control] ⁷⁶	Exposure: Amalgam restorations min.10yrs. Women divided 2 groups: <4 dental amalgam restorations (n= 27); >4 amalgam restorations; (n=15)	Oxidative stress: Antioxidant marker: glutathione (reduced form)	Glutathione (reduced form) increased in women with dental amalgam fillings vs control subjects (p<.05). strong correlation between Al levels and glutathione (r = 0.48, p<.05)
Cabana-Munoz 2019 [Cross sectional with control] ⁷⁷	Exposure: Group 1) Amalgam + long term titanium implants; 2) Amalgam alone vs control: No dental materials	Oxidative stress: systemic taurine levels (pM)	Systemic taurine levels significantly reduced in patients with long-term dental amalgams as compared to controls (p<.05)
Loupou 2020 [Prospective cohort] ⁷⁸	Hg silver restorations vs NA	Maternal health: Dental amalgam status and Gestational hypertension	Dental amalgam status NS associated with GH either in unadjusted or adjusted models. Adjusted ORs (95% CI) for GH according to presence of dental amalgam reported first trimester visit: 1.31 (0.92, 1.85) and 1.32 (0.86, 2.04) for women with 1–4 amalgams and with ≥ 5 amalgams, respectively vs without amalgam. Findings similar for presence of amalgams at third trimester. Models considering fish consumption did not change the associations between number of amalgams and odds ratio of GH in either 1st or 3rd trimesters. Sensitivity analysis including covariates missing data in model showed minimal changes in results. Another sensitivity analysis (excluding participants reporting dental amalgams at first trimester but missing data at third trimester) showed minimal changes in GH results with presence of dental amalgam in either trimester (aORs (95%CI) = 1.11 (0.74, 1.66) and 1.20 (0.73, 1.96) for women with 1–4 and with ≥ 5 amalgams, respectively vs without amalgam. No association between no. dental amalgams (first and third trimester measure together) and SBP or DBP

Piagno 2020 [Prospective longitudinal] ⁷⁹	Amalgam	Exposure: Estimated short-term exposure to mercury in BC- $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	The maximum estimated 8-h average ground-level elemental mercury vapour concentration associated with crematorium emissions was $0.31 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. As in the case of long-term exposure, there is no indication that short-term exposure to peak ground-level mercury vapour concentrations associated with crematorium emissions poses a significant risk to human health
Piagno 2020 [Prospective Longitudinal] ⁷⁹	Amalgam	Exposure: Estimated long-term risk exposure to mercury in BC-Hazard quotient	Maximum estimated annual average ground-level elemental mercury vapour concentration associated with crematorium emissions: $7.9 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. At this exposure, assuming reference concentration $0.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, hazard quotient: 0.026 . If more conservative reference concentration $0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ used, hazard quotient increases to 0.13. In either case, hazard quotient is sufficiently less than 1 and risk is deemed acceptable; i.e. no significant risk of adverse effects on human health from long-term exposure to mercury vapour at concentration of $7.9 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Strong (green shade) a=Casa Pia trial,bOutcome estimate was adjusted for the baseline level (i.e. study year 1) of urinary mercury, each porphyrin measure, gender, race, blood lead level, and GST-a level. ASD=Autistic Spectrum Disorders, CI=CI, DF=Degrees of Freedom, DBP=Diastolic Blood Pressure, GH=Gestational Hypertension, N=number, NS=Non-Significant, aOR=Adjusted Odds Ratio, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SBP=Systolic Blood Pressure			

Table 51: Patient dental amalgam removal/replacement and other symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Anthropomorphic: Weight loss (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Non-significant change: Amalgam cohort: 0.44, 0.19, p=.136 , 0.27, 95% CI= -0.08, 0.62
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Anthropomorphic: Overweight (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Non-significant change: Amalgam cohort: 0.50, 0.09, p=.263 , 0.20, 95% CI= -0.15, 0.55
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort with control groups] ⁵⁰	Removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS attributed to amalgam vs No removal	Female health: Menstrual disorders (Baseline mean, mean change, p-value, SRM, 95% CI)	Amalgam cohort (n=19): 0.37, 0.11, p=.682 , 0.10, 95% CI= -0.43, 0.64
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Blood haemoglobin (g/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 138 (9); Before: 137 (12); After: 138 (12) Control/Before: NS Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Red blood cell count (10 ¹² /l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 4.6 (0.3); Before: 4.5 (0.4); After: 4.5 (0.4); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Haematocrit (%)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 40.5 (3.0); Before: 40 (3.6); After: 40.5 (3.8); Before/After: NS; Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Red blood mean corpuscular Volume (fl)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 88.1 (3.8); Before: 88.9 (3.8); After: 88.8 (4.7); Before/After: NS; Before/After: NS

Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Red blood mean corpuscular Haemoglobin (pg)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 29.8 (1.3); Before: 30.6 (1.7); After: 30.6 (1.7); Before/After: NS; Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Blood platelet count (109/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 252 (52); Before: 256 (42); After: 247 (40); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Serum LDH (μ kat/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 5.4 (0.7); Before: 6.3 (1.0); After: 5.0 (0.6); Control/Before: p<0.01; Before/After: p<0.01
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Serum cholesterol (mmol/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 5.3 (0.7); Before: 5.6 (1.3); After: 5.7 (1.1); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: NS
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Serum sodium (mmol/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 139.9 (1.6); Before: 138.5 (1.3); After: 140.6 (1.9);
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam vs no intervention	Clinical chemistry variables: Serum potassium (mmol/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 4.0 (0.2); Before: 3.9 (0.3); After: 4.1 (0.3); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<0.05
Frisk 2007 [CBA] ⁶²	Removal dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to	Clinical chemistry variables: Serum creatinine (μ mol/l)	24 amalgam removed, 22 control. Mean (SD)-Control: 84.1 (7.8); Before: 84.7 (11.9); After: 80.6 (10.5); Control/Before: NS; Before/After: p<0.01

	amalgam vs no intervention		
Loupou 2020 [Prospective cohort] ⁷⁸	Hg silver restorations vs NA	Maternal health: Gestational hypertension	NS associations found for dental amalgam replacement. aORs (95%CI): 0.75 (0.40, 1.42) and 0.73 (0.39, 1.34) respectively for replacement within 12 months prior to first trimester visit and replacement during pregnancy
Loupou 2020 [Prospective cohort] ⁷⁸	Hg silver restorations vs NA	Maternal health: Blood pressure [Systolic and Diastolic]	Replacement of dental amalgam before/during pregnancy associated with decreased SBP while associations with DBP remained non-significant.
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	Low tolerance to environmental factors (N)	Significantly higher proportion replacement group reported symptoms than non-replacement group (p=.036)
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ⁵⁸	Amalgam replacement for individuals with OLR with CR	Sensitivity to electric or magnetic fields (N)	Significantly higher proportion replacement group reported symptoms than non-replacement group (p=.002). Analyses of subgroups after exclusion of all subjects without approved applications for subsidized dental restoration replacement (n = 81) and exclusion of subjects in replacement group with approved applications who had not stated that they had proceeded with replacement of dental amalgam restorations (n = 25), only one symptom remained significantly different between replacement vs non-replacement groups: sensitivity to electric or magnetic fields, more frequent in replacement group (p=.032)
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade) aOR=Adjusted Odds Ratio, CBA=Controlled Before and After, CI=Confidence Interval, CR=Composite Resin, DBP=Diastolic Blood Pressure, Hg=Mercury, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Non-Significant, OLR=Oral Lichenoid Reactions, SBP=Systolic Blood Pressure, SD=Standard Deviation, SRM=Standardized Response Mean			

Composite resin tables

Table 52: Patient composite/methacrylate exposure and allergy

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Ahlgren 2014 [Cross-sectional with control] ⁹	Exposure: Amalgam or Composite restoration in individuals with OLL vs DP or PSFF	Allergy: Composite allergy (N)	N. contact allergies to composite substances 12 in the OLL group and 6 in DP group (8 vs 4 patients, respectively). Oral lichen lesions adjacent to composite fillings found in three of eight patients with contact allergy to composite substances; in addition, another three patients had oral lichen lesions and composite fillings in one and the same quadrant. No contact allergy to composite substances were found in the two OLL patients who had composite fillings but no amalgam adjacent to the lichen lesions
Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁴³	Women with diagnosis 'Allergic stomatitis' vs women with 'Noninflammatory oral complaints. Allergen: Resins	Allergy: Patch test results: Allergen – Resins, N (%)	Allergic stomatitis (n=444) vs Non-inflammatory oral complaints (n=1231) Allergen, Concentration, Tested (N), Positive (N), Positive (%), 95% (CI): N.S: Epoxy resin 1% pet. 441 6 1.4 (0.5–2.9) 1216 15 1.2 (0.7–2.0) N.S: Melamine formaldehyde resin 7% pet. 438 3 0.7 (0.1–2.0) 1198 3 0.3 (0.1–0.7)
Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁴³	Women with diagnosis Allergic stomatitis' vs women with 'Noninflammatory oral complaints. Allergen: Methacrylate's	Allergy: Methacrylate's, N (%)	Women with allergic stomatitis sensitized primarily to metals, (meth)acrylates, and natural substances. To investigate sensitization to (meth)acrylates, included results from dental technician test series in evaluation. Comparable rates of sensitization observed for ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA; 4.1% vs. 0.7%), methyl methacrylate (MMA; 4.1% vs. 0.9%), 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA; 4.8% vs. 0.7%) and 2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate (HPMA; 4.3% vs. 0.7%). These rates of (meth)acrylate sensitization significantly higher than observed in controls . Only a few positive reactions detected for diurethane dimethacrylate (1.0% vs. 0.0%) and other (meth)acrylates tested. Significant difference was observed for PETA; 2.5% vs. 0.2%

Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁴³	Women with diagnosis Allergic stomatitis' vs women with 'Noninflammatory oral complaints. Allergen Acrylates/Methacrylate's	Allergy: Patch test results: Allergen-Acrylates and methacrylate's, N (%)	Allergic stomatitis (n=444) vs Non-inflammatory oral complaints (n=1231) Allergen, Concentration, Tested (N), Positive (N), Positive (%), 95% (CI): Significant difference: HEMA 1% pet. 442 21 4.8 (3.0–7.2) 1213 9 0.7 (0.3–1.4) Significant difference: HPMA 2% pet. 437 19 4.3 (2.6–6.7) 1200 8 0.7 (0.3–1.3) Significant difference: EGDMA 2% pet. 441 18 4.1 (2.4–6.4) 1215 8 0.7 (0.3–1.3) Significant difference: MMA 2% pet. 442 18 4.1 (2.4–6.4) 1216 11 0.9 (0.5–1.6) Significant difference: PETA 0.1% pet. 436 11 2.5 (1.3–4.5) 1202 2 0.2 (0.0–0.6) N.S: Ethyl acrylate 0.1% pet. 438 9 2.1 (0.9–3.9) 1202 6 0.5 (0.2–1.1) N.S: Ethyl methacrylate 2% pet. 437 5 1.1 (0.4–2.6) 1201 3 0.2 (0.1–0.7) N.S: Diurethane dimethacrylate 2% pet. 390 4 1.0 (0.3–2.6) 1038 0 0.0 (0.0–0.4) N.S: BUDMA 2% pet. 439 4 0.9 (0.2–2.3) 1205 4 0.3 (0.1–0.8) N.S: Tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate 2% pet. 438 3 0.7 (0.1–2.0) 1201 2 0.2 (0.0–0.6) N.S: TEGDMA 2% pet. 442 3 0.7 (0.1–2.0) 1216 2 0.2 (0.0–0.6)
Lynch (2015) [Retrospective cohort with before and after element] ⁴⁷	Partial/complete replacement of amalgams vs No removal/replacement	Allergy: Positive Reactions to Allergens in British Society of Cutaneous Allergy Standard Series, Dental Series, Amalgam Series, and Methacrylate Series, N (%)	0.5% Mercury 10 (32) 5% Nickel sulfate 7 (23) 0.5% Gold sodium thiosulfate 3 (10) 1% Cobalt chloride 3 (10) 2% Palladium chloride 2 (6) 2% Copper Sulfate 2 (6) 2% Toludine diethanolamine 1 (3) 1% Camphorquinone 1 (3) 3% Carba mix 1 (3) 0.1% Potassium dicyanoaurate 1 (3)
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to BPA in Atopic vs Non-atopic patients - %	Bisphenol A- Atopic: 5%; Non-atopic: 0%
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to methyl methacrylate in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	Methyl methacrylate- Atopic: 5%; Non-atopic: 2.5%
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to N-Dimethyl-p-Toludine in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	N-Dimethyl-p-Toludine- Atopic: 2.5%; Non-atopic: 0%

Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to Ethylenglycol dimethacrylate in atopic vs Non-Atopic patients - %	Ethylenglycol dimethacrylate- Atopic: 2.5%; Non-atopic: 0%
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to triethyleneglycol dimethacrylate in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	Triethyleneglycol dimethacrylate- atopic: 2.5%; Non-atopic: 0%
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to diurethane dimethacrylate in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	Diurethane dimethacrylate- atopic: 0% ; Non-atopic: 0%
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to (2-hydroxyethyl) methacrylate in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	2-HEMA- atopic: 5%; Non-atopic: 5%. Two other patients, one atopic, the other nonatopic, presented desquamative type lesions on the fingertips of both hands, together with positive patch test to methyl methacrylate (++) and (2-hydroxyethyl)- methacrylate (2-HEMA) (++) in case of the atopic patient. Both cases corresponded to occupational dermatitis, a dentist and metal factory worker, respectively
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Frequency of sensitized patients to BIS-GMA in Atopic vs Non-atopic patient's - %	BIS-GMA: No statistically significant difference in sensitization between Atopic vs Non-atopic group Atopic: (10% vs. 0%).
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁴	Atopic vs Non-atopic [Methacrylate's]a	Allergy: Summary Allergy	On comparing frequency of sensitization between Atopic and Non-atopic patients, 67.5% of Atopic presented sensitization vs 55% Non-atopic patients. This difference not statistically significant (p> 0.05) . Frequency of sensitization by group and by dental material tested compared in Figure 1. Those that presented greatest difference in sensitization for Atopic group with respect to Non-atopic group were ammoniated mercury (25% vs. 15%), benzoyl peroxide (22.45% vs. 2.5%), amalgam (17.5% vs. 2.5%) and BIS-GMA (10% vs. 0%). However, only benzoyl peroxide difference statistically significant (p<0.05)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Methacrylate	Allergy: Methyl methacrylate, 2% Positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 2 (1.7)

Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Methacrylate	Allergy: Triethyleneglycol Dimethacrylate, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 2 (1.7)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Methacrylate	Allergy: Ethieneglycol Dimethacrylate, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 2 (1.7)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Composite assumedb	Allergy: BIS/GMA 2%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 1 (0.9)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Methacrylateb	Allergy: Diurethane Dimetacrylate 2%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 1 (0.9)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Composite assumedb	Allergy: Epoxy Resin 1%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 1 (0.9)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Composite assumedb	Allergy: Bisphenol A 1%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 0 (0%)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Composite assumedb	Allergy: 2-HEMA 1%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 0 (0%)

Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Cobalt Chloride, 1% Positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 30 (26.1)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Nickel Sulphate 5% Positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 27 (23.5)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Sodium Thiosulphatoaurate, 0.25%, 20%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 9 (7.8)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Palladium Chloride, 20% positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 9 (7.8)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Potassium Dicyanoaurate, 0.02% positive skin patch test, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 6(5.2)
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁵¹	Not stated	Allergy: Allergy: Ammonium Tetacholoroplatinate 0.25%, N (%)	Skin patch results patients with OLR (N=115) 1 (0.9)
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aParticipants considered atopic when min. two criteria present: clinical history atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, allergic asthma, or food allergies; each confirmed by prick test. bLabelled "Synthetics". BPA=Bisphenol-A, BisGMA=Bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate, BUDMA=1-4-butanediol dimethacrylate, DP=Dermatitis Patients, EGDMA=Ethylene Glycos Dimethacrylate, HEMA=2-Hydroxyethyl methacrylate, HMPA=Hydroxypropyl Methacrylate, MMA=Methyl methacrylate, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLR=Oral Lichenoid Reactions, PETA=Pentaerythritol Tri Acrylate			

Table 53: Patient composite exposure and genotoxicity

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Pettini 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁸⁰	Micro-hybrid/resin composite vs No Composite/amalgam exposure	Genotoxicity: SCE/cell, Mean (SD)	No statistically significant difference. Controls vs exposed: Mean 5.6(SD 0.8) vs 5.9(SD 1.3), Median: 5.5 vs 5.6, Range: 4.4-7.6 vs 4.1-8.6;
Pettini 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁸⁰	Micro-hybrid/resin composite vs No Composite/amalgam exposure	Genotoxicity: HFC, Mean (SD)	No statistically significant difference. Controls vs exposed: Mean 6.4(SD 6.4) vs 6.7 (SD 7.7), Median: 4.0 vs 4.0, Range: 0-20 vs 0-20
Pettini 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁸⁰	Micro-hybrid/resin composite vs No Composite/amalgam exposure	Genotoxicity: CA, Mean (SD)	No statistically significant difference. Controls vs exposed: Mean 1.9(SD 1.8) vs 1.7(SD 1.8), Median: 2.0 vs 1.7, Range: 0-8 vs 0-8
Pettini 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁸⁰	Micro-hybrid/resin composite vs No Composite/amalgam exposure	Genotoxicity: PRI, Mean (SD)	No statistically significant difference. Controls vs exposed: Mean 2.7(SD 0.1) vs 2.7(SD 0.1), Median: 2.7 vs 2.7, Range: 2.5-2.9 vs 2.6-2.9

Gavic 2019 [RCT] ⁸¹	Compomer-Twinkly Star	Genotoxicity: DNA damage at same time point (n micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis) (Frequency)	NS difference in micronuclei frequency across time: Highest frequency after 7d post-restoration (not statistically significant ($p=.092$) vs day 0. NS difference frequency of nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, and karyorrhexis. Karyolysis frequency statistically higher in samples taken 30d following restoration ($p<.001$) vs day 0 & vs day 7 + 90 ($p=.020$). Statistically sig.increase: Frequency no. binucleated cells after 7 and 30ds following restoration ($p=.001$ and $p<.001$, respectively). No sig.difference: samples taken after 90d ($p=.162$)
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin	Genotoxicity: Micronucli (N)	ANOVA and Student–Newman–Keuls confirmed a statistically significant difference for the frequency of micronuclei in samples taken seven ($p=.0021$) and 30d following the restoration ($p=.0498$)
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin	Genotoxicity: Karyolyses (N)	Statistically significant difference throughout all three sampling times: ($p=.0186$, 0.0112 , 0.0002). Time of exposure and type of material had a significant effect on the occurrence of karyolysis ($\beta=0.47$; $p=.000$ and $\beta=0.25$; $p=.004$, respectively)
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin	Genotoxicity: Nuclear buds (N)	Statistically different 180d post restoration ($p=.0093$)
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Vertise Flow composite	Genotoxicity: Micronucleated cells (N)	Significant increase in samples collected seven ($p=.0277$) and 30d ($p=.0374$) following the restoration vs baseline value.
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Vertise Flow composite	Genotoxicity: Binucleated cells (N)	Vertise: Significant increase 180d vs baseline ($p=.0095$). time of exposure and smoking exhibited significant impact on the occurrence of binuclear cells ($\beta=0.31$; $p=.000$ and $\beta=0.63$; $p=.043$, respectively). NS change in levels for Kalore resin across all time points.
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: Nucleoplasmatic bridges (N)	No significant difference at any time points from pre-treatment for either material
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: Micronuclei (N)	ANOVA: no statistically significant difference between two tested composite materials during the same time of exposure. only the type of composite material displayed a connection to micronucleus frequency ($\beta=0.24$; $p=.014$). Kalore levels at 7 and 30d significantly higher than pre-treatment levels
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: Nuclear buds (N)	ANOVA: no statistically significant difference between two tested composite materials during the same time of exposure. Kalore levels at 180d post treatment significantly higher than pre-treatment levels
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: Karyolysis (N)	ANOVA: no statistically significant difference between two tested composite materials during the same time of exposure
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: Tail length DNA molecules gingival cells (μm)	Significantly higher than pretreatment at 30 & 180d both materials: ANOVA/Student-Newman-Keuls: Exposure: 30d (Kalore: $p=.0004$ and Vertise Flow $p=.0013$). 180d (Kalore: $p=.0350$ and VF: $p=.0010$) 30d significantly higher vs control and 7d exposures. Highest values measured after 30d exposure. Time of exposure and smoking positively

			impact the tail length values ($\beta=0.45$; $p=.000$ and $\beta=0.58$; $p=.049$, respectively). PROGRESS-PLUS: General model of regression: test influence of subjects' age, gender, smoking and alcohol consumption, state of health and use of medication, X-ray exposure, and dietary habits). No significant effect
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁸²	Kalore composite resin vs Vertise Flow	Genotoxicity: % DNA tail in gingival cells	Significantly higher than pre-treatment at 30 & 180d both materials: Highest values measured after 30d exposure. multivariate analysis, the association between dental filling material and DNA damage measured by tail intensity was enhanced by exposure time ($\beta=0.51$; $p=.000$), alcohol consumption ($\beta=1.05$; $p=.041$), and fruit consumption ($\beta=0.99$; $p=.035$). PROGRESS-PLUS; General model of regression: test influence of subjects' age, gender, smoking and alcohol consumption, state of health and use of medication, X-ray exposure, and dietary habits). No significant effect
Study quality: Weak (red shade). ANOVA=Analysis of variance, CA=Chromosome Aberrations, HFC=High Frequency of SCE, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, PRI=Proliferation Rate Index, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SCE=Sister Chromatid Exchange, SD=Standard Deviation			

Table 54: Relationship patient exposure composite resin and immune function

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable composites (preventative), Non-flowable compomer (restorative), non-flowable composite)*	Immune function: WBC counts	Multivariable model between no. resin-composite treated surfaces at follow-up and immune function: no consistent association
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable composite (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function-- %CD69 + PHA, %CD25 + PHA	Multivariable model between no. resin-composite treated surfaces at follow up and immune function: consistent association (at 6mo. T-cell function %CD69+PHA: 1.1 p<.05) but not further follow ups. No consistent association for %CD25+PHA
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable compomer (restorative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function- %CD69 + PHA, %CD25 + PHA	Multivariable model between no. resin-composite treated surfaces at follow up and immune function: no significant association except at five yr follow up (-1.4 p<.05) for %CD69+PHA only
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable composite (restorative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function- %CD69 + PHA, %CD25 + PHA	Multivariable model between no. resin-composite treated surfaces at follow up and immune function: No significant associations
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable bisGMA-composite (restorative)	Immune function: B-cell activation- %CD69 + PWM, %CD23 + PW	Significant positive association between current number of non-flowable bisGMA-based composites and changes in B-cell activation, indicating increased activation, present at 6-months but not 1-year or 5-year visit (%CD69 + PWM only). Other materials: NS association
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable bisGMA-composite (restorative)	Immune function: Monocyte function- %DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	Significant positive association between current number of non-flowable bisGMA-based composites and changes in B-cell activation, indicating increased activation, present at 6-months but not 1-year or 5-year visit (%DHE=PMA only). Other materials: NS association
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable bisGMA-composite	Immune function: Neutrophil-%DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	As number of restorations increased, function decreased at both 6mnths and 1yr follow-up, but not at yr 5

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	BisGMA-based flowable sealant/PRR,	Immune function: Monocyte function- %DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	As number of restorations increased, function decreased at both 6mnths and 1yr follow-up, but not at yr 5. Changes NS
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	BisGMA-based flowable sealant/PRR	Immune function: Neutrophil Neutrophil- %DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	As number of restorations increased, function decreased at both 6mnths and 1yr follow-up, but not at yr 5. Changes NS
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable compomer (Restorative)	Immune function: Monocyte function- %DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	NS changes for each follow up point
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable compomer (Restorative)	Immune function: Neutrophil-%DHE+PMA, %Rho+PMA	NS changes for each follow up point
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Resin composite	Immune function: Overall summary	Repeated measures of immune function over entire 5-year follow-up in multivariable model, associations between the present number of resin-composite surfaces and immune function changes were generally of negligible magnitude
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-Flowable composite (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: B-cell activation	Present number of bisGMA-based standard composite restorations associated with increased B-cell activation markers over follow-up (B-cell %CD69+PWM, $\beta=1.7$, 95% CI:0.6,2.7; %CD23+PWM, $\beta=2.2$, 95% CI:0.5,4.0)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable resin composite (preventative)	Immune function: B-cell activation	Significant positive associations between cumulative treatment levels of composite over follow-up and B-cell responsiveness changes persisted in secondary analyses (not shown); furthermore. Estimates similar for flowable resin-composites 10-SY $\beta=1.0$, 95% CI: -0.1,2.7
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-Flowable composite (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: B-cell activation	Significant positive associations between cumulative treatment levels of composite over follow-up and B-cell responsiveness changes persisted in secondary analyses (not shown). Estimates similar for non-flowable resin-composites 10-SY $\beta=1.2$, 95% CI: -2.1,4.5)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Total WBC count	Significant positive association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.2(0.03, 0.3) p=.02
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Granulocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Monocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell %CD69 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell%CD25 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell%CD69+PWM	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell%CD23+PWM	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %DHE+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.6
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %Rho+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up:-0.3
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %DHE+PMA	Significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.2(-0.4, -0.04) p=.02
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Flowable Composites (Preventative)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %Rho+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.2

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Total white blood cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Lymphocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Granulocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Monocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell: %CD69 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell %CD25 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell%CD69+PWM	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell%CD23+PWM	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.3
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Monocyte function%DHE+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.7

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Monocyte function: %Rho+PMA	Significant Association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 1.1 (0.1, 2.0) p=.02
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %DHE+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, primary teeth)]	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %Rho+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.2
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations ⁴ [Secondary analysis RCT]	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: WBC counts	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Granulocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.1
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte cell count	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell: %CD69 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.5
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: T-cell: %CD25 + PHA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.7
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD69+PWM	Significant Association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 1.7(0.6, 2.7) p=.002

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Lymphocyte function: B-cell: %CD23+PWM	Significant Association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 2.2 (0.5, 4.0) p=.01
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %DHE+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.6
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Monocyte function: %Rho+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.3
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT -NECAT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %DHE+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: -0.0
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT -NECAT] ⁴	Non-flowable Compomer (Restorative, permanent teeth)	Immune function: Neutrophil function: %Rho+PMA	No significant association [β estimates (95% CI)] between present number of tooth surfaces with resin-composites or amalgam and immune function changes from baseline, from repeated measures models over 5-year follow-up: 0.4
Shenker 2008 [RCT-NECAT] ⁵	Amalgam vs Composite	Immune function: Distribution of lymphocytes, monocytes and neutrophils	No consistent or significant difference between and within treatment groups at 5-7 days , 6mnths, 12mnths, 60mnths post-treatment based on ANCOVA models.

Study quality: Strong (green shade). aMultivariable models for resin-composite materials adjusted for type of resin-composite material (no. surfaces currently treated with sealant/preventive resin restoration, compomer, or composite), age, time from baseline visit, study site, baseline blood lead level, and parent-reported asthma or allergy. Models for amalgam created to parallel models for composites and mutually adjusted for amalgam on primary and permanent teeth, as well as sealant/preventive resin restorations, age, time from baseline visit, study site, baseline blood lead level, and parent-reported asthma or allergy. Models included immune function changes from pretreatment at 6-months, 1-year, 1.5-year, and 5-year follow-up visits. CI=Confidence Interval, M=Mean, mnths=Months, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, NS=Not Significant, PRR=Preventative Resin Restoration, SD=Standard Deviation, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, WBC=White blood Cell

Table 55: Patient composite exposure and neuropsychological symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Executive functioning: overall summary	Multivariate ANOVA: association between composite and impairments in tests of executive function not statistically significant (p=.18)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Executive functioning: overall summary	Multivariate analysis of variance, association between composite and impairments in tests of executive function was not statistically significant (p=.18)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary	Neuropsych test scores over follow-up not associated with tertile of sealant or PRR treatment levels. No statistically significant associations or trends observed for test score changes among those with any sealant/PRR treatment. Sensitivity analyses confirmed these findings
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary	Increasing compomer or composite exposure, adjusted mean neuropsych test change scores between baseline and 4- or 5yr follow-up generally consistent in direction of increasing impairment, but few statistically significant associations
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych functioning: WIAT: Overall summary	No significant association with surface year exposure: Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: no significant association with surface yrs exposure
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WCST	No statistical association between exposure and score: Compared to children who ever received any sealants or PRRs, minority of children receiving no sealants or PRRs during the study (<6% of children) had smaller increase in errors on the executive function WCST (e.g., mean total errors 3.8 vs. 17.2-17.8 increase)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WIAT	No significant association between exposure and score: Compared to children who ever received any sealants or PRRs, minority of children receiving no sealants or PRRs during the study (<6% of children) had distinctly worse 5yr changes in WIAT T (e.g., mean 4.7-point decrease vs. 1.3-1.9-point decrease)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WIAT	Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: no significant association with surface yrs exposure

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WISC-III FSIQ	No significant association between exposure and score: Compared to children who ever received any sealants or PRRs, minority of children receiving no sealants or PRRs during the study (<6% of children) had distinctly worse 5yr changes in WISC-III IQ (e.g., mean 1.7 point decrease vs. 2.2–3.5 point increase) Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: –1.7 (2.1)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WISC-III FSIQ	Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, 3.2 (0.6). Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: no significant association with surface yrs exposure
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Overall summary: WISC-III FSIQ	Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: no significant association with surface yrs exposure. Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 2.9 (0.5)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Colour	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 15.7 (3.0)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Colour	Significant association exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 19.7 (0.7). Change scores for the Colour naming trial significantly associated with greater exposure to composites (10 posterior-occlusal surface years total composites $\beta = -1.5$, SE=0.5, p=.004), indicating poorer ability to name colours
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Colour	Significant association with surface years exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 19.7 (0.7). change scores for the Colour naming trial were significantly associated with greater exposure to composites (10 posterior-occlusal surface years total composites $\beta = -1.5$, SE=0.5, p=.004), indicating poorer ability to name colours
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Colour-Word	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*:13.9 (2.4)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 13.1 (0.6)

		interference: Colour-Word	
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Colour-Word	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 12.9 (0.5)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Word	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 25.9 (0.9)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Stroop Colour-Word interference: Word	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 25.4 (0.8)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Trail making test: Part B-Part A	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: -24.7 (13.2)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Trail making test: Part B-Part A	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, -27.4 (3.5) Worse change scores with higher total exposure to compomer/composite were also found for other measures of executive function: Trail-Making Test Part B Part A ($\beta = -3.0$, SE=2.5, $p=.23$), but results were not statistically significant
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Trail making test: Part B-Part A	Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, -31.4 (3.1) Worse change scores with higher total exposure to compomer/composite found for other measures of executive function: Trail-Making Test Part B Part A ($\beta = -3.0$, SE=2.5, $p=.23$), but results were not statistically significant
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal cancellation: ordered trial: no. errors	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, -19.3 (0.5)

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal cancellation: ordered trial: no. errors	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, -19.1 (0.5)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal fluency: category fluency	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 9.6 (0.4)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal fluency: category fluency	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 9.5 (0.4)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal fluency: Letter fluency	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 13.5 (2.0)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal fluency: letter fluency	Significant association with exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 13.8 (0.6). Children with greater exposure to either compomer or composite had poorer change scores on Letter Fluency; an additional 10 posterior-occlusal surface yrs was associated with a decreased mean change score by 0.8 (SE=0.4, p=.035)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: Verbal fluency: letter fluency	Significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 13.2 (0.5) Children with greater exposure to either compomer or composite had poorer change scores on Letter Fluency; an additional 10 posterior-occlusal surface yrs was associated with a decreased mean change score by 0.8 (SE=0.4, p=.035)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: No. categories achieved	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 7.9 (4.0)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: No. categories achieved	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 1.1 (0.1)

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: No. categories achieved	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 1.1 (0.1)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total errors	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 3.8 (4.1)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total errors	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 15.9 (1.1)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total errors	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 16.6 (1.0)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total perseveration errors	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 0.8 (0.4)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total perseveration errors	Significant association with exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 17.6 (1.1). Worse change scores with higher total exposure to compomer/composite measures of executive function: perseverative errors in the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test ($\beta=1.4$, SE=0.8, $p=.08$)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WCST: Total perseveration errors	Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 18.5 (1.0). Worse change scores with higher total exposure to compomer/composite found for other measures of executive function: perseverative errors in Wisconsin Card Sorting Test ($\beta=1.4$, SE=0.8, $p=.08$) but results not statistically significant
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Mathematics	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: -5.3 (3.0)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Mathematics	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, -1.9 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Mathematics	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, -2.2 (0.7)

Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Reading	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: -4.7 (2.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Reading	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, -1.7 (0.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WIAT: Reading	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, -1.3 (0.7)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Freedom from distractibility	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 1.4 (3.0)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Perceptual organisation	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: -3.4 (2.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Perceptual organisation	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, 3.9 (0.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Perceptual organisation	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 3.9 (0.7)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Verbal comprehension	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: -1.0 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Verbal comprehension	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, 2.0 (0.7)

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Verbal comprehension	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 1.6 (0.6)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Freedom from distractibility	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, 3.8 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Freedom from distractibility	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 2.8 (0.7)
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Processing speed	No significant association between exposure and score: Adjusted Mean (SE) Changes in Neuropsychosocial Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Total Cumulative Exposure to Flowable Sealants and Preventive Resin Restorations*: 0.9 (3.4)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Processing speed	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=219, 7.0 (0.9)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WISC-III FSIQ: Processing speed	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 5yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer or Composite on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 6.8 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: GMI	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 8.0 (0.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: GMI	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 7.5 (0.6)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Learning	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 9.9 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Learning	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 10.1 (0.8)

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Overall summary	Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: No significant association with surface yrs exposure
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Overall summary	Secondary analyses combining total posterior-occlusal composites exposure: no significant association with surface yrs exposure
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Verbal memory	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 2.7 (0.7)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Verbal memory	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 2.2 (0.6)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Visual memory	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 6.5 (0.9)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAML: Visual memory	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 5.7 (0.8)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAVMA: Visual motor composite	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=201, 3.3 (0.9)
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and Neuropsych [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁶⁸	Resin composite/compomer vs NA	Neuropsych: WRAVMA: Visual motor composite	No significant association with surface year exposure: Changes in Neuropsych Test Scores between Baseline and 4yr Follow-up, by Cumulative Exposure to Dental Compomer on Posterior-Occlusal Surfaces, Multivariable-Adjusted Coefficients for Mean (SE) Change Scores. N=255, 4.0 (0.8)
Mikhailichenko 2019 [Retrospective observational] ⁶⁹	Exposure: CRR	Neuropsych:	NS correlation between dementia development and CRR: aOR values were 0.972 and 1.025 for subjects with <8 restorations and >9 restorations, respectively
Study quality: Strong (green shade). ANOVA=Analysis Of Variance, aOR=Adjusted Odds Ratio, CI=Confidence Interval, CRR=Composite Resin Restorations, FSIQ=Full Scale Intelligence Quotient, GMI=General Memory Index, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, PRR=Preventative Resin Restorations, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SE=Standard Error, WCST=Wisconsin Card Sorting Test, WIAT=Wechsler Individual Achievement Test, WISC=Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, WRAML=Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning, yr=Year			

Table 56: Patient composite exposure and oral health

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Ahlgren 2014 [Cross-sectional with control] ⁹	Exposure: Composite in OLL vs DP patients	Oral health: OLL diagnosis (N)	42/74 patients' composite restorations adjacent to lichen lesions. OLL group: mean 14.4 surfaces with composite. DP group: mean surfaces with composite 11.0 (t test: p=.027). In both groups, all patients with composite restorations also had amalgam restorations. Only two patients in OLL group had composite fillings adjacent to lichen lesions and with no amalgam in region. All other patients with composite fillings adjacent to lesions also had amalgam adjacent to or in contact with lesions
Duame 2021 [Cross-sectional with control] ⁷⁰	Exposure: Composite resin	Oral health: Correlation between different dental restorative materials & OLP (correlation coefficient and p value)	Composite restorations sig.correlated with local OLP (0.22* p =.01); However, correlations low and possibly not clinically significant
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Overall summary	When comparing change in periodontal clinical parameters, statistically significant improvement in GI, PI, BOP, GR, KG, GR, KG, and CAL. No statistically significant improvement in PD at six sites per tooth, yet data close to significant (p=.06)b
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Hypersensitivity	When comparing analogous sites in CRR treatment, no statistically significant improvement in DH (means: initial = 7.0 ± 2.0, final = 3.25 ± 3.5, p=.25)
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Gingival index: bleeding on probing	Significant improvement: Mean change baseline-3-month Follow-up 0.63 (0.44) (12 sites)b
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Clinical attachment levels (%)	Significant improvement: Mean change baseline-3 month Follow-up 0.18 (0.31) (12 sites)b
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Probing depth (mm)	NS improvement: Mean change baseline-3 month Follow-up 0.04 (0.41) (12 sites)b
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Gingival recession (mm)	Significant improvement: Mean change baseline-3 month Follow-up 0.04 (0.41) (12 sites)b

Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Plaque Index (mm)	Significant improvement: Mean change baseline-3 month Follow-up 0.08 (0.51) (12sites)b
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁸⁴	CRR vs CTGa	Oral health: Keratinized gingiva	Significant improvement: Mean change baseline-3 month Follow-up 0.35 (0.81) (12 sites)b
Ma 2021 [Retrospective observational: nested case-control] ⁷¹	Exposure: Composite resin restorations individuals with OLP	Oral health: OR of developing OLP for times receiving composite resin restorations (95% CI, P-value)	Composite resin restorations not associated with altered odds of OLP. aORs of OLP onset: 0.809 (95% CI = 0.587–1.116, p=.1972), 0.502 (95% CI = 0.336–0.750, p=.0008)c, and 0.764 (95% CI = 0.541–1.080, p=.1277) in those receiving fillings for 1–2, 3–4, and over 5 times/Yr throughout study, respectively, mean aOR of 1.007 (95% CI = 0.978–1.037, p=.6557) per each additional resin restoration. Subgroup analysis showed no significant relationship between composite restorations on posterior or anterior teeth or OLP [See paper for stats]
Ptak 2023 [Retrospective cohort] ¹¹	Exposure: Amalgam/composite restorations	Oral health: Occurrence pulpal disease, N (%)	NS Association pulpal disease: 96 (8.35%), p>.05 (Frequency: n=1151 (64.7%))
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aNot relevant to this review, bUnclear which group findings pertain to. cOR Adjusted for age, gender, socioeconomic status, comorbidities including systemic diseases and oral diseases such as periodontitis, average dental visits/yr, cumulative times of resin, amalgam fillings, root canal therapy, and tooth extraction BOP=Bleeding on Probing, CAL=Clinical Attachment Levels, CI=Confidence Interval, CRR=Composite Resin Restorations, CTG=Connective Tissue Graft, DH=Dental Hypersensitivity, DP=Dermatitis Patients, GI=Gingival Index, GR=Gingival Recession, KG=Keratinized Gingiva, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, PI=Plaque Index, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus, aOR=Adjusted Odds Ratio, OR=Odds Ratio, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial			

Table 57: Patient composite exposure and psychosocial symptoms

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Aggression	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -1.2(1.1); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.2) p=.66 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1(0.4) p=.66
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Aggression	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.8(1.1). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1 (0.2) p=.60 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.02(0.4) p=.95
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Delinquent behaviours	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -2.1(1.3); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.2(0.2) p=.30 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.9(0.4) p=.05
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Delinquent behaviours	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -1.6(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.2 (0.2) p=.32 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.7(0.5) p=.16
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Withdrawn	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -1.7(1.2); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.003(0.2) p=.99 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1(0.4) p=.77
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Withdrawn	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -1.8(1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.2) p=.06 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.6(0.4) p=.15
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Externalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): 1.0(2.0); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.2(0.3) p=.57 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4(0.6) p=.56
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Externalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 1.6(2.0). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.03 (0.3) p=.92 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(0.7) p=.53
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Total problem behaviours	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -1.7(2.1); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.3) p=.83 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.5(0.67) p=.44

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Behaviour: CBCL Change score: Total problem behaviours	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.8 (2.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1 (0.3) p=.87 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.1(0.7) p=.93
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Behaviour: Core syndrome: Delinquent behaviours (β (SE) P)	Cumulative exposure level to sealants and/or PRRs was not associated with psychosocial assessments. Flowable sealant: -0.1 (0.2) 0.45 . PRRs: 0.1 (0.3) 0.76 . No interactions between sealant/PRR exposure and age, study site, or gender
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Behaviour: Total problem behaviours (β (SE) P)	Cumulative exposure level to sealants and/or PRRs was not associated with psychosocial assessments. Flowable sealant: -0.2 (0.3) 0.50 ; PRRs: -0.1 (0.5) 0.84 . No interactions between sealant/PRR exposure and age, study site, or gender
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: BASC: Clinical maladjustment (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite sealant: -0.2 (0.2) 0.38 . PRR: -0.7 (0.4) 0.12
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: BASC: Emotional symptoms index maladjustment (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite Sealant: -0.3 (0.2) 0.21 . PRR: -0.5 (0.4) 0.24
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: BASC: Personal adjustment (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite sealant: 0.2 (0.2) 0.37 . PRR: 0.3 (0.4) 0.40
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Clinical maladjustment	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: -3.8(2.7). 10 SY Beta (SE): -0.6(0.8) p=.45 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.1(1.5) p=.96
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Clinical maladjustment	Statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -4.5 (2.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.7 (0.4) p=.06 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.6(0.8) p=.04
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Emotional symptoms index	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: -5.4(2.6). 10 SY Beta (SE): -0.7(0.7) p=.32 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(1.4) p=.75

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Emotional symptoms index	Statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -5.9(2.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.8(0.4) p=.02 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.8(0.7) p=.01
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Personal adjustment	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: 0.6(2.8). 10 SY Beta (SE): -0.8(0.8) p=.29 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.4(1.5) p=.34
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR Change Score: Personal adjustment	Statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 0.3(2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): -1.0 (0.4) p=.02 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -2.3 (0.8) p=.004
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 50.4(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.2) p=.62 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.05(0.5) p=.92
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 50.5(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.5(0.2) p=.04 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1,0(0.5) p=.05
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression Change Score	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: -1.4(2.7). 10 SY Beta (SE): -1.3(0.8) p=.09 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.5(1.5) p=.29
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Depression Change Score	Not statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -2.4 (2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE):0.6 (0.4) p=.12 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.9(0.8) p=.26
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Clinical maladjustment	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 46.4(1.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.3) p=.74 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.1(0.6) p=.84

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Adjusted mean (SE) Clinical maladjustment	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 46.6(1.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.7(0.3) p=.02 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.4(0.6) p=.02
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 44.7(1.6). 10-SY Beta (SE):-2.0(0.3) p=.54 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.1(0.6) p=.84
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety	Not statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 44.3(1.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4(0.3) p=.14 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.3(0.5) p=.64
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety Change Score	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97:-6.2(2.8). 10 SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.8) p=.91 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.6(1.5) p=.68
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Anxiety Change Score	Statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -6.4 (2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE):0.7 (0.4) p=.10 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.6(0.8) p=.04
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Personal adjustment	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 50.3(1.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.2(0.2) p=.35 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.8(0.5) p=.14
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Personal adjustment	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 50.5(1.4). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.003(0.2) p=.99 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.8(0.2) p=.002
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Emotional symptoms index	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 46.9(1.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.003(0.2) p=.99 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.3(0.5) p=.60
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: BASC-SR: Emotional symptoms index	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 46.6(1.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.8(0.3) p=.003 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.7(0.5) p=.002

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Anxious/depressed	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -1.5(1.2); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.002(0.2) p=.99 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1(0.4) p=.71
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Core syndromes - Anxious/depressed	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -1.1 (1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.2 (0.2) p=.23 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.8(0.4) p=.07
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Internalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -1.5(2.2); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.1(0.3) p=.87 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.3(0.7) p=.68
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Psychological: CBCL Change score: Internalizing problems	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -0.9(2.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.1 (0.3) p=.72 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.7(0.8) p=.37
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: Competence (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite Sealant: 0.1 (0.3) 0.71 . PRR: 0.2 (0.5) 0.65
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: Core syndrome: Anxious/Depressed (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite sealant: -0.2 (0.2) 0.26 . PRR: 0.3 (0.3) 0.23
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT]	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Psychological: Core syndrome: Withdrawn (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite sealant: -0.1 (0.2) 0.40 . PRR: 0.1 (0.3) 0.83
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Social wellbeing: BASC: School maladjustment (β (SE) P)	No significant association between exposure and score: Composite sealant: -0.2 (0.3) 0.58 . PRR: -0.5 (0.5) 0.35
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR Change Score: School maladjustment	Statistically significant change: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: 0.03(3.0). 10 SY Beta (SE): 1.7(0.8) p=.04 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 3.5(1.6) p=.03
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR Change Score: School maladjustment	Not statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 0.9(2.9). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4 (0.4) p=.36 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.1(0.9) p=.22

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 51.7(1.8). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.4(0.3) p=.18 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(0.7) p=.50
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 51.5(1.8). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.8(0.3) p=.02 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.8(0.7) p=.24
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school Change Score	Statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: -0.7(3.4). 10 SY Beta (SE): 1.5(0.9) p=.10 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.4(1.8) p=.03
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Attitude to school Change Score	Not statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): -6.4 (2.6). 10-SY Beta (SE): (3.2) 0.8(0.5) p=.08 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 1.4(1.0) p=.16
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 52.5(1.3). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.2(0.2) p=.44 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.5(0.4) p=.26
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations	Statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 52.8(1.2). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.6(0.2) p=.005 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -1.5(0.5) p=.001
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations Change Score	Not statistically significant: (among children age 8 y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE), N=97: 3.5(2.6). 10 SY Beta (SE): 0.4(0.7) p=.57 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.05(1.4) p=.97
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: Core syndromes - Interpersonal relations Change Score	Statistically significant: N=85. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 3.0 (2.5). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.7 (0.4) p=.05 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.7(0.4) p=.03

Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: School maladjustment	Not statistically significant: n=182. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 52.4(2.8). 10-sy Beta (SE): -0.3(0.3) p=.37 . Posterior occlusal sy: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.4(0.6) p=.58
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: BASC-SR: School maladjustment	Not statistically significant: n=204. Psychosocial function score, by cumulative exposure (Surface years) Year 5 T-Score, adjusted mean (SE): 52.5(1.7). 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.5(0.3) p=.07 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): 0.5(0.7) p=.42
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [UDMA-based Compomer, primary teeth]	Social wellbeing: CBCL Change score: Competence	Not statistically significant: N=155. Change Score adjusted mean (SE): -0.4(2.3); Total 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4(0.3) p=.20 . Posterior-Occlusal 10-SY Beta (SE): 0.4(0.6) p=.55
Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁷³	Health [BisGMA-based Composite, permanent teeth]	Social wellbeing: CBCL Change score: Competence	Not statistically significant: N=178. BASC-SR Change Score (among children age 8y or over at baseline), adjusted mean (SE): 0.3 (2.3). 10-SY Beta (SE): -0.5 (0.3) p=.10 . Posterior occlusal SY: 10 surface years Beta (SE): -0.5(0.7) p=.47
Study quality: Strong (green shade). BASC=Behaviour Assessment Scale for Children, BPA=Bisphenol-A, BisGMA=Bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate, CBCL=Child Behaviour Check List, CI=Confidence Interval, N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, PRR=Preventative Resin Restoration, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SD=Standard Deviation, SE=Standard Error, SY=Surface Years, UDMA=Urethane Dimethacrylate			

Table 58: Patient composite exposure and other

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Hu 2021 [Retrospective observational - Nested case-control] ⁸⁵	Composite vs No composite	ADHD: Overall risk of ADHD	Significant difference between groups: After adjusting for age, patients with CRR higher risk ADHD than patients without (aOR = 1.25; 95% CI = 1.13–1.38). Adjusted OR CRR for ADHD was 1.14 (95% CI = 0.92–1.41) and 1.29 (95% CI = 1.14–1.43) for non-CRRs for females and males, respectively
Hu 2021 [Retrospective observational - Nested case-control] ⁸⁵	Composite vs No composite	ADHD: Risk of ADHD according to time since first restoration placement	OR for time interval from first CRR to index date with ADHD: Logistic regression analysis: risk ADHD 1.19-fold within 1yr after CRR (95% CI, 1.04–1.35) and 1.25-fold after 1yr (95% CI, 1.14–1.37) vs no CRR. Positive association with an increased time interval up to 3yrs from first CRR
Hu 2021 [Retrospective observational - Nested case-control] ⁸⁵	Composite vs No composite	ADHD: Risk of ADHD according to number of restorations	OR for no.CRRs of those with ADHD: The ORs of children with 1–3 times, 4–7 times, 8–11 times, and ≥1 2 times CRRs were 1.19 , 1.08, 1.10, and 1.24 -fold risk of ADHD, respectively. Children with 4–7 times and 8–11 times CRRs did not reach the statistical significance . Results did not reveal positive association with increase in no.CRR
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Anthropomorphic: BMI and body fat, %	No significant associations between sealant/PRR exposure levels and changes in BMI or body fat% for girls or boys
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁸³	Flowable sealant/Preventative resin restorations vs NA	Female health overall summary: Age of menarche (yrs)	No significant difference: Among girls, menarche occurred slightly later with greater exposure to sealants/PRRs (age-adjusted hazard ratio=0.91, 95% CI 0.83, 1.01; p=.08
Woods 2009 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁸⁶	Amalgam	General physical health: Urinary porphyrin (µg/L)	No effects of treatment mean concentrations of uro- (8-carboxyl), hepta- (7-carboxyl), or hexa- (6-carboxyl) porphyrins. Mean concentrations penta-, precopro-, and coproporphyrins slightly elevated among amalgam-treated subjects, particularly at follow-up yr 3yr corresponding to highest urinary Hg concentrations. Not statistically sig.due to small N each group. PROGRESS-PLUS: No sig. effects of race (black vs white) on porphyrin excretion in children and adolescents with/without amalgam treatment. Comparable treatment effects all year's follow-up among boys/girls 8–9 yr at baseline, with amalgam treatment-specific increases in penta-, precopro- and coproporphyrin, (porphyrins sensitive to Hg exposure). No statistically significant interaction observed between gender/follow-up year over time. Effects greater for 8-9 yr old at baseline who showed treatment-specific increases in penta-, precopro-, and coproporphyrins that were most apparent during yr 2 through 3 of follow-up vs RBC
Woods 2009 [RCT-Casa Pia] ⁸⁶	Amalgam vs CR	General physical health: Urinary porphyrin (µg/L)	No sig. effects amalgam treatment on mean concentrations of uro- (8-carboxyl), hepta- (7-carboxyl), or hexa- (6-carboxyl) porphyrins found. NS elevation mean concentrations of penta-, precopro-, and coproporphyrins among amalgam-treated subjects, particularly at yr 3 follow up which was year corresponding to highest urinary Hg concentrations. These effects most pronounced for younger subjects (8-9 yr old at baseline). Children 8 to 9 yr old at baseline showed treatment-specific increases in penta-, precopro-, and coproporphyrins that were most apparent during yr 2 through 3 of follow-up, vs composite group. None of these changes statistically

			<p>significant due to small N in each group. PROGRESS-PLUS: PROGRESS-PLUS: No sig. effects of race (black vs white) on porphyrin excretion in children and adolescents with/without amalgam treatment. Comparable treatment effects all year's follow-up among boys/girls 8-9 yr at baseline, with amalgam treatment-specific increases in penta-, precopro- and coproporphyrin, (porphyrins sensitive to Hg exposure). No statistically significant interaction observed between gender/follow-up year over time</p>
<p>Study quality: Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, BMI=Body Mass Index, CI=Confidence Interval, CRR=Composite Resin Restoration, PRR=Preventative Resin Restoration, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial, SD=Standard Deviation,</p>			

Glass ionomer vs composite resin/compomer

Table 59: Glass ionomer cement - all outcomes

Study [Study Design]	Restoration material/exposure	Broad impact category: Specific outcomes measured (Unit)	Outcome details
Lin 2017 [Retrospective cohort] ¹⁵	Glass ionomer vs amalgam vs composite	ADHD: Incidence rate	ADHD incidence rate for amalgam restorations was 33.3/100 000 person-years, similar to 31.5/100 000 person-years for people with composite resin or glass ionomer restorations (p=.19). 10-year ADHD hazard probability for amalgam restorations: 0.028 vs 0.025 for composite resin or glass ionomer restorations (p=.19). Cox proportional hazard regression analysis: crude HR for ADHD 1.06-fold higher for people with amalgam restorations (95% CI=0.97-1.15, p=.19) than composite resin or glass ionomer restorations. After adjustment for potential confounding factors (ie age, sex, number of tooth restorations during 2002-2011, fluoride varnish application, medical institution, urbanization level and systemic diseases), adjusted HR for ADHD amalgam restorations: 1.05 (95% CI=0.96-1.14, p=.27 ; in univariate Cox model, those with 6 or more amalgam restorations higher risk of future ADHD (HR=1.20, 95% CI=1.04-1.38, p=.015) vs composite resin or glass ionomer restorations. However, multivariate model revealed risk of future ADHD in these people similar to people with other restorations (HR=1.00, 95% CI=0.86-1.15, p=.97). All study population with amalgam restorations: a N=44 034 Univariate: Hazard ratio: 1.06 95% CI: 0.97-1.15 p=.19 . Multivariate: Hazard ratio: 1.05, 95% CI: 0.96-1.14 p=.27 . [Subgroup analysis data reported table 2]
Dermata 2018 [RCT] ⁸⁷	Health (Composite resin Z250 vs GIC-Vitremer)	Oral health: Gingival health (USPHS criteria), N (%)	Statistically sig. differences favouring Vitremer at 12 and 24-months (RR=0.24; P=.03). 12 months: Z250 vs Vitremer- Rating A: 46 (85%) vs 58 (100%), Rating B: 8 (15%) vs 0 (0%), Rating C 0(0%) vs 0 (0%) p=.002. 24 months: Rating A: 34 (74%) vs 51 (94%), Rating B: 12 (26%) vs 3 (6%), Rating C: 0(0%) vs 0 (0%) p=.005
Gavic 2019 [RCT] ⁸¹	GIC- Ketac Molar	Genotoxicity: DNA damage at same time point (n micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis) (Frequency)	NS frequency changes in no. binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, and karyorrhexis. Statistically sig. difference in frequency micronuclei in samples taken 30d following restoration (p=.027). No sig. difference: samples collected 7 and 90d following restoration
	GIC- Ionofil Molar	Genotoxicity: DNA damage at same time point (n micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis) (Frequency)	NS frequency changes in no. micronucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, and karyorrhexis. Sig. difference no. binucleated cells samples taken 30d following restoration (p=.029)
	Compomer vs GIC-Ketac Molar) vs GIC-Ionofil Molar	Genotoxicity: DNA damage at same time point (n micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis) (Frequency)	NS difference between three tested materials during same time of exposure for these parameters, EXCEPT Sig. difference: no. of binucleated cells in samples taken 7a days following restoration with Twinkly Star and Ketac Molar (p=.010). PROGRESS-PLUS: Gender: Only gender displayed connection to no. nucleoplasmic bridges ($\beta=-0.301$, p=.039). Greatest no. tested factors had sig.effect on karyorrhexis occurrence: gender ($\beta=-0.292$, p=.033). Age: Significantly impacts occurrence binuclear cells ($\beta=-0.328$, p=.022)
Study quality: Weak (red shade), Moderate (yellow shade), Strong (green shade). aGraph indicates sig difference between twinkly star and Ketac molar (higher value for twinkly star) at 30 days post restoration. ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, CI=Confidence Interval, D=Days, GIC-Glass Ionomer Cement, N=Number, NS=Non-Significant, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trial			

References

1. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Barregard L, et al. Neuropsychological and renal effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1775-83.
2. DeRouen TA, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Neurobehavioral effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1784-92.
3. Roberts MC, Leroux BG, Sampson J, et al. Dental amalgam and antibiotic- and/or mercury-resistant bacteria. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(5):475-9.
4. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Brown OA, et al. Dental sealants and composite restorations and longitudinal changes in immune function markers in children. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2014;24(3):215-25.
5. Shenker BJ, Maserejian NN, Zhang A, McKinlay S. Immune function effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(11):1496-505.
6. Perng WT, Ma KS, Hung HY, et al. Dental caries and risk of newly-onset systemic lupus erythematosus: a nationwide population-based cohort study. *Curr Med Res Opin*. 2023;39(2):307-17.
7. Lauterbach M, Martins IP, Castro-Caldas A, et al. Neurological outcomes in children with and without amalgam-related mercury exposure: seven years of longitudinal observations in a randomized trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(2):138-45.
8. Bellinger DC, Daniel D, Trachtenberg F, et al. Dental amalgam restorations and children's neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2007;115(3):440-6.
9. Ahlgren C, Axell T, Moller H, et al. Contact allergies to potential allergens in patients with oral lichen lesions. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2014;18(1):227-37.
10. Halperin-Sternfeld M, Saminsky M, Machtei EE, Horwitz J. The association between dental proximal restorations and periodontal disease: A retrospective 10-18 years longitudinal study. *Quintessence Int*. 2016;47(3):249-59.
11. Ptak DM, Solanki A, Andler L, et al. The Pulpal Response to Crown Preparation and Cementation. *J Endod*. 2023;49(5):462-8.
12. Barregard L, Trachtenberg F, McKinlay S. Renal effects of dental amalgam in children: the New England children's amalgam trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2008;116(3):394-9.
13. Martin MD, Woods JS, Leroux BG, et al. Longitudinal urinary creatinine excretion values among preadolescents and adolescents. *Transl Res*. 2008;151(1):51-6.
14. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Biomarkers of kidney integrity in children and adolescents with dental amalgam mercury exposure: findings from the Casa Pia children's amalgam trial. *Environ Res*. 2008;108(3):393-9.
15. Lin PY, Wang J, Chiang YC, et al. Risk of subsequent attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder among children and adolescents with amalgam restorations: A nationwide longitudinal study. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2018;46(1):47-53.
16. Maserejian NN, Hauser R, Tavares M, et al. Dental composites and amalgam and physical development in children. *J Dent Res*. 2012;91(11):1019-25.

17. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Zhang A, et al. Dental amalgam and psychosocial status: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(5):470-4.
18. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Biometals*. 2011;24(2):215-24.
19. Duplinsky Thomas G, Cicchetti Domenic V. The Health Status of Dentists Exposed to Mercury from Silver Amalgam Tooth Restorations. *International Journal Of Statistics In Medical Research*. 2012;1(1):1-15.
20. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive symptoms in dental assistants with previous occupational exposure to metallic mercury. *Neurotoxicology*. 2009;30(6):1202-6.
21. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive and neurological symptoms in norwegian dentists. *Saf Health Work*. 2011;2(2):176-82.
22. Jones L, Bunnell J, Stillman J. A 30-year follow-up of residual effects on New Zealand School Dental Nurses, from occupational mercury exposure. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2007;26(4):367-74.
23. Franzblau A, d'Arcy H, Ishak MB, et al. Low-level mercury exposure and peripheral nerve function. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(3):299-306.
24. Thygesen LC, Flachs EM, Hanehoj K, et al. Hospital admissions for neurological and renal diseases among dentists and dental assistants occupationally exposed to mercury. *Occup Environ Med*. 2011;68(12):895-901.
25. Heratizadeh A, Werfel T, Schubert S, et al. Contact sensitization in dental technicians with occupational contact dermatitis. Data of the Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) 2001-2015. *Contact Dermatitis*. 2018;78(4):266-73.
26. Lygre GB, Aase H, Haug K, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and risk of symptoms of attention-deficit and hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2018;46(5):472-81.
27. Adams JB, Romdalvik J, Levine KE, Hu LW. Mercury in first-cut baby hair of children with autism versus typically-developing children. *Toxicological & Environmental Chemistry*. 2008;90(4):739-53.
28. Watson GE, Lynch M, Myers GJ, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam: evidence from the Seychelles Child Development Study main cohort. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2011;142(11):1283-94.
29. Watson GE, Evans K, Thurston SW, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam in the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study: associations with neurodevelopmental outcomes at 9 and 30 months. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(6):1511-7.
30. Daniels JL, Rowland AS, Longnecker MP, et al. Maternal dental history, child's birth outcome and early cognitive development. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2007;21(5):448-57.
31. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh Englund G, Ekbohm A, et al. Cognitive function among sons of women who worked in dentistry. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2012;38(6):546-52.
32. Watson GE, van Wijngaarden E, Love TM, et al. Neurodevelopmental outcomes at 5 years in children exposed prenatally to maternal dental amalgam: the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*. 2013;39:57-62.
33. Bjorkman L, Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R. Perinatal death and exposure to dental amalgam fillings during pregnancy in the population-based MoBa cohort. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(12):e0208803.

34. Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R, Bjorkman L. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and pregnancy outcome. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2016;44(5):442-9.
35. Lindbohm ML, Ylostalo P, Sallmen M, et al. Occupational exposure in dentistry and miscarriage. *Occup Environ Med.* 2007;64(2):127-33.
36. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh-Englund G, Ekbohm A, et al. Mortality among sons of female dental personnel--a national cohort study. *J Perinat Med.* 2014;42(5):655-61.
37. Hegglund I, Irgens A, Tollanes M, et al. Pregnancy outcomes among female dental personnel--a registry-based retrospective cohort study. *Scand J Work Environ Health.* 2011;37(6):539-46.
38. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Mercury, silver and selenium in serum before and after removal of amalgam restorations: results from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2023;81(4):298-310.
39. Bjorkman L, Sjursen TT, Dalen K, et al. Long term changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam restorations. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2017;75(3):208-19.
40. Melchart D, Vogt S, Kohler W, et al. Treatment of health complaints attributed to amalgam. *J Dent Res.* 2008;87(4):349-53.
41. Sjursen TT, Lygre GB, Dalen K, et al. Changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam fillings. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2011;38(11):835-48.
42. Eyeson J, House I, Yang YH, Warnakulasuriya KA. Relationship between mercury levels in blood and urine and complaints of chronic mercury toxicity from amalgam restorations. *Br Dent J.* 2010;208(4):E7; discussion 162-3.
43. Forkel S, Schubert S, Corvin L, et al. Contact allergies to dental materials in patients. *Br J Dermatol.* 2024;190(6):895-903.
44. Rojas-Alcayaga G, Carrasco-Labra A, Danus P, et al. Determination of susceptibility to sensitization to dental materials in atopic and non-atopic patients. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2012;17(2):e320-4.
45. Weber ME, Yiannias JA, Hougeir FG, et al. Intraoral metal contact allergy as a possible risk factor for oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol.* 2012;121(6):389-94.
46. Lartitegui-Sebastian MJ, Martinez-Revilla B, Saiz-Garcia C, et al. Oral lichenoid lesions associated with amalgam restorations: a prospective pilot study addressing the adult population of the Basque Country. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2012;17(4):e545-9.
47. Lynch M, Ryan A, Galvin S, et al. Patch testing in oral lichenoid lesions of uncertain etiology. *Dermatitis.* 2015;26(2):89-93.
48. Marell L, Tillberg A, Widman L, et al. Regression of oral lichenoid lesions after replacement of dental restorations. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2014;41(5):381-91.
49. Pezelj-Ribaric S, Prpic J, Miletic I, et al. Association between oral lichenoid reactions and amalgam restorations. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2008;22(10):1163-7.
50. Sinha N, Hamre HJ, Musial F, et al. Health complaints before and at one and five years after removal of dental amalgam restorations - data from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2024;83:219-29.
51. Suter VG, Warnakulasuriya S. The role of patch testing in the management of oral lichenoid reactions. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 2016;45(1):48-57.
52. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Cognitive status in persons with amalgam-related complaints. *J Dent Res.* 2010;89(11):1236-40.
53. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Stressful negative life events and amalgam-related complaints. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2011;39(1):12-8.

54. Weidenhammer W, Hausteiner C, Zilker T, et al. Does a specific dental amalgam syndrome exist? A comparative study. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2009;67(4):233-9.
55. Lygre GB, Sjørusen TT, Svahn J, et al. Characterization of health complaints before and after removal of amalgam fillings--3-year follow-up. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2013;71(3-4):560-9.
56. Zwicker JD, Dutton DJ, Emery JC. Longitudinal analysis of the association between removal of dental amalgam, urine mercury and 14 self-reported health symptoms. *Environ Health*. 2014;13:95.
57. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Removal of dental amalgam restorations in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam: A prospective cohort study. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2020;47(11):1422-34.
58. Naimi-Akbar A, Svedberg P, Alexanderson K, et al. Health-related quality of life and symptoms in patients with experiences of health problems related to dental restorative materials. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2013;41(2):163-72.
59. Weidenhammer W, Bornschein S, Zilker T, et al. Predictors of treatment outcomes after removal of amalgam fillings: associations between subjective symptoms, psychometric variables and mercury levels. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2010;38(2):180-9.
60. Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Analysis of dental amalgam fillings on primary Sjogren's syndrome: A population-based case-control study in Taiwan. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021;100(47):e28031.
61. Bjorkman L, Brokstad KA, Moen K, Jonsson R. Minor changes in serum levels of cytokines after removal of amalgam restorations. *Toxicol Lett*. 2012;211(2):120-5.
62. Frisk P, Danersund A, Hudecek R, Lindh U. Changed clinical chemistry pattern in blood after removal of dental amalgam and other metal alloys supported by antioxidant therapy. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2007;120(1-3):163-70.
63. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, et al. Dental Amalgam Fillings and Multiple Sclerosis: A Nationwide Population-Based Case-Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(8).
64. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Association between Dental Amalgam Filling and Essential Tremor: A Nationwide Population-Based Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(3).
65. Chen KH. Association between Parkinson's Disease and Dental Amalgam Filling: A Study of Nationwide Population-Based Case Control in Taiwan. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*. 2020;18(5):7159-65.
66. Hsu YC, Chang CW, Lee HL, et al. Association between History of Dental Amalgam Fillings and Risk of Parkinson's Disease: A Population-Based Retrospective Cohort Study in Taiwan. *PLoS One*. 2016;11(12):e0166552.
67. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Daniel D, et al. A dose-effect analysis of children's exposure to dental amalgam and neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2007;138(9):1210-6.
68. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and neuropsychological development in children: treatment level analysis from a randomized clinical trial. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(5):1291-7.
69. Mikhailichenko N, Yagami K, Chiou JY, et al. Exposure to Dental Filling Materials and the Risk of Dementia: A Population-Based Nested Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(18).

70. Daume L, Kreis C, Bohner L, et al. Clinical characteristics of oral lichen planus and its causal context with dental restorative materials and oral health-related quality of life. *BMC Oral Health*. 2021;21(1):262.
71. Ma KS, Thota E, Huang JY, et al. Onset of oral lichen planus following dental treatments: A nested case-control study. *Oral Dis*. 2023;29(3):1269-81.
72. Montebugnoli L, Venturi M, Gissi DB, Cervellati F. Clinical and histologic healing of lichenoid oral lesions following amalgam removal: a prospective study. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol*. 2012;113(6):766-72.
73. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function in children. *Pediatrics*. 2012;130(2):e328-38.
74. Wright B, Pearce H, Allgar V, et al. A comparison of urinary mercury between children with autism spectrum disorders and control children. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(2):e29547.
75. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant dose-dependent relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and kidney integrity biomarkers: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2013;32(4):434-40.
76. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Bravo-Gonzalez LA, et al. Increased Zn/Glutathione Levels and Higher Superoxide Dismutase-1 Activity as Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in Women with Long-Term Dental Amalgam Fillings: Correlation between Mercury/Aluminium Levels (in Hair) and Antioxidant Systems in Plasma. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(6):e0126339.
77. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Camacho Alonso F, Merino JJ. Increased Systemic Malondialdehyde Levels and Decreased Mo/Co, Co/Fe(2+) Ratios in Patients with Long-Term Dental Titanium Implants and Amalgams. *J Clin Med*. 2019;8(1).
78. Louopou RC, Trottier H, Arbuckle TE, Fraser WD. Dental amalgams and risk of gestational hypertension in the MIREC study. *Pregnancy Hypertens*. 2020;21:84-9.
79. Piagno H, Afshari R. Mercury from crematoriums: human health risk assessment and estimate of total emissions in British Columbia. *Can J Public Health*. 2020;111(6):1011-9.
80. Pettini F, Savino M, Corsalini M, et al. Cytogenetic genotoxic investigation in peripheral blood lymphocytes of subjects with dental composite restorative filling materials. *J Biol Regul Homeost Agents*. 2015;29(1):229-33.
81. Gavic L, Gorseta K, Glavina D, et al. In vivo assessment of genotoxicity in buccal cells of children undergoing tooth restoration. *Cent Eur J Public Health*. 2019;27(4):312-9.
82. Tadin A, Galic N, Mladinic M, et al. Genotoxicity in gingival cells of patients undergoing tooth restoration with two different dental composite materials. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2014;18(1):87-96.
83. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Trachtenberg FL, et al. Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations and psychosocial, neuropsychological, and physical development in children. *Pediatr Dent*. 2014;36(1):68-75.
84. Leybovich M, Bissada NF, Teich S, et al. Treatment of noncarious cervical lesions by a subepithelial connective tissue graft versus a composite resin restoration. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent*. 2014;34(5):649-54.
85. Hu CJ, Yu HC, Chang YC. Investigation of the Impact of Dental Care via Composite Resin Restoration among Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: A Registry-Based Nested Case-Control Study. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2021;9(7).

86. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Urinary porphyrin excretion in children with mercury amalgam treatment: findings from the Casa Pia Children's Dental Amalgam Trial. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*. 2009;72(14):891-6.
87. Dermata A, Papageorgiou SN, Fragkou S, Kotsanos N. Comparison of resin modified glass ionomer cement and composite resin in class II primary molar restorations: a 2-year parallel randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*. 2018;19(6):393-401.